

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH
AND MODELLING

D6.7 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impact – update M34

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Executive Summary

This report provides an update of D6.3 “*D6.3 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impacts,*” which aimed at describing and assessing community and citizen responses during the initial phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. The report has identified, summarised and compiled the key findings from the D6.1, “*Baseline report: Community and citizen responses,*” D6.5, “*Baseline report: Community and citizen responses - update M24,*” and the WP6 expert interviews that were conducted by COVINFORM target countries within the context of WP6 research activities until July 2023 (note that information regarding the updated expert interview guidelines can be found in D6.2, “*Research design: Community and citizen responses*” and D6.6, “*Research design: Community and citizen responses - update M28*”).

As stated in D6.3, it is important to conduct further in-depth empirical research and analysis of the findings which relate to community and citizen responses and impacts during the three distinct COVID-19 phases. D6.7 is the second iteration of D6.3, which provided an initial descriptive analysis of the findings of interviews conducted with representatives of civil society organisations and grassroots initiatives active in COVID-19 responses. Similarly to the preceding Deliverable, D6.7 also examines the cases of ten municipalities: Vienna, Austria; Antwerp, Belgium; Birmingham, England; Mannheim, Germany; Athens, Greece; Rome, Italy; Lisbon, Portugal; Madrid, Spain; Gothenburg, Sweden; and Swansea, Wales (UK). It furthermore reports findings for sites in which too few data had been conducted as of the time of D6.3 submission.

The scope of this deliverable is municipal/sub-municipal: it explores the way that local conditions and actors in target cities and neighbourhoods across COVINFORM countries mediated the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, and simultaneously contributed in shaping the relevant responses to it.

Similarly to D6.3, this report has explored the following three dimensions of Community and citizen responses:

- 1) Local baseline conditions
- 2) Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)
- 3) Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

In order to provide a holistic understanding of these dimensions, COVINFORM partners have identified relevant data within the WP6 expert interviews with representatives of civil society organisations and grassroots initiatives (as first reported in D6.3), as well as data collected during two phases of desk research (as first reported in D6.1 and D6.5). COVINFORM partners adhered to a standardised template in order to guide the extraction of the relevant data within the aforementioned dimensions across target countries (see Annex 1). The countries under study are Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales.

The current report includes an Introductory chapter (Chapter 1), which is followed by an overview of the methods utilised to conduct the empirical research (Chapter 2). Then, an analysis is provided of the three dimensions across all the COVINFORM countries (Chapter 3). The aforementioned dimensions will predominantly emphasise commonalities and disparities identified across the COVINFORM target countries in terms of civil society organisation and citizen responses during the three distinct pandemic phases (T0, T1 and T2). The findings of D6.7 will be explored in further detail within the context of D6.8 deliverable “*Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen*”

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responses and impacts – update” due in M36. Finally, the last chapter (Chapter 4) presents lessons learnt that have been identified in relation to the three dimensions of this report.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
CSO	Civil society organisation
RQ	Research Question(s)
D	Deliverable
M	Month
LGA	Local Governments Association
MAGs	Mutual Aid Groups
SCVS	Swansea Council for Voluntary Service
NHS	National Health System
BAME	Black, Asian, and minority ethnic
PEMAM	Plan Territorial de Emergencia Municipal del Ayuntamiento de Madrid
EYST	Ethnic Minorities & Youth Support Team
GO	Governmental Organisations
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisations
AML	Área Metropolitana de Lisboa
F2F	Face-to-Face
GDP	Gross domestic product
VCFSE	Voluntary, Community, Faith, and Social Enterprise sector
WMCA	West Midlands Combined Area
CMC	Municipality of Cascais
WP	Work Package(s)
GRT	Gypsy Roma Travellers
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
SES	Socio-Ecological System Framework

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides an update of D6.3, *D6.3 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impacts*, which aimed at describing and assessing community and citizen responses during the initial phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. In D6.3, three thematic areas were explored to identify and comprehend community and citizen responses and impacts in the COVINFORM target countries:

- 1) Local baseline conditions
- 2) COVID-19 impact timelines
- 3) Local multi-stakeholder responses

In D6.7, besides providing the second iteration of the examination of the aforementioned thematic areas, the consortium conducts more in-depth analysis of findings that relate to vulnerability, the emergence of new vulnerabilities that relate to COVID-19, and how CSOs and citizen grassroots initiatives have responded to vulnerable target groups.

The scope of the second iteration is to review and describe community structures and stakeholder networks, local implementations and impacts of governmental responses, and voluntary and citizen-led responses in selected sub-national research sites. It is based on the research conducted for D6.1 'Baseline report Community and citizen responses', D6.3 'Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impacts', and D6.5 "Baseline report: Community and citizen responses - update M24". The main objective of D6.7, as the second iteration of D6.3, is to report on the empirical research conducted with CSO representatives in the sub-national research sites as of Spring 2022 until Summer of 2023. This deliverable integrates data and main findings drawn from interviews that were conducted despite challenges in recruiting CSO representatives during the overlapping COVID-19 and Ukraine crises.

The following list includes some of the main lessons learned and good practices that emerged from the analysis of D6.7:

- 1) The pandemic has increased the size of the vulnerable population and aggravated the situation of those who were already worse off.
- 2) Civil society organisations have played an important role in the response to the pandemic, collaborating with other institutions and social actors.
- 3) A number of solidarity initiatives have been carried out in COVINFORM countries, such as the creation of neighbourhood support networks, the distribution of food and hygiene products, and care for the elderly and vulnerable.
- 4) The pandemic has highlighted the importance of addressing precarious working conditions and the need to strengthen social protection systems.
- 5) Existing networks between local authorities and CSOs were very effective in setting up a variety of support activities for particular communities, so these need to be fostered by authorities in preparation of new societal disruptions.
- 6) In several countries, there was a rise of reported racist incidents when the news broke that segregated social groups such as BAME people suffered more disproportionately and were thus seen as more vulnerable than white populations. Such social developments need to be anticipated and avoided.
- 7) Gender roles and existing socio-economic differences between men and women were prone to cause deeper inequalities for already disadvantaged groups. As a decision was made across WP4-7 to focus general population research on vulnerable women, particular profiles of vulnerable women are identified, such as second-generation migrants, single-parent

households, women who are responsible for two families, women who come from third countries and are not fluent in the native language, particularly young women who arrived just before the pandemic, and older women who have lost their jobs.

- 8) In some cases, low trust in societal institutions affects the implementation of health campaigns in a negative way, in this case the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, including trust in politicians, news media and authorities on all administrative levels, also health care authorities. This distrust tends to hinder proper integration, as well as the migrant residents' ability to accept important health related information.
- 9) Another key lesson is that information efforts reached out but not into immigrant-dense neighbourhoods. Meaning that information about the pandemic reached the residents of these areas, but the messages and the call for preventive actions were questioned more and followed less than in the majority community. Despite information in more than 20 different languages, local health centres and vaccination centres, particularly in cases such as Sweden, in 2020 the spread of infection was higher and the vaccination rate lower in these areas. One factor that significantly contributed to raising the vaccination rates in 2021 was so-called "vaccination guides", i.e., locally recruited people who mastered several languages and with similar cultural and ethnic backgrounds as the residents of the area. These guides were locally known and therefore trusted by the residents. They managed to fill the gap between local civil society and public authorities in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic.

2 Methodology

This deliverable addresses knowledge gaps that have been identified in D6.3, by providing an update of the initial findings that are presented in the D6.3 report. Besides utilising data drawn from the baseline report D6.1, “*Baseline report: Community and citizen responses*”, this report also incorporated data from the updated baseline report D6.5, “*Baseline report: Community and citizen responses - update M24*,” and WP6 expert interviews that were conducted with representatives of civil society organisations and grassroots initiatives. In D6.3, it was indicated that those partners who were unable to conduct the required N=5 interviews by the date of submission would do so in the following months. The following table indicates the interviews conducted per site. All additional interview findings have been integrated into this report.

Site	Interviews conducted prior to May 2022 and reported in D6.3	Additional interviews conducted after May 2022 and integrated into the present report
Austria (Vienna)	3	2
Belgium (Antwerp)	3	2
England (Birmingham)	0	5
Germany (Mannheim)	5	0
Greece (Athens)	5	0
Italy (Rome)	4	1
Portugal (Lisbon)	5	0
Spain (Madrid)	5	0
Sweden (Gothenburg)	4	1
Wales (Swansea)	4	1

In order to achieve the overarching objectives that were identified in D6.6, this report (D6.7) has implemented an updated analytical approach, examining three distinct pandemic phases:

- T0: Baseline until the pandemic outbreak
- T1: COVID-19 outbreak until vaccination rollout
- T2: Vaccination until current date

Moreover, D6.7 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impact – update M34 takes into consideration of the COVINFORM overarching research questions:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response of certain vulnerable groups?
- RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?

- RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

This report conducts an in-depth examination of three thematic areas and their respective subjections:

- **Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)**
- **Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)**

T1 = from the beginning of the pandemic until vaccination began to have an effect on policy

T2 = starting when vaccination began to have an effect on policy, until now

- **How CSOs contributed to crisis management in the research site during the period T1.**
- **How CSO responses changed between T1 and T2, and what factors may have driven those changes.**
- **Examples of participatory practices that emerged in the research sites and practices that involved “ordinary people” in an active way.**
- **Local impacts of governmental responses in the research sites, occurrence of unintended impacts, gaps in governmental responses, and how CSOs and/or participatory practices filled the aforementioned gaps.**
- **Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management**
- **The vulnerable groups that interviewees’ CSOs work with changes in CSO target groups between T1 and T2.**
- **Changes in existing vulnerabilities, emergence of new vulnerabilities and relevant CSO responses to address these changes.**

The information that is presented in this deliverable is complimented by country frameworks which implement Ostrom’s Social-Ecological System framework (Annex 2). The SES framework is known as an empirically applied conceptual framework which is utilised to analyse complex social systems; an explanation of the SES framework methodology can be found in D3.2, “*Multi-site research design and methodological framework*”. More details on the methodology can be found in D6.6, “*Research design: Community and citizen responses - update M28*”. In conclusion, this report will lay the foundation for D6.8 which will explore the identified findings further and specifically answer overarching research questions by conducting synthesis of findings and documenting the lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts.

3 Country Reports

The following ten country reports present the basis for the analysis of the COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of WP6: civil society response. These country reports will be taken up in the D6.8 deliverable to answer the overarching research questions in a cross-country analysis and synthesis. The overall aim is to holistically and critically reflect upon all data that have been acquired within the context of the research activities conducted in WP6 and summarise the main findings. Moreover, these country reports will also be explored further in D6.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts – update M36, that will answer the aforementioned overarching research questions of the COVINFORM project.

3.1 Austria

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

Vienna is both the capital city of **Austria** and a state in its own right, as part of the federal state system of Austria. It has its own municipal government and is also home to the national government. The social democrats have consistently nominated the mayor of Vienna since 1945. With a population of just over 1.980.000 Vienna is not only the city with the largest population, but also the most populated state in Austria¹. One of the factors contributing to the demographic changes in Vienna has been the population with a migration background. They have played a role in both population growth and the age structure of the city. Almost half (42.6%) of Vienna's population had a migration background in 2022.² Economically, Vienna plays an important role in Austria. With a gross regional product of around 100 billion euros, it is responsible for more than a quarter of Austria's economic output. The basis of Vienna's economic power is the service sector, which accounts for more than 85 percent of Vienna's economic output, and in addition trade and business-related services.³

The report is based on the activities of four CSOs based in Vienna and on interviews with their members. CSO 1 works for a city-wide women's support organisation focused on helping migrant women of Muslim background. They offer assistance on human rights issues, domestic concerns, and provide German classes to illiterate women. CSO 2 advises individuals facing financial hardship at a transnational aid organisation. They provide short-term financial support for rent, energy bills, and other expenses, primarily assisting migrants, excluding students and asylum-seekers. CSO 3 manages a transnational aid organisation's services for homeless people and refugees in Austria. Their role involves overseeing budgets, proposals, and organisational matters related to social support, particularly during the COVID-19 response. CSO 4 was founded in 2015 and focuses on supporting and accommodating refugees. The goal is to foster interaction and engagement between refugees and the local community. The organisation has a football team, a cooking group, a swimming group and a theatre group.

¹ <https://wien1x1.at/bevoelkerungsentwicklung-2022/>.

² <https://www.wien.gv.at/menschen/integration/daten-fakten/bevoelkerung-migration.html>.

³ <https://www.wko.at/service/w/zahlen-daten-fakten/Wiener-Wirtschaft-in-Zahlen-2021.pdf>.

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

In **Austria** the CSOs were not directly involved in the crisis management. However, they took on important roles in supporting vulnerable community members. During the first phase of the pandemic, the interviewed CSOs had to adapt their everyday habits, but things gradually returned to normal after the initial lockdown. However, all four organizations experienced disruptions in their operations. Three organizations had to switch to remote work, communicating with clients through phone or email instead of their usual face-to-face interactions. The shift to remote work posed challenges for CSOs and their target groups, who do not always have access to technology or internet, or who lack the skills to use it.

“At the beginning of the pandemic, where I had to tell people to send their documents to us via email, it was a total disaster, particularly for older people this was really challenging. However, latest since the first (COVID) winter, none of my clients had issues sending documents electronically”. (CSO_2, Austria).

Even though language and technology barriers posed challenges, creative solutions were found. For example, CSO 4 tried to improvise and set up a radio channel. Around six to seven volunteers maintained regular communication with participants by sharing tasks and activities through internal channels. In the initial weeks, there were daily updates and assignments such as ball training or sharing recipes. One of the organisations did not follow the 2G rule and allowed clients without being immunised to use their services with the aim to keep their services as accessible as possible. However, this was experienced as unsafe for the employees who had already returned to the office for face-to-face communication.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **Austria**, some interviewees did not specifically mention changes between pandemic phases, but they did discuss the impact of lockdowns. For instance, a practitioner from CSO1 told us that she started using WhatsApp for her classes as many of her clients did not have a laptop or computer. The women were particularly affected by the lockdowns as they faced challenges finding a suitable space for online classes and experienced difficulties in language learning through WhatsApp. However, staying connected was important for them, and the classes provided an opportunity for social interaction outside their families. The interviewee's workload increased during the lockdowns as they had to teach smaller groups via WhatsApp instead of larger in-person classes. When it came to the decision whether or not to allow in-person classes, the organisation had to set the rules itself. They did not receive any guidelines from the Ministry of Education, but closely followed public school closings.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

In earlier stages of the pandemic, the City of Vienna coordinated several participatory initiatives, and currently, many **Austria**-wide initiatives are supported or organized by established institutions such as the Red Cross, Caritas, and Diakonie. Some initiatives were temporarily repurposed to provide COVID-19-related support, like the Initiative Pro-Hund, which offered specific information and assistance related to walking dogs during quarantine. Volunteering was affected, with 20% of volunteers stopping their work due to pandemic-related measures. However, one-third of those who continued

volunteering took on additional activities, and certain volunteering efforts shifted to online platforms, excluding certain groups. Austria-wide examples are the Team Österreich Nachbarschaftshilfe, a volunteering platform run by the Austrian Red Cross and ORF radio station; Long COVID-19 Austria, a self-help group for individuals affected by Long COVID; and HaltDerGewalt, an online support and consultation service for female victims of violence.

In Vienna, there are three distinct participatory initiatives. Firstly, there are localized Grätzlhilfe Telegram groups, formed during March/April 2020, aiming to connect neighbours and provide support during the COVID-19 pandemic. These groups address various issues, including COVID-19-related concerns, grocery shopping assistance, and political debates. While the number of members in these groups is limited and the discussions have shifted away from COVID-19, they continue to engage in community activities. Secondly, the Plaudertischerl initiative, organized by Diakonie and supported by the Ministry of Health, facilitates social connections by bringing people from different backgrounds together in cafes or community centres for conversations. Although primarily an offline initiative, an online option is also available. The initiative operates in Vienna and Lower Austria and promotes social cohesion and well-being. Finally, the City of Vienna's Wohnpartner initiated a neighborhood telephone service called Nachbarschafts-Telefon in March 2020. The hotline provided support and answered questions for residents, addressing topics such as helping older people, children's activities, and community networking. However, the current status and duration of this service, as well as its usage data, are unknown.

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

In **Austria**, several negative impacts can be observed such as the interruption of CSO activities: During the initial phase of the pandemic, all three CSOs experienced interruptions in their activities. Two of the CSOs had to switch to remote work and support their clients by phone or email. This resulted in a lack of direct contact with clients and challenges in adapting to new forms of communication. Financial vulnerability and structural disadvantage: CSOs' clients, particularly migrant women and the financially disadvantaged, faced additional challenges during the pandemic. Language barriers, social exclusion, and difficulties navigating Austrian bureaucracy were reported. Migrant women's lack of German language skills hindered their access to important services and support.

Limited support for certain groups: Some groups, such as students and asylum-seekers, were excluded from receiving support from certain aid organizations. This created gaps in the governmental response, leaving these vulnerable populations without adequate support. Limited access to essential services: The closure of health and social services during the lockdowns had a significant impact on vulnerable groups, including individuals experiencing homelessness or housing instability. Many services, including food banks, stopped providing services, leaving people in need without access to food or medical care. Language barriers and compliance: Language barriers were a challenge in communicating important information about the pandemic and public health measures to diverse populations. The lack of clear and accessible information led to lower compliance with public health measures among some migrant groups. Vulnerability of CSO employees: CSO employees were themselves vulnerable during the pandemic. They experienced the crisis while supporting their target groups in the same crisis. The lack of protective equipment such as masks and the inability to work from home were cited as problems.

In terms of gaps in government interventions, the closure of key services and limited support for certain groups resulted in gaps in the provision of assistance to vulnerable populations. Community-driven initiatives and CSOs played a role in filling these gaps. For example, individuals and organizations volunteered to run errands for vulnerable people, introduced migrant women to online platforms and language courses, and initiated projects to combat loneliness and social isolation. Social media was also used to connect people in need with volunteers.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Austria**, the clients of the four interviewed CSOs face multiple vulnerabilities at once. For example, Muslim migrant women in a Central European city experience gender stereotypes, financial vulnerabilities, and structural challenges tied to their migrant status. Language barriers and social exclusion due to limited German proficiency add to their difficulties in managing everyday life and dealing with Austrian bureaucracy. Many women in the program suffer from psychological health issues and trauma, which hinders their learning progress. Homesickness is also prevalent among those who arrived as refugees. Refugees also commonly face economic challenges, as they often arrive in their host countries with limited financial resources. In addition, this group faces language barriers and experience discrimination. The clients of CSO 1, a women's support organization focusing on migrant women of Muslim background, experience financial vulnerabilities and other structural issues related to their migrant status. The women in their classes often face psychological health issues and have difficulties progressing in their German language learning. The pandemic and related restrictions further impacted these women by limiting their social interactions and access to support.

The second CSO deals with financial vulnerabilities and structural disadvantages faced by people living in Austria. The pandemic highlighted three main groups particularly in need of their services: individuals living in precarious situations for an extended period, those whose support networks collapsed during the first lockdown, and self-employed individuals who experienced income loss due to the pandemic. The latter group often required substantial lifestyle changes, as they were unaccustomed to seeking financial support. Many Viennese residents rely on informal networks for assistance, but the pandemic disrupted these support systems. In the case of CSO 2, a transnational aid organization providing support to people experiencing financial hardship, there were three main groups in need of their services, including self-employed individuals who lost their income due to COVID-19. This suggests that the pandemic caused new vulnerabilities among individuals who had not previously required financial support.

The third CSO focuses on people affected by homelessness, including rough sleepers and refugees mainly from Syria, Afghanistan, and Ukraine. Clients of this CSO often have chronic health issues and limited means to protect themselves against the virus due to lack of private spaces. Understanding the dynamics of the pandemic is challenging for some, and quarantine measures can isolate them further. During lockdowns, the cessation of health and social services left vulnerable individuals without access to food or healthcare. Language barriers, especially for migrants from Eastern European countries, hindered compliance with public health measures. The employees of the CSO also faced vulnerability as they simultaneously experienced the crisis themselves while supporting their target group through

the same crisis. CSO 3, an aid organization working with homeless people and refugees, highlighted the vulnerabilities of their target groups, including chronic health issues, limited means of protection against the virus, and difficulties accessing food and healthcare services during lockdowns. Language barriers also affected compliance with public health measures.

The fourth CSO works with refugees who have experienced forced displacement. It is important to recognize the diversity and resilience within refugee populations, as individual experiences and vulnerabilities can vary. Nevertheless, there are some factors that make this group particularly vulnerable, such as the lack of legal status. They face uncertainty regarding their rights and protections in their host countries. Moreover, many refugees have had traumatic experiences in their home countries or during their journey to seek safety. Such experiences can have severe psychological and emotional impacts, making them more vulnerable to mental health disorders.

"And then they often have very severe traumas, yes, or the men also, that they can't swim and then just go over the sea without a life jacket and there they just sometimes lose a family member [...]. They are of course already impaired, that they have such a trauma." (CSO_4, Austria)

For the clients of CSO 4, an organisation that offers regular leisure activities to refugees, language and cultural barriers were intensified as in-person interactions and language support programs were disrupted. Additionally, mental health issues among refugees were exacerbated due to increased isolation, fear, and uncertainty.

All four CSOs took actions to address these issues, including initiatives at a community level. Voluntary and resident-led initiatives emerged to support vulnerable groups, such as running errands for them, introducing migrant women to online platforms and language courses, and facilitating social interactions through virtual cafes or online discussion tables. These initiatives aimed to mitigate the impact of the pandemic and provide assistance where needed.

Overall, while the specific views of the interviewees on the changing and new vulnerabilities caused by the pandemic are not explicitly stated, it can be inferred that the pandemic has exacerbated existing vulnerabilities and created new challenges for CSOs' target groups in Austria. CSOs have responded by adapting their services and collaborating with community initiatives to address the evolving needs of vulnerable populations.

3.2 Belgium

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Belgium**, the research site is the Antwerp district of Borgerhout. This description is given in D6.3 of Borgerhout as Antwerp's smallest district. It is densely populated, housing over 45,000 inhabitants. The Borgerhout district is characterised by its diversity: in 2020, only a minority of Borgerhout residents had two Belgian parents, and there are many first- and second-generation migrants living in the district. The incomes of Borgerhout residents are also relatively low compared to the rest of Antwerp. An interviewee described Borgerhout:

"There is far too little green space, there are a lot of children, there is a very large mix of people. A large proportion of people, especially in North Borgerhout, struggle with poverty, are often

low-literate, many newcomers are here. So you have a bit of everything here that requires attention from the policy, that's here.” (CSO_4, Belgium).

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

In **Belgium**, the first period of the pandemic was a challenging time characterised by extreme uncertainty for all of the respondents. Looking back, one respondent remembers that *“nobody knew exactly what was happening, and what was going to happen in the future.”* (CSO_4, Belgium) A few of the organisations moved to being predominantly online, which came with numerous challenges. One expert lamented that his organisation was *“particularly slow”* to switch to a digital way of working, and it took several months for this to improve. (CSO_4, Belgium)

One expert had quite a different experience, because their organisation managed to continue most of their service provision to the houseless/homeless people and to people who use drugs. For this CSO, the most pressing issue in the early phase of the pandemic was that of face masks: *“the masks were a major problem, it was a battle to obtain masks.”* (CSO_4, Belgium) In the face of the limited availability of personal protective equipment, the CSO had to find a balance between continuing to provide high-quality services to their target groups and minimising risk of COVID-19 transmission. They indicated that this was an extremely challenging balancing act, which led to considerable discussion within the organisation as well. It was possible for one of the organisations to stay open for some of the lockdown, following the required protocols. However, as other organisations were then closed, it meant that people would visit the service for other reasons, making it much broader than before. They adapted to the needs of the community, but often without the necessary resources.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **Belgium**, during the second time period characterized by COVID-19 restrictions, the interviewees highlighted various difficulties. Restrictions on group meetings hindered one organization's work, which focuses on facilitating dialogue among people. Another CSO highlighted issues when one child was sick within a group, meaning the whole group faced quarantine. This was a problem because of how important group dynamics were for this organization. Attempts to find alternative solutions, like meeting in small groups outdoors, presented practical challenges. The constantly changing rules required constant readjustment and the respondents expressed frustration with the extra workload and the vagueness of the top-down rules that changed frequently. Raising awareness about and enforcing the COVID-19 restrictions was a major challenge for a CSO. Convincing their clients about the importance of the measures proved difficult, leading to disagreements and tension.

Eventually, the interviewees noted that their CSOs' activities had largely returned to normal. They maintained a hybrid working model with both face-to-face and virtual modes, which they viewed positively. Although a sense of stability had returned, the decentralization of COVID-19 policy posed new challenges. Instead of clear top-down instructions, different sectors were now responsible for developing their own guidelines, leading to inconsistencies according to one respondent,

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

In the research site of Antwerp, in **Belgium**, several participatory practices emerged that actively involved ordinary people in various ways during the COVID-19 pandemic. Deliverable 6.5 has described examples of these initiatives, which aimed to foster community engagement, promote trust, and address the needs of vulnerable populations. In Antwerp, the Sensi Ambassadors initiative engaged diverse individuals with extensive networks in their neighbourhoods, religious communities, or migrant communities. These ambassadors received COVID-19 training, distributed multilingual communication materials, and served as trusted sources of information (City of Antwerp, 2020). The Antwerp helps platform supported volunteer initiatives by connecting residents in need with willing volunteers (Van Berendoncks, 2020). The Coronababbels initiative provided tailored psychosocial support through community organizations to various target audiences, addressing concerns and referring participants to specialized care (Stad Antwerpen, 2021). In Borgerhout, food distribution initiatives, like the neighbourhood restaurant launched by 't Werkhuys, provided affordable or free meals to families in financial difficulties (source: WP6 interviews).

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

Participatory initiatives in **Belgium** emerged rapidly to address urgent needs, that formal government agencies often could not respond to (El Khalfioui, 2020). These practices addressed various issues such as loneliness, financial hardship, practical assistance, and the need for tailored COVID-19 information and outreach. One of the participants discussed the importance of civil society reaching out to people in various languages, to ensure no one was left behind. He argues this could also be seen as a weakness in response, that *“when you have to go door to door with a whole army, you are losing people.”* (CSO_3, Belgium)

There were challenges in ensuring collaboration and participation throughout the initiatives, particularly due to the rapid setup and the limited participation of vulnerable populations (El Khalfioui, 2020). COVID-19 restrictions hindered live activities and exposed the digital divide affecting certain vulnerable groups. One of the experts expressed his frustration about how *“many types of support services and organisations just retracted behind their computers, which particularly for vulnerable groups made it very difficult to get help.”* A positive side-effect of the pandemic is considered to include the *“more efficient use of digital tools.”* (CSO_4, Belgium)

Governmental actors played different roles in the participatory practices. Some initiatives were initiated due to a lack of official support, but later stages involved facilitation by government actors (Post, 2020). The duration of participatory practices varied, with some being short-lived and directly responsive to the crisis, while others received long-term funding to continue their activities beyond the immediate pandemic impact (Post, 2021). Government investment in these initiatives provided financial support and extended their reach. However, sustainability was not always guaranteed if government priorities shifted, leading to potential strains on government-led initiatives (Amies, 2021). One CSO (CSO_3, Belgium) discussed the freedom of not relying on subsidies, unlike other civil society organisations.

Particularly early on in the pandemic, interviewees considered the governmental responses to have overlooked the severity of the collateral damage caused by the COVID-19 restrictions. However, the interviewees also shared the sentiment that public agencies generally tried their best, and that an

improved balance was found as time passed. One CSO (CSO_2, Belgium) explained, for example, that as the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the food insecurity faced by many households in the district, his CSO prioritised the scale-up of providing affordable community meals. They received additional funding for this during the pandemic, and they have now been awarded long-term financing to continue it.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Belgium**, the four CSOs involved in the expert interviews work with target groups that are vulnerable in various ways, from a broad group of underprivileged people that are mainly defined by their level of income to a more specific group of houseless/homeless people and individuals with drug addiction problems. In the context of COVID-19, the vulnerable groups targeted by the CSOs changed to some extent. For instance, for the CSO working with underprivileged groups, it became clear during the pandemic that the general approach of the Belgian government that categorizes people as ‘underprivileged’ based on their income level, i.e. more specifically whether or not they receive an ‘increased compensation’ (‘verhoogde tegemoetkoming’ in Dutch) did not cover everyone in need of special assistance. Consequently, the organisation decided to be more flexible in who they were targeting. On the other hand, the pandemic also magnified the vulnerability of some groups. For the houseless/homeless people, for instance, the COVID-19 rules were in many cases almost impossible to follow. In this context, one of the experts criticized the government’s lack of nuance when, during the first lockdown, they ordered everyone to stay at home:

*“When there was a lockdown, homeless people could not stay at home, like the minister advised everyone to do... A government also has to think about that, especially the groups of homeless people, what do you do with them? First of all, they do not have a house, so they did go outside. We heard stories of people who got fined three times in one day because they were not following the rules of the lockdown. But they also had nowhere to go, so that was a problem.”
(CSO_4, Belgium)*

As the pandemic progressed, this repressive policy of fining homeless people for being on the street was adjusted, but the rigidity of the lockdown rules in the beginning of the pandemic did have concrete consequences for this group. Indeed, not only were they not able to stay ‘at home’, they were even fined for being on the street as the quote above illustrates.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the vulnerable groups targeted by other CSOs in the research site (identified in the context of D6.5) varied. One CSO, for instance, focused specifically on migrant communities with limited knowledge of Dutch and aimed to debunk COVID-19 related misinformation among these communities by distributing multilingual information and recruiting so-called ‘ambassadors’ to provide a trusted source of information. Other CSOs targeted various specific groups of vulnerable people, ranging from young people to sex workers and newly arrived migrants or people living in poverty more generally.

In the COVID-19 context, in general, the main drivers of vulnerability identified by the experts revolve around poverty and living conditions. A shared sentiment between the respondents was that

vulnerability arises from a combination of factors. One of the experts, for instance, felt vulnerability is made up of *“a sum of vulnerable factors: housing, finances, health, age, network, and of course the neighbourhood where you live. The more vulnerable factors, the more likely you are to be hit harder.”* (CSO_1, Belgium). Another expert coined the term ‘*information-poverty*’ to highlight the fact that the difficult access to information for some groups of people (e.g. because of language issues or due to a lack of access to mainstream information channels) could also be considered a form of vulnerability.

At the same time, the experts also mentioned that similar vulnerabilities already existed in pre-pandemic times but that indeed, as mentioned, the COVID-19 crisis magnified them and made them more visible. In other cases, specific vulnerable groups in need of assistance also widened, requiring CSOs to rethink how to define who they were targeting. As mentioned in the above section, one of the CSOs for instance experienced that their definition of ‘underprivileged’ people had become too narrow. When they noticed that the pandemic worsened food insecurity for a lot of people, they launched a neighbourhood restaurant with affordable take-away meals; however, the organisation chose not to use the specific category of ‘increased compensation’ (see above) but instead tried to target a broader group of people with a ‘low income’.

3.3 England

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

Birmingham, a geographic community within the West Midlands and a county in **England**, was selected as the research site where interviews should take place for the COVINFORM project. The reason why Birmingham was selected as TRI’s main research site is because of the close and pre-existing networks that TRI has with CSOs and Public Health Directors in the area. As reported in D6.1, *“Baseline report community and citizen responses,”* it was estimated that, in 2018, 1,141,400 people live in Birmingham.⁴ In the year 2023, the population now amounts to 2,665,100 people in total.⁵ Furthermore, D6.1 reported that the 2011 Census highlights Birmingham’s diversity with ethnic groups including: White British (53.1%), Pakistani (13.5%), Other ethnicity (6.7%), Indian (6%), White other (4.8%), Caribbean (4.4%), Mixed (4.4%), Bangladeshi (3.0%), African (2.8%), and Chinese (1.2%).⁶ Birmingham is divided into 69 wards, each with 1-2 councillors that are members of Birmingham City Council. Compared to the rest of the West Midlands and England as a whole, Birmingham has a younger age structure with 22.8% of the population under 16 and 12.9% of the population aged 65 years or over.⁷

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, D6.1 reported vulnerabilities among Birmingham’s workforce, which *“was already characterised by lower skill levels, lower employment rates and high rates of unemployment and economic activity amongst working age residents”*.⁸ Other vulnerabilities noted in Birmingham before the COVID-19 pandemic include those from ethnic groups already suffering from poor health and poverty, those living in more deprived areas with higher levels of pollution, those

⁴ https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/info/20057/about_birmingham/1294/population_and_census/2.

⁵ <https://worldpopulationreview.com/world-cities/birmingham-population>.

⁶ https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/downloads/file/9741/2018_ks201_ethnic_group.

⁷ https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/downloads/file/9742/2011_birmingham_population_and_migration_topic_report.

⁸ https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/downloads/file/18942/economic_recovery_strategy_2021.

already struggling to access health services, and those with disabilities.⁹ Furthermore, children and young people were also identified as vulnerable before the COVID-19 pandemic (ibid). For instance, pre-COVID-19, it was reported that a high proportion of vulnerable children live in low-income households in the West Midlands Combined Area (WMCA) (ibid). In addition, homeless people were also considered to be vulnerable in Birmingham before the COVID-19 pandemic (ibid). In 2019, it was reported that the WMCA area had an aggregated 3.46 homeless households per 100,000 households which was said to be considerably higher than the national average (1.49) and West Midlands Region (1.72). Dudley (a town in the West Midlands) was reported to have the highest rate of 3 per 100,000 households (ibid). Those also living in temporary accommodations were vulnerable (ibid). In the year 2019, the WMCA had an aggregated 3.34 households in temporary accommodation per 100,000 households and 77.4% of these households were with children. Other vulnerabilities include those with specific health and additional support needs, and the elderly (especially those being cared for) (ibid).

As stated in the D6.3, “*Analysis Community and citizen responses and impacts*,” examples of CSOs in the research site before COVID-19 include the work of MAGs (Mutual Aid Groups) and the Voluntary, Community, Faith, and Social Enterprise (VCFSE) sector. The sector comprises charities, public service mutual, social enterprises, and several other non-profits.¹⁰ Note that MAGs are volunteer led initiative where groups of people in a specific area unite to support one another, “meeting vital community needs without relying on official bodies.” (Power & Benton, 2021).¹¹ Regarding the VCFSE sector, the aim is to “provide better, more effective public services, while also creating social value that benefits society more widely.”¹²

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

CSOs in **England** were supported by their respective governments to provide the much-needed support to vulnerable communities (Wilson et al., 2021, Rees et al., 2021). To address such needs, there was a requirement to shift the types of services provided to communities. There was a specific request for services for individuals whose typical support and care needs could not be met by themselves or by their own networks, including houseless/homeless people, or those requiring dedicated medical care, income or food help, hands-on daily help, or assistance with childcare and education (Harris, 2021).

⁹ PHE Population Intelligence Hub. (n.d.). (rep.). Regional Health Impact of COVID-19 Task and Finish Group (pp. 2–35). West Midlands Combined Authority.

¹⁰ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-role-of-voluntary-community-and-social-enterprise-vcse-organisations-in-public-procurement/the-role-of-voluntary-community-and-social-enterprise-vcse-organisations-in-public-procurement#:~:text=VCSE%20organisations%20can%20include%20charities,more%20widely%20%5Bfootnote%207%5D>.

¹¹ Power, A., & Benton, E. (2021). Retrieved from <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/covid19/2021/05/06/where-next-for-britains-4300-mutual-aid-groups/#:~:text=A%20mutual%20aid%20group%20is,without%20relying%20on%20official%20bodies>.

¹² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-role-of-voluntary-community-and-social-enterprise-vcse-organisations-in-public-procurement/the-role-of-voluntary-community-and-social-enterprise-vcse-organisations-in-public-procurement#:~:text=VCSE%20organisations%20can%20include%20charities,more%20widely%20%5Bfootnote%207%5D>.

With a particular focus on Birmingham, the D6.3 deliverable stated that the city saw an immediate upsurge of activities, including voluntary organisations taking hasty action with no external ‘prompting.’ As reported in the *Community-based responses to Covid-19 in Birmingham: Insights and experiences* report, Mutual Aid Groups (MAGs) worked across neighbourhoods and volunteer-led initiatives and faith groups reacted to needs immediately. Worth touching on here is the Birmingham’s coordinated city-wide response. This involved recognised leadership within the Voluntary, Community, Faith, and Social Enterprise (VCFSE) sector by organisations well-known for certain areas of specialist knowledge. The key goal was to contribute effectively to city wide planning and decisions, underlining the needs of vulnerable communities. Organisations from across the VCFSE sector functioned collaboratively to combat the impact of the COVID-19 crisis. The COVID-19 Community Champions are relevant here as well. The network provided up-to-date information on how residents should protect themselves and others against the COVID-19 virus. With this in mind, Birmingham also had a locality-based and hyper-local community response. In the report addressing Birmingham’s CSO response and adaptation to COVID-19 (Wilson et al., 2021), researchers shed light on how the pandemic led to a rise in unemployment and uncertainty amongst individual’s futures. Responding to these challenges, established groups re-shifted their focus away from operating the types of activities originally provided pre-COVID-19 and towards offering welfare advice. Besides service adaptation, both countries also witnessed a surge in participation within the voluntary sector (Rees et al., 2021).

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **England**, it was reported that work within the voluntary sector was paused because of the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The work that was carried out within this sector required 1-2-1 support, and at this point, organisations started working from home. CSO_1 explained:

“This massively changed the way we worked. We had to become familiar with platforms such as Zoom and Teams, working remotely and making sure people were properly connected.”
(CSO_1, England)

Similar to the above statement made by the interviewee from CSO_1, the interviewee from CSO_2 explained that the COVID-19 pandemic meant that their organisation could not do face-to-face work. As a result, their work had to be carried out online. By transitioning online, the interviewee explained that their organisation had to organise their own events, which was a new aspect for them. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, all events were attended via third sector organisations. Additional changes during this time period involved taking on work outside of the organisation’s remit. This organisation focuses on health-related issues, and the interviewee explained that they had to start supporting people who were losing their jobs as a result of the pandemic. Commenting on this topic in further detail, the interviewee explained:

“Because we were working outside of our remit and supporting those who lost their jobs, we had to partner up with organisations we wouldn’t necessarily partner up with. It was a good learning curve because there was a lot more our organisation could start doing with other organisations.” (CSO_2, England)

Similar to CSO_1 and CSO_2, the organisation of CSO_3 moved online during this time period. Only a few people would go in to make sure that people were working from home. Most of the work was being carried out via Zoom, and during this time period, the interviewee's organisation began focusing on educating their users on digital skills. The interviewee said the following:

“Our organisation began teaching their users how to use our services online. Part of the organisation's work involved doing door-to-door visits to help install apps onto people's devices. Besides digital assistance, support also involved offering phone calls to help with any other queries.” (CSO_3, England)

In relation to changes in T2, interviewees reported that when lockdowns came to an end, it made it possible for organisations to resume their work. CSO_1 commented:

“Things became easier for us, especially in terms of face-to-face interactions. Although we knew some people within our workforce were not vaccinated, there was still an increase in confidence among our and other organisations to get back to work and provide the services we were initially providing.” (CSO_1, England)

During this time period, another interviewee (CSO_2) explained that their organisation began focusing on community needs that they typically wouldn't engage in. Specifically, working with people from community groups that were not receiving effective communication to help boost vaccine uptake. Specifically speaking, the barriers were access to reliable and understandable public health communication. In their own words, the respondent explained:

“We were trying to increase uptake. We would not normally take part in these kinds of things and encourage people, but our work was all about getting the message out and making sure people are being heard. We also made sure that information was going out to people in a format that they could understand. So, I think we started using some of that learning from the lockdown in the sense that when information was being given to communities, there was a lot of miscommunication and misinformation, and people were sharing things that were not right and doing things that were not helpful to them. We made sure to communicate in a way that people could understand, and that information was simple enough for people to take the vaccine up.” (CSO_2, England)

Following the introduction of vaccines, the interviewee (CSO_3) reported that their services began taking place in outdoor spaces. Commenting on this transition, the interviewee explained:

“Our first group activities which were face-to-face took place in parks and not in the centre, because we know some people wouldn't be taking up the COVID-19 vaccine.” (CSO_3, England)

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

A number of promising participatory practices in **England** are identified including the *Local Governments Association (LGA)*: Responding directly to the COVID-19 pandemic, many town councils in the UK recruited volunteers to offer aid to the most vulnerable parts of the population.¹³ Local Governments Association (LGA) websites gather all the required information for local entities to

¹³ Cooperation experiences between civil society and local/regional governments. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://oidp.net/en/covid19/page.php?id=46>.

"prepare in this regard" (ibid). Moreover, the *Community Action Response* is a relevant practice. The aim of this campaign was to strengthen awareness of the requirement to be "attentive to those around us and help the most vulnerable (ibid). The Community Action Response campaign was launched by Eden Project Communities and associated partners; The National Lottery Community Fund, Nextdoor, Neighbourhood Watch, Campaign to End Loneliness and Eco Attractions Group in 2020. That said, the Eden Project Communities is a UK wide network that has appeared out of the community building campaign The Big Lunch, which reaches over six million people in communities annually (ibid). *Mutual aid groups* were created to give residents the opportunity to help provide specific forms of assistance during the COVID-19 outbreak.¹⁴ Key motivations for the set-up of mutual aid groups (MAGs) during the COVID-19 outbreak include organising support efforts for people who are self-isolating, particularly if those doing so are part of a more at-risk demographic, such as the elderly and people with pre-existing conditions.¹⁵ At present, all COVID-19 related MAGs in operation can be found on the COVID-19 Mutual Aid UK website.¹⁶ There are 59 existing MAGs providing COVID-19 support in the West Midlands, a region where Birmingham constitutes a major city.¹⁷ In relation to Birmingham-based groups providing help to those self-isolating during the pandemic, examples of MAGs include the Birmingham Mutual Aid and COVID-19 Community Response Group.¹⁸ The main priority of this group has been to support the elderly, isolated, and immunocompromised when self-isolating.¹⁹ Another example of a group providing self-isolation support is the COVID-19 Mutual Aid Harborne B17, a group which brings separate streets and small areas together to look out for and support one another (ibid). Support has come in the form of food banks, advertising opportunities to take part in COVID-19 research and joining online social groups such as art groups. A further example of a MAG that has provided self-isolation support is that of the Acocks Green Together: COVID-19 Community Support Volunteers group.²⁰ The group explicitly supports those that live and/or work in the Acocks Green Ward, an electoral ward in south-east Birmingham. Thus far, the support provided particularly to those self-isolating and are elderly and/or immunocompromised has involved access to food and completing errands (ibid). In addition, *Coronavirus Tech Handbook* is a notable practice. This website was developed in March 2020 to crowdsource data concerning the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus.²¹ Developed in Newspeak House, a makerspace for politics in London, the website has been used by doctors,

¹⁴ Access to support. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://www.bvsc.org/covid-19-pathways-for-accessing-support-in-birmingham>.

¹⁵ Covid-19 Mutual Aid – Local organising to support the most vulnerable in our communities. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://covidmutualaid.org/>.

¹⁶ Covid-19 Mutual Aid – Local organising to support the most vulnerable in our communities. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://covidmutualaid.org/>.

¹⁷ Mutual Aid - West Midlands. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://www.mutual-aid.co.uk/area/west-midlands>.

¹⁸ Birmingham Mutual Aid and Covid-19 Community Response Group. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://www.mutual-aid.co.uk/group/birmingham-mutual-aid-and-covid-19-community-response-group>.

¹⁹ Birmingham Community Solidarity: Coronavirus Response. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://www.facebook.com/groups/3234138479933658/about>.

²⁰ Acocks Green Covid-19 Mutual Aid. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://www.mutual-aid.co.uk/group/acocks-green-covid-19-mutual-aid>.

²¹ Keck, C. (2020). Technologists Are Crowdsourcing a 'Coronavirus Tech Handbook' to Track Resources. Retrieved 26 August 2022, from <https://gizmodo.com/technologists-are-crowdsourcing-a-coronavirus-handbook-1842291959>.

teachers, researchers, and manufacturers discussing ventilators and personal protective equipment, and more.²² To date, the handbook had already helped:

- Doctors residing in the UK to offer advice to doctors living in Ecuador on how to develop safe personal protective equipment;
- MAGs in the UK to share ideas of organising volunteers and their finances;
- The exchange of dashboards to store and shed light on important data relating to COVID-19 (ibid).

Concluding, *Trees for Cities* is a UK charity which has an aim of planting urban trees and creating greener cities. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the #GrowYourLove campaign was formed and run by a partnership between search engine Ecosia, tree planting charity Trees for Cities and the NHS Forest, who work with healthcare organisations to open up their green spaces to local communities and encourage improved use of the natural environment. In addition, this project was coordinated by the Centre for Sustainable Healthcare to improve the health and wellbeing of staff, patients, and communities by planting trees and forming green spaces on or near to NHS land.²³

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

In **England**, CSO_1 explained that there was acknowledgement from the local government that they could not have supported people in Birmingham without the help of the voluntary sector. In terms of gaps, the interviewee explained that the biggest issue was poor communication between the central government with the local government. Commenting on the poor communication between the two bodies, the interviewee shed light on the following:

“There was quite a difference between local government responses and central government responses. For example, with regard to the national NHS volunteering scheme that was implemented, it was a nice idea on paper. However, because there was not much conversation with people at the local level, there ended up being a long waiting list of NHS volunteers that never got deployed anywhere because of all that had already been addressed. Because the central government did not properly communicate with the local government about what was happening in the local area, a lot of time, effort and money was wasted doing things that did not need to be done.” (CSO_1, England)

The second interviewee suggested that *“we were not in a position to fill in governmental gaps.”* (CSO_2, England). CSO_5, in terms of governmental responses, explained that governmental gaps filled in by the wider community included providing support from a faith perspective. According to the interviewee, the biggest gap fillers in terms of support were faith communities. In his own words, the interviewee said:

“Every Friday, within the mosques and temples, and Sunday, within the churches, these places became filled with people trying to help others, pray with others, encourage others, uplift

²² Coronavirus Tech Handbook. Retrieved 7 September 2022, from <https://www.crowdfunder.co.uk/p/coronavirustechhandbook>.

²³ Early, C. (2020). “A living monument” – new campaign will plant trees for NHS. Retrieved 6 September 2022, from <https://www.yourweather.co.uk/news/trending/a-living-monument-new-campaign-will-plant-trees-for-nhs.html>.

others, and sort out food bank distributions. These people weren't involved in contracted services. These are people with hearts and compassion.” (CSO_5, England)

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **England**, in terms of non-governmental collaborations, CSO_1 interviewee explained that they work with three broad groups: Voluntary organisations: Support is given to these organisations to achieve their aims and make sure they have the finances to keep them operating. As a collective, the respondent said they also help give the voluntary sector a voice. Public sector body (and some private sector bodies): They advise specific bodies on how to engage with community groups and the voluntary sector. People who need support from the voluntary sector: This includes vulnerable people and the disadvantaged. Thus far, the CSOs have run a number of strategic programmes in collaboration with the voluntary sector and public sector agencies to tackle specific issues. As stated by the interviewee:

“The programmes were all lottery funded, and three examples of programme support include: (a) Talent Match: helping young people who have been in long-term unemployment, (b) Ageing better: helping older people who are isolated get together to bring an end to isolation and (c) Changing Futures Together: working with people who have multiple complex needs (e.g., homelessness, substance abuse, and mental ill health).” (CSO_1, England)

Regarding governmental collaboration, the interviewee confirmed that they do work closely with governmental bodies, mainly at a local level through the local authority and combined authority. In addition, the interviewee reported that they work on a national level as well. The interviewee explained:

“During the pandemic, I was the regional lead for the West Midlands area that fed into the voluntary sector emergencies partnership that was working at a national level. I met with them regularly.” (CSO_1, England)

The interviewee reported domestic abuse cases rising as a result of the pandemic. At the time of the interview, the interviewee already knew that cases would most likely increase. This is because people were more domestically confined during the pandemic. Although the interviewee's CSO did not create a special domestic abuse service for victims to access, the interviewee was aware of locally run campaigns (e.g., Women's Aid), which their organisation was working closely with during the pandemic. The interviewee commented:

“There was a campaign that was run locally such as Women's Aid and others (we supported the campaigns) which was trying to get the word out to people in the sense that if they needed help or if they were experiencing domestic violence, they could contact their local shelters and get support.” (CSO_1, England)

Another interviewee (CSO_2) explained that they work closely with the residents of Birmingham, to better understand their experience of health and social care. The organisation works at two different levels, e.g., governance level and working with people in research. The other side of their work is to

collect feedback from people. Furthermore, the organisation stated that they work closely with third sector organisations and community organisations. In their own words, the interviewee explained:

“This is to make sure we’re hearing from everyone in Birmingham. A big part of our work is health and inequalities. Part of this work requires targeting people who need health and social care support the most. Once we’ve identified the groups of people who need this kind of support, we then contact community groups in those specific areas to make sure our work reached the people we need to reach in these specific areas.” (CSO_2, England)

The interviewee further added:

“Our work would not be possible if we were not partnering up with commissioners and providers of health and social care.” (CSO_2, England)

This interviewee acknowledged that the pandemic made those who were already homeless and experiencing domestic abuse more vulnerable to the COVID-19 pandemic. Commenting on the actions they took to support such groups, the interviewee said:

“We did a lot of work with Shelter and Crisis to make sure that the most vulnerable within society were supported. Besides supporting homeless communities, we also worked closely with organisations that support women who, during COVID-19, are struggling with domestic abuse.” (CSO_2, England)

The interviewee further added:

“Overall, close collaboration with different groups and organisations helped with the COVID-19 response but then again, considering how big Birmingham is, support may not have reached everyone.” (CSO_2, England)

The third CSO, explained that they supported the Chinese community to engage, navigate, access services, and connect with the wider community. The organisation has two broad pillars. First, they are a member organisation and second, they focus on social activity. With regard to social activities, the CSO engages in coach trips and excursions. The work they do is commissioned, meaning that they have programs that are funded by the council and National Health Service (NHS). Close work with other organisations has included collaborations with the Birmingham Irish Association and an Indian-Sikh organisation. In terms of collaboration with the government, previous examples have included work with the Department of Levelling up. Generally speaking, a lot of the services they provide focus on maintaining good wellbeing and providing information, advice, and guidance. Additional services also include a carers support project and a small day service for the elderly. The majority of people who attend their centre and access their services have been people over the age of 50. The elderly predominantly come from the Chinese community who have issues not just around IT skills, but literacy as well. The interviewee commented:

“A lot of these people are facing barriers, in terms of accessing services and a lot of it is down to literacy because of the government wanting everything to be digital. These barriers also apply to those who have English as a first language and are disadvantaged with everything going online. The people who are less visible and not listened to are those coming from mainland China.” (CSO_3, England)

CSO_5 works closely with people who are unemployed from all kinds of backgrounds. In terms of collaboration, the organisation has worked with Westlands Authority and mental health charities to

help them with their campaign and messaging to different communities. The interviewee touched on one example and pointed out the following:

“Our organisation has worked with construction companies and infrastructure programs like the HS2 high speed rail to help with the recruitment of people from diverse backgrounds.”
(CSO_5, England)

Throughout the T1 and T2 phases, the interviewees did not report on target group changes. Moreover, the interviewee (CSO_5) reported that the pandemic led to the exacerbation of mental health issues. At the time of the interview, the interviewee did not report on what kind of work was being carried out within their CSO to address this issue. However, the interviewee did report that he knew of other organisations trying to offer counselling and therapeutic support. Furthermore, the interviewee stressed that the exacerbation of mental health issues created new vulnerabilities for people from black communities. Commenting on this topic, the interviewee explained:

“On a broader scale, I didn’t and still don’t know of any other culturally appropriate service that would say, OK, this is the organisation that you refer black people to.” (CSO_5, England)

3.4 Germany

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

The local research sites in Mannheim, **Germany**, are the neighbourhoods of Schönau, Neckarstadt-West, and Innenstadt/Jungbusch. These neighbourhoods were selected due to their high average population density, living density, and unemployment rate, indicators which often correlate with poor health outcomes (Stadt Mannheim, 2022; Galobardes et al., 2006a, 2006b). Interviewees generally described these sites prior to COVID-19 as disadvantaged, noting how co-occurring physical/health, psychological, and social vulnerabilities compounded one another within the local populations. However, interviewees also mentioned the depth and breadth of cooperation and networking among local civil society groups and the local public sector institutions involved in supporting vulnerable groups. While some interviewees criticized certain dimensions of interaction between CSOs and the public sector during the pandemic (such as the effectiveness of communication), all interviewees positively characterised the baseline level of networking within the social sector as high.

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

Interviewees in **Germany** testified that at the start of the pandemic, neither they nor their target groups knew what to expect. However, all interviewees agreed that within a short timeframe, living conditions for their target groups became more difficult and unstable. One severe impact was that governmental services became very difficult to access: e.g., employment services for the precarious; immigration services for refugees; etc. It should be noted that even before the pandemic, such services were characterised by interviewees as difficult for their target groups to access. This resulted in increased pressure on CSOs to fill gaps in governmental services. Most interviewees focused their descriptions on those impacts that most affected their own target groups. However, some also noted that building fear and confusion, and increasingly strict restrictions, negatively impacted the entire

population, but vulnerable groups in particular. During the period of increased restrictions – such as lockdowns – conditions remained very challenging. Some interviewees' organisations were able to resume most of their services within a relatively short timeframe (albeit sometimes digitally), while some were not. Smaller organisations appear to have often been more severely disrupted. Interviewees' organisations implemented health-protective strategies, such as offering services through a window rather than in the same room. Eventually, CSOs of all sizes moved forward with digitalisation when possible. However, for smaller organisations, this sometimes ran into barriers such as lack of work laptops. All interviewees reported that their workloads increased greatly, due to an increase in service requests, the need to adapt workflows, and the need to introduce additional steps in nearly all workflow (e.g., hygiene considerations).

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

The introduction of vaccinations in **Germany** brought a gradual reduction in stress. All interviewees agreed that their organisations took advantage of loosening restrictions to re-introduce a broader range of services as soon as possible. Several interviewees' designation as "system-relevant workers" meant that they had access to resources that helped expedite this, such as testing, PPE, and priority vaccines. All interviewees also reported that the pandemic forced some positive changes, such as increased digital competence; new training opportunities; and improved efficiency with regard to the delivery of some services. However, all interviewees also reported that challenges, such as high workloads and disconnect within the staff and between staff and clients, still persisted after vaccination and the loosening of restrictions. Especially smaller organisations reported that not all services could be re-introduced, and that certain health-protective measures remained in place well after the introduction of vaccines, including some with adverse effects on operations (e.g., a reduction in personnel present on-site, due to the presence of at-risk groups among staff).

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved "ordinary people"

When it comes to initiatives in **Germany** as a whole, digitalization played a role in enabling citizen participation. One well-known nationwide online initiative initiated by the German government was called #hackthevirus, which sought to exploit digitalization and its benefits in terms of crisis management. Over 43,000 citizens, scientists, and specialists participated, and the solutions developed during the hackathon were published as open-source material. It can hence be termed a pioneer project of citizen participation in times of a crisis of this scale. The "*Post-Coron-A-Mat*" was an online participatory practice that aimed to aggregate knowledge. It was led by a think tank rather than the government, and serves more as a collective reminder of lessons learned from the Corona pandemic than as a means of direct service provision. Although its long-term impact remains to be seen, it was undoubtedly conceived as a long-term project. In contrast, the "*Impf-O-Mat*" did not aim to engage the public or aggregate knowledge, but rather to help people make an informed decision about vaccination. The initiators were two scientists, but the website was operated and supported by the Ministry of Social Affairs, Health and Integration. *Krisenchat* was another example of an online service, but with a very different focus: mental health. This nationwide WhatsApp chat service provided voluntary and confidential psychological support to children and young people, who were considered vulnerable to the mental and social effects of COVID-19 measures such as lockdowns and school closures. With over 50,000 consultations at the time of assessment, the immediate positive impact of

Krisenchat was highly visible; its main goal was to have a long-term positive effect by preventing negative consequences related to isolation and lockdowns.

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

Interviewees in **Germany** praised some aspects of the local governmental response, such as the speed with which the city formed a COVID-19 task force, the fact that responses were multilingual from the offset, and the fact that CSOs and public authorities were generally well-networked with one another.

"There's really no one we don't work with, except political parties of the extreme direction [...] Not a week goes by that I don't talk to at least 50 players" (CSO_3, Germany).

However, interviewees also indicated that governmental institutions did not prove resilient upon the onset of the crisis, often scaling back services or becoming much harder to access. Interviewees stated that the sudden reduction in governmental services was "catastrophic" for both CSOs and their target groups. During lockdowns, several key social services, such as the Youth Welfare Office, offered no face-to-face access and limited telephone access, meaning that they were effectively only available to the digitally literate.

"[Lack of accessibility by telephone] was absolutely catastrophic" (CSO_2, Germany).

Additionally, the imposition of additional procedural barriers, such as COVID-19 testing requirements and stricter scheduling, often proved to be 'the straw that broke the camel's back' for vulnerable populations who had already faced access barriers. Several interviewees stated that these barriers mitigated the positive impact of relief efforts, such as subsidies for the self-employed. All interviewees indicated that their organisations and other CSOs worked to fill gaps in governmental services. However, the extent to which CSOs could do so was often limited by a lack of effective coordination, or even timely communication, with governmental actors.

With regard specifically to risk communications, interviewees confirmed that public authorities took the lead in Mannheim. Several interviewees praised governmental risk communications measures for being multilingual; for utilising multiple channels (e.g., posters, videos, radio, online); and for (sometimes) focusing on the specific needs of vulnerable populations. However, some interviewees also criticised governmental risk communications for missing certain gaps: e.g., non-visual communications for the blind; the lack of "simple language" translations; the imposition of unrealistic demands for compliance; and drawbacks of a 'fear-based' approach in general.

"[I am critical of] fear-mongering, the whole thing: the health care system is collapsing and everything is terrible, instead of placing an emphasis on the importance of the community" (CSO_2, Germany).

"Fear-based communication I think brought out a lot of these resistance attitudes. Self-efficacy should have been addressed much more, you could have done a thousand fun things instead of complicating everything with German dourness" (CSO_5, Germany).

The role of CSOs was often to distribute materials; only one interviewee indicated that their organisation actively created new materials (related to that organisation's own service offers).

"We distributed a four-page flyer with offers, from walking the dog to conversations to shopping to pen pal offers" (CSO_4, Germany).

"We kept trying things in public spaces that sent out a message, texts on bridges, chalk on the ground, we're still here trying to be here for you, it was hard" (CSO_5, Germany).

Several interviewees also positively assessed the public health authorities for running effective vaccination campaigns. Specifically, they praised mobile vaccination efforts (vaccination buses and teams). Points criticised by interviewees included the lack of effective explainer videos on vaccination and difficulty in booking vaccination appointments for the digitally excluded. As with risk communications, CSOs took a supporting role in vaccination campaigns, primarily distributing information and expediting access.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

With regard to vulnerability in **Germany**, interviewees characterised their target groups' vulnerabilities and risks as intersectional. Cases mentioned included deaf refugees; transgendered victims of domestic violence; single parents of autistic children; etc. Interviewees noted that vulnerabilities can lead to a sense of disempowerment; however, some also stressed positive characteristics such as resilience and determination.

"People who say of themselves, we're cut off, no one hears us, no one redoes the houses, no one cares about us" (CSO_4, Germany)

"They are often desperate people, but open to doing something themselves [...] People often bring with them the willingness to become active themselves and do something to improve their lives" (CSO_1, Germany).

In Germany, CSOs and grassroots initiatives supplemented governmental efforts to provide material, social, and psychological support to vulnerable groups. Examples included networking platforms to offer help with daily needs (e.g., in Berlin, Bürgeraktiv – das Engagementportal: www.berlin.de/buergeraktiv/); petitions concerning access to vaccinations for people with disabilities or re-opening childcare in particular neighbourhoods; social media channels used to connect neighbours willing to assist people in need, which was managed under the hashtag #Nachbarschaftschallenge; etc. The majority of local practices in the Mannheim region do not appear to have been governmentally led or initiated; many arose as grassroots campaigns inspired by initiatives from different regions (like Gabenzaun), sometimes gradually being "adopted" or gaining support from a range of CSOs and public-sector institutions (like QuaranTeen). All interviewees agreed that the pandemic made life significantly more difficult and unstable for their target groups within a short period of time. Both the pandemic itself and its social impacts aggravated existing vulnerabilities: e.g., poor access to services; precarious employment and housing; disrupted schedules; adverse social and psychological consequences of being locked down; etc. Another factor that aggravated existing vulnerabilities was the decreased availability of governmental services. CSOs often attempted to fill gaps in the service spectrum; however, their capacity to do so varied greatly based on their size, resources, and other factors.

In addition to aggravating the intersectional vulnerabilities of CSO target groups, the pandemic and its social effects exposed CSO employees to significant stress. As mentioned throughout this report,

workloads universally increased, as did the compliance burden at work. Several interviewees reported that some of their clients found it difficult to adhere to health-protective regulations, which caused them significant stress. Interviewees furthermore found it stressful to try to mediate between different understandings of the pandemic (e.g., to dispel misinformation and conspiracy theories, persuade target groups of the importance of complying with regulations, etc.).

3.5 Greece

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Greece**, the main target sub-national unit was the Municipality of Athens, which is the biggest socio-demographic municipality in Greece with approximately 664,046 residents (Cities Network for Integration, n.d.)²⁴, while the region has, according to the new estimations from elstat 3,814,064 residents (Elstat, 2021)²⁵. The municipality is divided into seven districts²⁶ and consists of homogenous communities of mainly Greek orthodox Christians, several ethno-religious minorities such as Pomaki, Armenian, Romani, Jewish and Muslim, as well as migrants and refugees. The migrant crisis has led to a 22.84%²⁷ increase of foreign nationals in Athens, particularly in areas that face challenges of social and urban space deprivation, (Koutrolikou & Siatitsa, 2011)²⁸, (Institute of local Administration, 2018)²⁹. From an economic point of view, elstat (2018) estimates the GDP of Athens (Attica) at €22,915³⁰. Regarding governance, municipalities are responsible for the management of local affairs within their area of jurisdiction, although decisions are implemented with the collaboration and supervision of the Greek government at a national, regional and local level (Hellenic parliament, n.d.)³¹. Greek municipalities adhere to a top-down approach. Therefore all municipal decisions are implemented by the mayor and the municipal council (City of Athens, n.d.)³². In Greece, the pandemic did not radically change this governmental structure, while it has exacerbated vulnerabilities such as homelessness, elderly in need of care, or employees and employers who were forced to stop their business activities as systemic weaknesses emerged. According to our expert interviews, interviewees indicate to have encountered both socio-homogenous and diverse working environments, due to the increased percentage of migrants and refugees. Experts, at a pre-pandemic phase (T0) have defined

²⁴ <https://www.cnigreece.gr/en/municipalities/athens/>.

²⁵ <https://www.statistics.gr/en/2021-census-res-pop-results>, p.40.

²⁶ <https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/entry/Athens#Districts>.

²⁷ <https://worldpopulationreview.com/world-cities/athens-population>.

²⁸ <https://encounterathens.wordpress.com/2012/08/10/the-construction-of-a-public-discourse-for-athens-centre-media-migrants-and-inner-city-regeneration/>.

²⁹ https://www.ita.org.gr/el/images/meletes_ita/%CE%A3%CF%84%CF%81%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B7%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8C%CF%82_%CE%A0%CF%81%CE%BF%CE%B3%CF%81%CE%B1%CE%BC%CE%BC%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B9%CF%83%CE%BC%CF%8C%CF%82_%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%82_%CE%A0%CF%81%CF%89%CF%84%CE%B5%CF%8D%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%83%CE%B1%CF%82.pdf.

³⁰ Hellenic Statistical Authority (ΕΛΣΤΑΤ). (2018). *Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (NUTS I and NUTS II) / 2018*. Available at: <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SEL57/->.

³¹ <https://www.hellenicparliament.gr/en/Vouli-ton-Ellinon/To-Politevma/Syntagma/>.

³² <https://www.cityofathens.gr/who/dimotiko-symvoylio/>.

vulnerable citizens which include, homeless people, citizens in extreme poverty, children, substance-dependant persons / drug addicts, mentally ill persons and minority groups of diverse backgrounds.

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

As of the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic until later phases (T0 - 2), in **Greece**, Attica was one of the regions with the most COVID-19 confirmed infections, particularly due to the high human density of the area. Respective authorities were highly challenged to keep track of confirmed infection cases per district or municipalities, due to the hospitalization in different areas than a citizen's permanent residence, nevertheless, during the first phase of the pandemic (T1) at least 447,975 cases and 12,903 deaths are estimated according to the daily infection rate statistics of the national organization of public health (EODY, 2020 – 2021)³³. In order to mitigate the consequences of COVID-19, national and regional points of governance implemented containment measures which emphasized on non-pharmaceutical solutions such as social isolation and social distancing. A nationwide campaign was initiated with the slogan “we stay at home” that encouraged citizens to limit social interactions. Even though these measures were successful, prolonged isolation inevitably negatively impacted the psychological health / wellbeing of both the general population and vulnerable groups in Greece, while PTSD, depression, sleep deprivation among other mental health phenomena were observed in residents of Athens (Anastasiou & Duquenne, 2021)³⁴. The impact of the pandemic was also extremely negative for children as adults due to the lack of social interaction (Magklara et al, 2020)³⁵, increased family disputes, and lack of physical exercise . To tackle the latter issue, often due to limited green, open spaces, the Municipality of Athens with the support of relevant ministries, implemented an urban space renovation scheme (“great walk”) which would provide citizens with open, green spaces to visit and exercise whenever COVID-19 measures were less strict (Rajabifard, Foliente and Paez, 2021)³⁶. The pandemic and the implemented measures during the first phase also had an immensely negative impact on businesses, as business activities were suspended, particularly in the leisure, retail and tourism industries (In.gr, 2021)³⁷, (Skai, 2021)³⁸, (Grant Thornton, n.d.)³⁹ in both Athens and the rest of Greece. During this and later phases, minorities such as Jews and Muslims in Athens would celebrate their respective religious events according to relevant COVID-19 measures (AthensVoice, 2021)⁴⁰, while a study concluded that refugees and migrants would face increased risks of infections in

³³ <https://eody.gov.gr/epidimiologika-statistika-dedomena/ektheseis-epidimiologikis-epitirisis-loimosis-apon-sars-cov-2/ektheseis-covid-19-2021/>.

³⁴ <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/10/1/27>.

³⁵ <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.10.18.20214643v1>.

³⁶ https://books.google.gr/books/about/COVID_19_Pandemic_Geospatial_Information.html?id=5D8xEAAAQBAJ&printsec=frontcover&source=kp_read_button&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Greece&f=false.

³⁷ <https://www.in.gr/2021/02/17/economy/ereyna-oi-epaggelmatikes-kai-oikonomikes-epiptoseis-tou-koronaizou/>.

³⁸ <https://www.skai.gr/news/greece/ey-anisyxoi-8-stous-10-ellines-gia-oikonomia-sti-meta-covid-epoxi>.

³⁹ <https://www.grant-thornton.gr/insights/article/survey-coronavirus-greek-economy-gr/>.

⁴⁰ <https://www.athensvoice.gr/epikairota/ellada/714076/ramazani-ekatontades-moysoylmanoi-sto-temenostis-athinas/>.

temporary placement camps (Bouloutza, 2021)⁴¹. Even though the general public and vulnerable groups were observed to be supportive of the implemented measures at first, demonstrating high rates of trust, optimism and confidence (Ta Nea, 2020)⁴², (Dianeosis, 2020)⁴³, during the second lockdown the negative psychological and socio-economic impact was more apparent which led to increased complaints by unions in Athens, particularly in relation to the new modus operandi of business activities (Emmanouil, 2020)⁴⁴. The widespread frustration eventually led to protests and riots, leading to violence between law enforcement agents and the citizens of Athens (iEfimerida, 2021)⁴⁵

During the first phase, the Municipality of Athens in cooperation with the national government and international organizations had the central role. The municipality issued frequent COVID-19 updates on their website (ThisIsAthens.org, n.d.)⁴⁶, conducted dissemination activities utilising both traditional and contemporary means (fliers, advertisements, etc), targeting both the general population and vulnerable groups. The Greek government implemented a mobile phone service number 13033 that allowed citizens of Athens to request permission of movement during lockdowns by digitally informing the law enforcement agencies. This measure significantly helped control the spread of the pandemic in Athens, one of the municipalities with the highest human densities in Greece (GTP, 2020)⁴⁷. In addition, the municipality of Athens in collaboration with the National Public Health Organization offered free rapid COVID-19 tests in designated areas such as the subway station next to the Syntagma square (EODY, 2022)⁴⁸. Moreover, the Municipality of Athens implemented the “help at home” initiative, in which medical staff and social workers offered healthcare assistance, counselling and delivery of essential-need products to elderly citizens and people with health-related conditions in Athens (GTP, 2020)⁴⁹. Within the context of the Partnership for Healthy Cities, which was created in March 2020, in cooperation with the Hellenic Liver Patients Association “Prometheus”, the Greek Association of People Living with HIV “Positive Voice”, the City of Athens provided water, food and personal hygiene equipment (i.e. masks and gloves) and information in relation to COVID-19 to substance addicted, sex workers, migrants and homeless citizens of the municipality (Partnership for Healthy Cities, n.d.)⁵⁰.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

Since the outbreak of the pandemic until the rollout of the vaccine (T1) and from that point onwards until now (T2), CSOs in **Greece**, according to expert interviews, contributed in the response efforts by

⁴¹ <https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/561387805/ayximenos-o-kindynos-loimoxis-apo-ton-io-gia-toys-metanastes/>.

⁴² <https://www.tanea.gr/2020/03/23/greece/koronaio-pos-antidroun-oi-polites-stin-apagoreysi-kykloforias-kai-ta-ypoloipa-metra/>.

⁴³ <https://www.dianeosis.org/en/2020/04/how-greeks-live-during-the-pandemic/>.

⁴⁴ <https://www.naftemporiki.gr/finance/story/1653463/antidraseis-meta-to-neo-lockdown-stin-estiasi>.

⁴⁵ <https://www.iefimerida.gr/ellada/epeisodia-nea-smyrni-ton-gyro-toy-kosmoy-oi-eikones>.

⁴⁶ <https://www.thisisathens.org/whats-new/coronavirus-update>.

⁴⁷ <https://news.gtp.gr/2020/04/27/oecd-highlights-greece-best-practice-covid-19-mobile-app/>.

⁴⁸ <https://eody.gov.gr/stathera-simeia-komy-testing-eody/>.

⁴⁹ <https://news.gtp.gr/2020/04/01/athens-extends-help-at-home-program-support-vulnerable-groups/>.

⁵⁰ <https://partnershipforhealthycities.bloomberg.org/about/>.

collaborating with the governmental system. Expert interview findings indicate the immense importance of CSOs, who would often substantially support the governmental mechanisms, which was lacking behind in terms of healthcare capacity, as it has been weakened by the prolonged negative consequences of the financial crisis. An important lesson learned is that some CSOs are not plagued by highly complex bureaucratic mechanisms in comparison to governmental agencies, thus, have responded quickly in addressing the needs of the target groups, particularly during phase 1. Another lesson learned was that during these two phases (T1 & T2), CSOs in collaboration with governmental agency representatives, due to a lack of established protocol in relation to cooperation, were able to adapt quickly, went the extra mile with their actions, and became more innovative. They thus, addressed issues more realistically instead of completely adhering to the organizational mandate, which would confine their course of actions. Due to the changing nature of the pandemic, CSOs adapted their approaches to better address the needs of their target groups. This was particularly apparent in remote and vulnerable groups, who in most cases were marginalised⁵¹. As a response, a successful practice was developed, which was a shift-based mobile unit that provided essential need products, healthcare and provided information about the pandemic. Overall, CSOs are observed to have contributed to the social service and healthcare provision as well as risk communication and awareness raising. Regarding social and healthcare service provision, CSOs provided healthcare and counselling to vulnerable groups⁵² as well as personal hygiene and protection equipment. Moreover, CSOs collaborated with anti-violence – anti abuse, psychological and governmental networks to provide tailored solutions for target audiences. In relation to communication and awareness raising, CSOs contributed to the creation of innovative solutions such as a chat-bot for potential victims of domestic abuse. At the same time they collaborated with governmental entities in awareness raising campaigns for good hygiene practices and the vaccination campaign⁵³.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

On a nationwide scope, in **Greece**, COVID-19 had severe physical and socio-psychological consequences. Prolonged lockdowns, social isolation, loss of life, uncertainty and financial instability would cause the deterioration to the physical and mental wellbeing of both the general public and vulnerable groups. To address such challenges, bottom-up approaches from citizen-led initiatives could be observed, who were mainly engaged in the distribution of food and essential-need items. What is more, they provided more sophisticated assistance such as education and medical services, sometimes in collaboration with CSOs and the governmental mechanism (Coordination Centre for Refugees and Migrants – Municipality of Athens, n.d.)⁵⁴. Moreover, citizens would also engage in information dissemination and communication activities. According to our expert interviews, such initiatives were observed on a nationwide scope and were an integral part of the holistic response to the pandemic. Some notable initiatives in Athens are the community kitchens “[the other human](#)” (Asimakopoulos,

⁵¹ I.e. Roma, migrant and refugee communities, as well as homeless and drug addict citizens, living under the line of poverty.

⁵² Such as: Minority groups, disabled, children, elderly, citizens with no income or below the poverty line etc.

⁵³ CSOs implemented innovative strategies that would require both traditional methods such as community discussions, posters, leaflets, door-to-door visitations, street awareness raising activities and contemporary methods that involved social media information awareness activities.

⁵⁴ <https://www.acmr.gr/services/anthropon-gevmeta/>.

2020), (Alfavita, 2020), “El Chef” (Roubou and Poulis, 2020)⁵⁵, “Migrant Shelter”(Poulimeni, 2020) and in the rest of Greece, “We Stay Active, community, Solidarity”, “Coordination COVID-19: Solidarity of Thessaloniki”, “Social space Oikopolis”, “Perivolarides”, “Team of Social Solidarity of Xanthi”, “Sunday kitchen of Solidarity”, “Social shelter of migrants in Xanthi Nobody Alone”, “social medical facility and pharmacy of Chania”, or “Moria Corona awareness team” (Poulimeni, 2020)⁵⁶

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

In **Greece**, systemic capacity and capability weaknesses are observed, particularly in the implementation of policies and practices from governmental responses. CSOs have contributed to support vulnerable groups and mitigate the aforementioned vulnerabilities decisively. CSOs would utilise all means and methods of social interaction to communicate with vulnerable citizens and tend to their needs. Examples include CSOs that address domestic abuse such as Diotima (Diotima, n.d.), Agkalia, a CSO that actively support single parent families who are socio-economically challenged (Agkalia, n.d.), or AMKE Fainareti and Initiative “Ψ” that provided psychological services (Initiative “Ψ”, n.d.).

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the daily lives of both the general public and vulnerable groups in **Greece**. Nevertheless, the situation was more severe in marginalised groups who were on extreme highly populated living conditions, lacked access to healthcare or faced educational and cultural barriers (Anastasiou et al, 2021), (Bouloutza, 2021). COVID-19 did not radically change how CSOs address the needs of vulnerable groups, since, according to expert interviews, CSOs would already tend to citizens who may not belong to their primary group of attention. According to the expert interviews, vulnerability is multi-dimensional by definition and includes biological and societal characteristics, taking into account health-related, cultural, educational and financial factors. During the pandemic, CSOs would address the needs of refugees, Roma people, homeless people, drug addicts, migrants, children, victims of abuse, single parents, the elderly, and individuals that experienced employment loss due to COVID-19 among other groups. The CSOs made it clear that they do not discriminate on who received assistance and support. Concluding, during all phases of the pandemic until now (T0, T1, T2) the CSOs remained actively engaged with their networks and their collaborative relationships with governmental agencies to address issues in healthcare and mental wellbeing provision, basic need items and protective, personal hygiene equipment distribution, information and awareness raising activities in relation to COVID-19, relevant policies, measures and vaccination.

⁵⁵ <https://thepressproject.gr/o-laos-tha-sosei-ton-lao-episkepsi-sti-syllogiki-kouzina-el-chef/>.

⁵⁶ <https://gr.boell.org/el/node/6275>.

3.6 Italy

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Italy**, before the starting of pandemic, CSOs and their professional networks already took care vulnerable groups such as houseless/homeless citizens, asylum seekers, refugees and other migrants, unaccompanied migrant minors, youth with disabilities, and vulnerable women. Via their organizations, they provide multiple services, such as reintegration and rehabilitation, medical services, protection from human rights violations, legal procedures for asylum seekers and refugees in reception centres, and counselling in reception centres. The majority of CSOs interviewed stated that pandemic "awakened" local communities, resulting in the creation of a network between CSOs, public and governmental authorities, international organizations, volunteers, and residents, thus increasing cooperation on minimizing the pandemic's effects. CSOs sometimes led cooperation with authorities and other organisations at all operational levels, prompted by both direct effects of the pandemic and indirect effects, such as citizens' sense of abandonment. The pandemic proved the importance of cooperation among organizations to respond to each issue the pandemic caused, as well as to better address the general needs of vulnerable groups. Vulnerable groups specifically mentioned by the interviewees included houseless/homeless citizens, the elderly, people with disabilities or psychological health problems, drug addicts, female victims of domestic violence, migrants, and asylum seekers and refugees (including unaccompanied minors and victims of torture). Some interviewees indicated that whereas their CSOs (or other CSOs in the research site) focused on assisting specific vulnerable groups before the pandemic, the criteria used to define their target groups were loosened during the pandemic, i.e., they offered assistance to any vulnerable person in need.

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

In **Italy**, respondents reported that fear and uncertainty prevailed at the beginning of the pandemic. Respondents also testified that pre-existing vulnerabilities were exacerbated during the first lockdown. Precarious socio-economic conditions led to further difficulties in organising daily life of the organisations' target population. However, difficulties were emphasised also for the organisations' workers who had to manage the health crisis. As mentioned in D6.3, the first phase of the pandemic was the most challenging, since a sense of fear and closure dominated. Early restrictions left some people unemployed and living in the streets, especially those who were working without a contract. Reliable information was not always easily available from governmental institutions, and hence, CSOs had to operate on an ad-hoc basis. Furthermore, practitioners had to work alone because of social distancing measures, and often felt lonely.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **Italy**, during the second period, additional operational challenges were raised for CSOs. Actually, the second phase was defined as the "reaction and solidarity" phase: citizens in municipal areas were either asking for help, or volunteering in any way they could. Epidemiological work was in the centre of actions. However, refugees and other migrants still faced the same issues as in the first phase (e.g., stagnant residency processes, etc.). Subsequently, the third phase included the roll-out of vaccinations,

which was acknowledged as a key means of contrasting the pandemic's worst effects. "Solidarity" and "vaccination" were the key aspects of the third phase. Vaccination enabled the loosening of some restrictions and as a consequence the resumption of important services, such as residency processes for refugees and other migrants. However, interviewees did stress that the rollout of vaccines did not immediately mitigate all of the harms facing vulnerable groups.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved "ordinary people"

In **Italy**, due to significant regional decentralisation, the measures adopted and initiatives promoted both at the national level and "from below" have differed in number and in terms of resources allocated per region. Even inside large cities, there have been some districts more supportive than others, mainly because of higher concentration of vulnerable people, but also depending on whether relevant civil society organisations or supportive networks were already present in a given district. The city of Rome deserves attention, because it is the largest municipality in Italy and it includes, a few blocks apart, very different districts and living environments, and also because Rome suffers significantly from a housing emergency. As a matter of fact, during the pandemic, when everyone needed a house, there was a great mobilisation to respond to this problem. The municipality repeatedly asked for support from associations, both international and grassroots in different areas. One organisation that stepped up to help address the housing crisis was Binario95, which launched the online campaign #VorreiRestareACasa [I would like to stay at home] to support people in need of housing, mainly homeless, via an online fundraising. The organisation increased shelter services in its centres to provide housing and various essential services. Specific administrative subdivisions sometimes promoted initiatives informed by localised conditions and concerns. For instance, Municipality XIII Roma Aurelio promoted the solidarity service campaign La Spesa Sospesa [Suspended Spending] to create a virtuous network to support in difficulty but it was also an opportunity to revitalise and support businesses after the long period of closure. The initiatives involved residents who could leave to vulnerable people necessities that they purchased, and food merchants who collected what has been left to make it available to eventual users.

Similarly, CSOs and cultural spaces that have deep roots in particular districts sometimes offered resources to the pandemic response. For instance, Sparwasser, a café and cultural space in a popular district, was closed for COVID-19 measures. With the support of Nonna Roma, a prominent organisation in Rome, the café was turned into a shelter with about 10 beds. The initiative was made possible also thanks to people who donated via online fundraising. Moreover, Nonna Roma launched an initiative to support the distribution of food parcels to low-income families through an online fundraising and a collection of the food and other useful goods in neighbourhood squares. It is worth noting that such localised/decentralised 'solidarity from below' has also proved successful in cities such as Naples and Bologna. In Naples, activists from the EX OPG squat, set up various assistance services: The Red Phone, to report illegalities and failures in the workplaces; a helpline for the elderly; a helpline against abuse; and even a guidance helpline for how to claim and use bonuses. All these activities were reported on during the pandemic period within major communication channels, e.g., newspapers and television news. Similarly, activists from Laboratorio Salute Popolare of Bologna, together with Mediterranea and Approdi NGOs, launched a medical-psychological emergency room that allowed people to have free telephone counselling with a volunteer. This initiative was promoted on the association's Facebook channels, especially in Bologna, but it was addressed to all people in need.

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

Interviewees in **Italy** voiced critical comments, especially in regards to the centralised nature of governmental services. Since governmental responses to COVID-19 were formulated far away from local communities, they did not always appropriately address those communities' needs; some CSOs had to implement changes continuously to adapt to new ministerial decrees during the pandemic. Spaces that had been created to assist the need of certain vulnerable groups had to be adapted to the needs of other, newly-vulnerable community members. Some organizations also had to reorient their mandates, implementing services beyond their main services. Issues regarding the healthcare system were also pointed out, such as systemic gaps and weaknesses. For instance, some interviewees suggested that vulnerable groups such as houseless/homeless people were neglected by the health care system. Interviewees assessed their own and other civil society associations as crucial in the management of the pandemic in Rome, and it was mentioned that they were a key player with whom government authorities worked efficiently to provide assistance, treatments, and vaccines. Throughout the pandemic, interviewees observed that cooperation increased between governmental authorities and CSOs (here it should be noted that even during the pre-COVID era, interviewees observed a high rate of cooperation). For instance, synergies between public and civil society were substantially important in efforts to serve and manage houseless/homeless people, a quite challenging activity. Public-private synergies were identified as key dimensions in responses targeted towards vulnerable populations, and it was acknowledged that they should be continued. Regarding the interviewees own personal lives, the pandemic affected them significantly. However, they worked hard to adapt to the era by reorganizing services and spaces, as well as taking on flexible shifts, etc. Some practitioners experienced a feeling of abandonment by institutions; however, they also expressed great levels of teamwork, team spirit, and solidarity.

As concerned governmental communication campaigns, respondents were quite critical of certain weaknesses and inadequacies. Issues such as poor coordination, unclear messages, or messages not appropriate for all citizens were observed. CSOs sometimes had to react quickly to fill these gaps and inadequacies. Language barriers and cultural aspects were also mentioned – issues that CSOs had to respond to by translating official messages and adapting them to their target groups' cultural attitudes. The vaccination campaign was acknowledged by interviewees to be quite successful, but its mandatory nature created scepticism, and in some cases, mistrust. Interviewees suggested that such campaigns must explain the importance of vaccination in clear, easy-to-understand, and comprehensive ways, and that special care must be taken when addressing non-Spanish-speaking populations. With regard to vulnerable refugee and migrant populations living in camps, centres, etc., cultural aspects and language were recognized to be the most critical limitations to both COVID-19 communication campaigns and vaccination campaigns. The interviewees' CSOs helped to face these issues by preparing leaflets and educating groups.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Italy**, the CSOs represented by the interviewees, in their professional network, assist vulnerable groups such as houseless/homeless citizens, asylum seekers, refugees and other migrants, unaccompanied migrant minors, youth with disabilities, and vulnerable women. Via their organizations, they provide multiple services, such as reintegration and rehabilitation, medical services, protection from human rights violations, legal procedures for asylum seekers and refugees in reception centres, and counselling in reception centres. In Rome, each interviewee tried to support a different issue aggravated by the pandemic: houseless/homeless people; health care for the houseless/homeless population or living in precarious housing conditions; the housing and reception of asylum seekers and refugees; the shelter for mothers with minor children, located in the north of Rome. In Rome, the COVID-19 situation was never as critical as it was in other Italian cities; however, not all population groups were impacted in the same way, and pre-existing inequalities were further stressed. Thus, the need for support was acknowledged and a specific website, RomaAiutaRoma, was established to provide a range of information, including solidary initiatives and resident-led initiatives. Other initiatives, such as mobile clinics providing care for marginalized groups, also depended on community involvement. Within our expert interviews, one interviewee mentioned that the pandemic “awoke” local communities, saying that due to limited support by the government, residents took the initiative and collaborated with local CSOs to offer help to people in need of assistance. Particularly in the second phase of the pandemic, residents showed solidarity and offered help in any way they could. They started reflecting on possibilities to help the most vulnerable in their communities, and established semi-autonomous systems of support, realizing they do not necessarily need guidance from any institution. The interviewee highlighted that the pandemic made citizens more aware about vulnerable groups in their neighbourhoods, and drove them to rethink the meaning of “community”. It was further noted that local CSOs experienced increased interest on the part of volunteers who wanted to be part of the response.

Another interviewee pointed out that as concerned the vaccination campaign, collaboration between GOs, NGOs, and the communities they serve was very important. People need to receive correct information, in their native language, to make them understand the necessity of being vaccinated. Collaborating with cultural mediators was the most appropriate way to promote the vaccine, according to this interviewee. Another interviewee pointed out that the inclusion of ethnic community leaders in vaccination campaigns significantly increased the vaccination rates within their community, leaving only a very small percentage unvaccinated.

In regards to temporary or permanent community changes, the first interviewee stated that his CSO’s surrounding community is atypical because being located near a train station, it involves all the people who live there, but also those who pass through it. On one hand, the pandemic exacerbated social differences within this community, but on the other hand, it brought greater cohesion and interest among those who lived in the same spaces. According to the second interviewee, COVID-19 acted as a wake-up call for local communities, which can be observed at a higher rate of volunteer participation:

“Increased requests for volunteers to be part of the association; increased donations and financial support.” (CSO_2, Italy)

According to the third interviewee, social distancing could have a long-term negative impact for relationships in society. In particular:

“There is a difficulty that, for heaven's sake, there is a virus, of course we must be careful, but at an even deeper level, it insinuates a certain mistrust for the other person, and therefore can be dangerous. I believe that the effects of all this will be seen later on, especially on children. I believe that relationships themselves should be taken care of more, as an approach, as an exchange, as listening, in order to try to recover what the distancing has created.” (CSO_3, Italy)

3.7 Portugal

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Portugal**, the communities in the Lisbon metropolitan area (AML, Área Metropolitana de Lisboa) are characterized by their sociodemographic and cultural heterogeneity, together with the presence of multiple vulnerability factors, namely high levels of generational and shared poverty, school failure, job insecurity, lack of opportunities and low incomes. On top of that, there are descriptions of a lack of social protection, social exclusion, and multi-level discrimination. Advanced age and disability were also mentioned as existent forms of vulnerability. In terms of CSOs in the research site, there have always been helpful and cooperative relationships between different community organizations leading to the creation and implementation of responses and the provision of support to the community.

“We work with all institutions that support immigrants here in our territory and with immigrant organizations that work on specific areas of vulnerability, for example, organizations that work with single mothers, or ones that are more geared towards supporting children, so we work in articulation depending on the specificity (...)” (CSO_5, Portugal).

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

While some CSOs in **Portugal** had a decrease in activity due to the impossibility of carrying out face-to-face activities and the nature of their work being very physical, other institutions had an overwhelming increase in requests for support and were able to keep working remotely. As a result, the socio-educational nature of some of these organizations had to shift into a response to emergency kind of intervention. However, established donation-supported CSOs sometimes proved unable to scale up their activity of supporting marginalized people to the degree required by the new crisis (Mota et al., 2021). Consequently, several initiatives resorting to volunteer work were observed in AML. While some of these initiatives were primarily self-organized, some have also formed partnerships with parish councils and public institutions that allowed the interventions to go further. Additionally, municipalities, such as the Municipality of Cascais (CMC), supported CSOs' projects, namely for the delivery of essential goods (Mota et al., 2021), and several local governments have created their municipal registers, reporting high numbers of additional COVID-19 volunteers. In sum, from the beginning of the pandemic, while much of the work was done independently by pre-existent CSOs and volunteer initiatives, there was also cooperation with government institutions at a local level.

“The Parish Council at the local level also gave great support in taking meals to isolated elderly people, walking pets, and taking medicines from the pharmacy. There was this type of service more at the public level, but always the logic of proximity (...)” (CSO_2, Portugal)

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **Portugal**, regarding the following periods, from when vaccination began to influence policy (i.e., 2021), there was some recovery, especially at the economic level, due to the success of the vaccination program and the relaxation of measures. On the other hand, in terms of CSO’s responses, slightly different challenges arose. CSO’s intervention was no longer an emergency response, but they still struggled to find ways to provide reliable information and maintain the capacity to respond to the most urgent vulnerabilities. One of the challenges mentioned was trying to find ways to support children and teenagers at online schools. Later, regarding the situation during the first months of 2022, interviewees mentioned permanent changes like having a reduced number of staff. During this time, life was also slowly returning to normal, with the return of face-to-face intervention, even though some COVID-19 measures were still in place (e.g., telework and mirror teams). There was greater interaction between the communities and the organizations, but vulnerabilities remained, so the responses created in the context of confinement were maintained over time, which, in turn, favoured social cohesion.

“At the moment, our team is insufficient for so many requests for support and the kids end up spending much more time inside our facilities, that is, after the confinement phase is over, they are almost always in the association. There was a much greater affiliation here, but basic problems of the community remain (...)” (CSO_2, Portugal)

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

One of the first major impacts of COVID-19 in **Portugal**, was the shift from organisation-based volunteering to informal/direct volunteering in response to urgent needs. Informal civil society quickly mobilised to fill the void often replacing the services normally provided by public, non-profit welfare organisations, which had to be reduced or put on hold. This shift resembles what has been called 'crisis' or 'disaster' volunteering – a one-off, short-term response to emergencies (Smith et al., 2016). Crisis volunteers often react *ad hoc* and without organisational context or guidance, volunteering based on individual decision-making and own resources (Trautwein et al., 2020), usually involving daily tasks (Hustinx, 2021). This is present in many of the initiatives that took place, for instance:

- “Vizinho amigo” (Friendly neighbour), which aimed to help at-risk persons with their daily purchases, thus preventing them from being more subject to the virus.
- “Comvidas” (Withlives), which objective was raising and managing volunteers for institutions that house and provide support for the elderly.
- “Caixa Solidária” (Solidarity box), an individual and voluntary initiative based on the simple idea of setting up donation boxes with the motto of “take what you need, leave what you can”.

Additionally, local collective activities (e.g., music bands, sports, neighbourhood cultural or social support associations) also helped and, interestingly, the average age of the volunteers was lower than that of groups that were previously active in supporting the most vulnerable citizens.

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

Non-pharmaceutical interventions in **Portugal** (e.g., social distancing and school closure) were the primary measures taken by the government, which made access to essential goods and services more difficult. In addition to causing economic distress, social distancing measures had a profound impact on social lives and mental well-being. In terms of drawbacks mentioned by the CSOs representatives interviewed, there were issues regarding pandemic communication, such as information exclusion, fake news, sensationalism, and lack of transparency and consistency in the communication processes, therefore aggravating vulnerabilities for those who already had barriers in access to information. Other gaps relate to the lack of a strategic plan, the lack of availability of government social services for vulnerable groups, delays and slow responses in health and social services, low capacity of the health services and the lack of training on the part of public entities so that people's rights are assisted.

The government response had some problems, but CSOs representatives also consider that there were successful measures and evaluate the government's response positively. There were synergies between private, resident and government organizations to support the community. While public entities played a more normative role, the CSOs played an active role in direct intervention in the field. Many of the participatory processes focused on the need to guarantee support to the most vulnerable groups in terms of goods and resources, as well as to affected sectors of the economy. Other practices focused on disseminating COVID-19 information or other information pertinent to safety and well-being. Initiatives aimed to meet non-material needs less related to COVID-19 (e.g., intellectual and cultural stimulation) were also identified.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Portugal**, the interviewees' CSOs work with vulnerable groups in the research site such as the visually impaired community; communities subject to generational poverty, job insecurity and social exclusion; children and young people; and migrants with lack of social protection. Most of the other CSOs in the research site work also with groups experiencing poverty. Some of the groups identified were families with low incomes, single mothers, children and immigrants – with different organizations targeting different levels of vulnerability. Lastly, there is no mention of CSO's target groups changing throughout the pandemic (only changes in the work done and in the number of requests).

When the pandemic hit, there was a worsening of the situations of vulnerability that were already characteristic of the communities. Informal employment situations were mentioned as being especially problematic due to people lacking support and protection, being sent away, and losing their income. Other impacts reported by the CSO representatives were increases in domestic violence cases aggravated by the stress of confinement and food shortage issues. There was an aggravation in social exclusion due to some populations (namely immigrants, the elderly and people without access to media sources) being excluded from the communication practices. Regarding immigrants, there were also mentions of discrimination by health and social services and lack of representation.

“Most of the people we accompany do not have access to the internet, many of them do not have television, and they do not have access to the news, so the information was often diffuse

and confusing, especially for some of them with the lack of understanding of Portuguese. There was a lot of information that came to them sometimes from unreliable sources (...) which was later determinant in the incidence of the disease in this community” (CSO_5, Portugal)

“The entire elderly population is the most vulnerable because they are already quite vulnerable, due to their dependence on families, the community, and external help. The isolation that was imposed created a major limitation in communication and access to digital platforms for access to the most diverse services. With the reduction of aid provided by the most diverse institutions, this population was left extremely isolated and with few resources to react.” (CSO_3, Portugal)

In the face of such negative impacts, CSOs took action to address changes and provide support.

“It was our biggest work during the confinement, the support for distance school. These young people already have aggravated situations of inequality of opportunities at school. Many of them do not have a computer. The association has a digital inclusion centre where many of these young people used to go. We had to close doors, so the support was provided from a distance, sometimes with telephones from neighbours who lent them so they could attend classes; we collected computers from the parish council, second-hand things to try to meet the needs” (CSO_2, Portugal)

3.8 Spain

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Spain**, the interviews were conducted in the city of Madrid with representatives of civil society organisations specialising in the care of vulnerable women. The context, therefore, is that of a large metropolitan city, with high living costs, which concentrates a higher percentage than the national average of foreign residents, mainly Latin Americans and North Africans. The economic crisis of 2008 and its negative consequences were still affecting workers when the pandemic hit. The financial crisis led to high levels of unemployment, a loss of purchasing power and precarious working conditions. These trends particularly affected foreign workers. Indeed, some migrants returned to their countries of origin because they could not cope with over-indebtedness and lack of employment. These returns weakened households, family and mutual support networks among migrants of the same origin. Changes in labour regulations in 2010 and 2012 contributed to employment growth at the cost of widespread use of temporary, part-time contracts with very precarious coverage in case of unemployment, illness, etc. This type of contract is the most common in the sectors where the activity of foreign workers legally residing in the country is concentrated: domestic service, home care for the elderly, children and the sick, work in bars, shops, restaurants and the tourist sector, small family businesses, etc. Immigrants in an irregular administrative situation – without residence and work permits – are forced into the underground economy where conditions of exploitation, precariousness and lack of labour rights are practically total. These trends affect migrant women workers in particular. On the other hand, the cuts in public services and social assistance that were imposed to meet deficit reduction targets did not mitigate the negative effects of the economic crisis on vulnerable populations. It is in this sphere that CSOs are working when the pandemic hits the country.

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

At the beginning of the pandemic, in **Spain** the CSOs interviewed were forced to cover activities that were interrupted mainly due to a lack of means of protection. There were times when CSOs found it difficult to meet the needs, either because they did not have the necessary equipment or human resources. The gradual introduction of restrictions required a change in the activities that CSOs used to carry out and a shift to providing immediate relief, such as food, goods and services. Their work shifted to mainly assisting by phone or with face-to-face visits to homes or on the street to provide an immediate response. Volunteering was also essential for the continuation of their activities. Their role in managing and cooperating with other organisations and public institutions was crucial in solving multiple problems and mitigating the impact of COVID-19, as well as helping vulnerable groups to contact the right organisation and seek help instantly.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **Spain**, after the first period of the pandemic, interviewees indicated that many of their organisations' activities shifted towards digitalisation. However, street work continued, as well as frequent visits to needy families to provide them with basic needs such as food, clothes and even computers. As public administrations closed during the lockdowns, CSOs operated continuously to accompany the most vulnerable people – especially women – throughout the pandemic, despite strict restrictions on confinement and mobility. With the gradual lifting of restrictions, in the "new normal" phase, most CSOs partially resumed face-to-face activities to assist citizens, mainly in terms of food distribution, which they began to carry out on site at their own headquarters, through a system of prior appointments, to avoid crowds of people.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

In Spain, multiple volunteering and solidarity initiatives were put in place to respond to the different areas where people needed support due to the pandemic. For example, volunteers sent letters of solidarity to people suffering from isolation and loneliness⁵⁷, several platforms were created to connect people offering support with those requesting it⁵⁸, telephone support lines were introduced⁵⁹, or virtual meeting spaces were created for the exchange of actors from different sectors⁶⁰. The Rey Juan Carlos University created an initiative to help elderly people take out the rubbish during the state of alarm in Madrid⁶¹. A group from Metro de Madrid has mobilised thousands of people through social

⁵⁷ <https://www.madridiario.es/cartas-para-paliar-soledad-enfermos-coronavirus>.

⁵⁸ <https://www.hacesfalta.org/oportunidades/iniciativas/buscador/>.

⁵⁹ <https://www.idea-alzira.com/becamos>.

⁶⁰ <https://diarioresponsable.com/noticias/29234-fundacion-hazloposible-continua-apoyando-la-labor-solidaria-gracias-a-forgood-es>.

⁶¹ <https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/El-Ayuntamiento/Todas-las-noticias/Madrid-se-suma-a-YoTeAyudoConLaBasura-jovenes-dispuestos-a-bajar-la-basura-a-quien-lo-necesite/?vgnnextfmt=default&vgnnextoid=8c0eea44a7b21710VgnVCM2000001f4a900aRCRD&vgnnextchannel=e40362215c483510VgnVCM2000001f4a900aRCRD>.

networks to raise funds for vulnerable people⁶². With their initiative, they were able to provide resources for health centres, the elderly, basic necessities or food for vulnerable people. From an operational point of view, the participation of citizens as volunteers was essential, their initiatives enabled many organisations to scale up interventions locally and ensured that CSOs were able to maintain their response, despite the increased demand for aid. In the Spanish case, the exponential growth and diversity of social initiatives created by civil society, community associations and self-organised neighbours to create mutual aid networks during the pandemic demonstrated, on the one hand, the absorption capacity and social resilience of grassroots organisations and ordinary citizens at both national and local levels and, on the other, the capacity to scale up citizen self-organisation from the local level, generating community solutions that in some cases were replicated nationally and internationally.

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

From the beginning of the State of Alarm in **Spain**, the CSOs interviewed claimed to be on the frontline providing health and social services to mitigate the social impact of the health crisis. Most CSOs claim that, in the first months of the pandemic, these organisations were the only ones in charge of providing social services to the most vulnerable populations (migrants, vulnerable women, homeless people, etc.), who were the most difficult for the administration to reach. These organisations claim that public institutions closed due to the State of Alarm and that the digital transition of local administrations to provide services to citizens was slow. Consequently, CSOs had to fill this gap during the first stage of the health crisis. In this regard, the main challenge mentioned by most CSOs was to continue to socially support the most vulnerable people – especially women – throughout the pandemic, despite severe restrictions on lockdown and mobility. Thus, the lockdown, while forcing most internal procedures to be carried out telematically or remotely from home, also meant a greater presence of CSOs on the streets. Many CSOs moved out of their offices to provide an immediate response on the street. This meant a radical change in the usual intervention logic of several of the CSOs consulted. Although Spanish CSOs in Madrid do not usually offer welfare service programmes or the provision of basic subsistence goods, during the pandemic many of the Madrid CSOs had to change their functions and programmes to adapt to the new social reality imposed by the health crisis. Thus, they put aside their usual programmes of awareness-raising and advocacy with public decision-makers to focus on contingency measures aimed at providing food, goods and basic necessities not only to vulnerable families but also to families facing a lack of solvency due to the impact of COVID-19, especially in the first months of the pandemic.

At the operational level, CSOs fulfilled two functions: on the one hand, they changed the way of attending to citizens from face-to-face to telematic or telephone; on the other hand, they provided immediate response to the needs of people seeking help directly in their homes or by attending to them in the street: using vans, either delivering food door-to-door every 15 days or using them as mobile offices to help the population to carry out telematic procedures for applying for social aid (unemployment benefits, subsistence allowances, applying for appointments to renew documents

⁶²<https://www.metromadrid.es/en/press-release/2020-05-10/an-initiative-by-metro-de-madrids-employees-raises-over-eu110-000-to-fight-covid-19>.

with immigration authorities etc). A key factor in this process was the involvement of citizens as volunteers, whose help enabled many organisations to expand their interventions at the local level and thus respond to the exponential increase in demands for social assistance triggered by the onset of the State of Alarm.

In terms of management and implementation during the health crisis, the CSOs interviewed reported playing a coordinating and collaborative role with other institutions and social actors. Within the framework of the Madrid City Council's Municipal Emergency Territorial Plan (PEMAM), CSOs acted jointly in coordination with public administrations, especially with the Madrid City Council, mainly in the phase of mobility restrictions (after the lockdown) to provide an immediate response to people requesting social assistance, either by referring these people to the City Council's social services or by providing certain services from the CSOs themselves, but with funding from the local public administration. Likewise, the CSOs consulted also highlight the prioritisation of networking between CSOs, through collaboration in joint interventions, basically sharing resources (logistical, material and human) to respond to the needs of the people who requested assistance throughout the health crisis, especially during the months of confinement. Here it is also necessary to include collaboration with the private sector. Particularly relevant was the role of CSOs as intercultural mediators between public administrations, especially at the local level, and the most vulnerable people seeking help, for example among sexually exploited women, migrant women in an irregular administrative situation and homeless people. In all these cases, the CSOs' action contributed to bringing public administration closer to these populations that it does not normally reach, overcoming linguistic, cultural and digital barriers, among others.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Spain**, Government measures to deal with the pandemic brought economic activity to a screeching halt, especially in sectors where migrant women workers are concentrated. Fear of contagion also led many families to lay off domestic workers and caregivers. Many women suddenly found themselves without work, with no income to meet daily household expenses. In general, the profile of vulnerable women does not change with the pandemic: it aggravates the situation of households that were already in a precarious economic and employment situation and increases the demand for social assistance, especially from families that until the pandemic had managed to stay afloat without assistance, or with minimal public support. Households without savings, family support or day-to-day living expenses were the hardest hit: demand for food, hygiene and virus protection products and household goods skyrocketed. In short, the pandemic has increased the size of the vulnerable population and aggravated the situation of those already worst off.

A number of profiles of particularly vulnerable women emerge from the interviews:

Second-generation migrants: young women who have not completed compulsory education, migrants or nationals whose parents are foreigners.

Single-parent households: women with dependent children.

Women who are in charge of two families: one in Spain and the other in their country of origin, which they support with their income.

Women who come from Africa and do not speak Spanish properly.

Women, especially young women, who arrived just before the pandemic and who lacked support networks.

Older women who have lost their jobs and, because of their age, have very little chance of finding them again.

Women victims of gender-based violence, who have been forced to live with their aggressor while in confinement.

Women affected by the digital divide: they do not have devices, internet connections and/or sufficient skills to carry out transactions digitally.

In addition to vulnerability linked to poverty, precarious employment or problems with language or access to technologies, migrant women during the pandemic have experienced health problems. These groups carry out tasks that involve personal relationships, for example: domestic service, caring for people or customer service, so they have had to go to their jobs to carry out essential tasks for the community. In short, they have been more exposed to illness because they cannot work from home. In some cases, the most vulnerable immigrant women have not had sufficient medical care due to delays in the processing of administrative files for foreigners, the management of health cards for immigrants and the impossibility of managing their health demands through the telematic and telephonic means provided by the health administration during the first months of the pandemic.

Finally, the emotional stress to which they have been subjected as a result of the economic difficulties they and their children have suffered, not being able to cover their most basic needs, not being able to send money to their families in their countries of origin, seeing how their children could not continue their studies properly because they did not have computers or good internet connections, and this has led them to suffer from mental problems such as anxiety or depression. Regarding possible changes in vulnerable communities or women affected by the pandemic, the organisations consulted are generally sceptical. In this sense, they consider that it is either too early to speak of hypothetical changes in behaviour, and even more so of lasting changes in Madrid society, or that, if such changes have taken place, they have been insufficient to modify the situation of vulnerability. On the other hand, with the new normality, some of these organisations express their concern about observing greater gaps in the health and social services of the public administrations for the care of the most vulnerable populations, in this case vulnerable women, which means that, after the health crisis, the vulnerability of these people may have continued to increase.

3.9 Sweden

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Sweden**, the chosen research site consists of two North-Eastern suburbs in Gothenburg, Bergsjön and Hjällbo. The sites are characterized as extremely diverse, both regarding residents' backgrounds and their attitudes and behaviour. Specifically, the research site is described by one interviewee as "very segregated" and "full of immigrants [from different countries] speaking different languages". Other interviewees mentioned that the research sites and adjacent neighbourhoods are different in terms of receptivity to health information. The sites are inhabited by migrants coming from different backgrounds and speaking many different languages. They also have lower socio-economic status than the Gothenburg average:

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2020	Bergsjön	Hjällbo	Gothenburg city, total
Residents born in other country	59,8 %	59,4 %	27,8 %
Residents with at least one parent born in another country	82,5 %	86,9%	37,5 %
Average annual income, personal (2019)	201,200 SEK	197,600 SEK	326,100 SEK
Unemployment	18.1 %	19.3 %	8.3 %
Post-college education, 3 yrs or more	17 %	14.7 %	37.3 %
Share of self-sufficiency	0.4	0.4	1.2
Own apartment/house	16.6 %	8.6 %	46.5 %

Table 1. Gothenburg City (2023).

The interviews revealed that many of the residents in the target area are poorly integrated with Swedish society and words as “gap”, “two cities” or “two societies” were used to metaphorically describe the remoteness between the general Swedish society and the target area. But there is also segregation between different cultural and ethnic groups in the neighbourhoods. All interviewees argued that the target group often had little education and language skills, both in their native languages and in Swedish, as well as low health literacy. All interviewees emphasised the vast prevalence of distrust for Swedish society including politics, media, the welfare system, etc. Also, groups with migration backgrounds were characterized as holders of incorrect information about the pandemic, and as vulnerable to a disinformation and myths regarding the virus, the vaccine, and the government’s intentions with it.

Several different CSOs were present in the research area already before the outbreak of the pandemic, of which several were sports, cultural and religious organisations. Also, already before the outbreak of the pandemic, so called “cultural guides” and “health guides” were present in the research area. Cultural guides (female and male) are recruited from migrant-dense suburbs, they share a linguistic and cultural background with asylum seekers and other migrants and provide support for the difficulties these people face in the Swedish society. “Cultural guides” work from family centres, childcare centres, or midwife’s offices. He or she provides information about cultural differences and how the Swedish society works. This may involve children’s rights, maternal and child health care, vaccinations, parental allowance, civil registration, equal parenting and what to do when a child becomes ill. “Health guides” are trained to inform about and discuss health issues (food habits, sleep, stress, exercise, other issues that affect health), and to raise health issues in their networks. Anyone that speaks several languages and understands Swedish may train to be a health guide. The training is provided by the city of Gothenburg. Being a “health guide” is a voluntary and unpaid assignment. The activities of “cultural guides” and “health guides” in the research area is financed by public means from the city of Gothenburg and the Västra Götalandsregionen, but the guides also work close together with CSOs in the area.-In general, the efforts of different CSOs during the pandemic was spontaneous and based on individual initiatives. As a consequence, their work was - at least at the beginning of the pandemic - poorly coordinated, both between CSOs and between CSOs and government authorities (Johansson, 2022).

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

It is worth noticing, that **Sweden** never implemented a total lockdown. Most CSOs involving children’s activities, especially outdoors activities like sports, went on as usual through the whole pandemic. Also, special activities were initiated during the pandemic, like inviting participants to F2F activities and children and parents to arts and crafts events, as well as offering more opening hours at a local youth

centre. Most CSOs targeting adults stopped F2F-meetings due to risk of infection and switched to digital meetings and activities. Also, some new digital activities were initiated due to the pandemic, e.g., local Facebook pages that invited people to assist each other in different ways (grocery shopping, outdoor meetings), urged people feeling isolated to gather outdoors for coffee and information about the pandemic and discussions about false information and spreading of rumours. It was soon realised that it was more difficult to reach out with the vaccine in areas with many foreign-born residents and among people with lower education and low wages, while the spread of infection was relatively high within these groups. During the pandemic and especially during the vaccination campaign, the “cultural guides” and “health guides” were renamed as “vaccination guides”. They visited residents, approached them in their own language, informed about the vaccine, and where and when it was available.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

In **Sweden**, during the first and second time period (pre-vaccine), the Swedish Corona strategy differed from other European countries with no obvious lockdowns. Thus, it is difficult to describe the impact of COVID-19 in terms of time periods defined by policy changes. In addition, the interviewees’ mission as “vaccination guides” was initiated as the vaccinations launched.

During the third period (post-vaccine), all interviewees argued that their and their “vaccination guide” colleagues’ hard work paid off, and that the vaccination rates increased immensely since the initiative was launched. There was a change of attitude towards vaccinations among the target group, from great scepticism to a larger amount of acceptance. The sub-area of northeast Gothenburg, Angered, is the area with the most significant increase of vaccination rates. As restrictions were gradually withdrawn, CSOs and “vaccination guides” returned to their ordinary activities.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

In **Sweden**, activities initiated by individual citizens during the pandemic aimed at the local community or even at a single neighbourhood (help with shopping, exchange of domestic services, informal FAQs on COVID-19, exchange of experiences from infection). Initiatives taken by organizations mainly targeted specific groups or segments in society. For example, specific professions and industries (healthcare workers, artists, tech, and IT sectors) or specific demographic groups (migrants, youths, children, elderly).

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

In **Sweden**, while online initiatives taken by public authorities, such as the municipality of Gothenburg, targeted vulnerable groups (vulnerable women, addicts, and the homeless), activities initiated by individual citizens aimed at the local community or even at a single neighbourhood (help with shopping, exchange of domestic services, informal FAQs on COVID-19, exchange of experiences from infection). Initiatives taken by organizations mainly target specific groups or segments in society. For example, specific professions and industries (healthcare workers, artists, tech, and IT sectors) or specific demographic groups (migrants, youths, children, elderly).

According to the interviewed “vaccination guides” they collaborated during the pandemic with other associations and medical centres working with similar goals, which was to inform about and increase vaccination rate in the research area. Meetings were arranged where they got together and could ask e.g. medical questions to medical professionals as well as get support and feedback from peers. The different representatives and organisations also had WhatsApp-groups where they could help each other out. The “vaccination guides” mainly filled in the information gaps/lacunae left by official health authorities who did not manage to reach out – or reach in – to the migrant population, due either to language difficulties, distrust, or both. All interviewees argued that the hard work paid off and that the vaccination rates increased immensely since the initiative was launched. There was a change of attitude towards vaccinations among the target groups, from great scepticism to more acceptance:

“For me, the best praise has been looking at the data. Before we started, perhaps 30% of the people living in the northeast had received vaccination. After two months of working worth this, it was almost 50%” (CSO_5, Sweden).

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Sweden**, since our research site is in migrant dense suburbs, the vulnerable group includes migrants from many different countries. Among them, there are variations in vulnerability due to age, general health conditions, overcrowded housing, and overrepresentation of people having exposed occupations. Our interviewees approached all these vulnerable persons. This did not change during the pandemic. The pandemic highlighted the vulnerability of people living in crowded households and having exposed professions, e.g., taxi drivers, supermarket cashiers, employees in retirement homes and home care services. First responders, e.g., persons working within health care and elderly care, were first affected by covid-19 infections, and anxiety with the situation. None of the above-mentioned circumstances were brought forward in the interviews.

3.10 Wales

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

In **Wales**, the Swansea Metropolitan Area can be characterised as the second largest urban area in Wales. Strong bonds geographically in the smaller deprived areas in Swansea County, though communities had mostly formed around gender, ethnicity, age, faith, and family histories of deep poverty. It’s an area that has many deprived areas; in particular, the villages north and east of Swansea city centre are poor (e.g. Morriston, Clydach, Pontardawe, Blaen-Y-Maes, Langyfelach), as are some urban neighbourhoods in Swansea (e.g. Sandfields, Sketty, Townhill). Swansea Council support for deprived communities (in accordance with the Welsh Government statistic) had initially been organised around the themes of employability, health, and education, but in 2018 it changed to mostly employability. Prior to the pandemic, the Swansea Metropolitan Area was characterised by socio-economic inequalities that follow ethnicity and gender lines with informally organised support networks and poverty levels that had very little capacity for setbacks. In Pembrokeshire, Gypsy Roma

Travellers (GRTs) are the largest ethnic minority, and they have been welcome there. However, in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot they experience more stigmatisation and racism. For refugees and asylum seekers, Swansea is found to have a particularly cohesive and collaborative network (Welsh Government 2023)

Changing impacts and responses throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

CSOs contribution to crisis management in the research site during the period T1

CSOs in **Wales** seemed to work with local and national governments where they had collaborative structures set up prior to the pandemic. For instance, a Stakeholder Engagement Officer at Public Health Wales explains that they liaised between the public health and environmental health teams of the Health Board, the Local Authority Staff, and underserved communities already and continued to do so after the start of the pandemic in Wales. A Community Engagement Officer employed by a local Council added that the CSOs already in their network regularly asked for community-based support that was often rapidly honoured. Therefore, local authorities seemed to be open to be told what CSO/community initiative to resource, especially during the early stages of the pandemic, and right until the behavioural measures were lifted in 2022.

Two Community Engagement Officers that were interviewed for this project were well-networked with different minority ethnic groups in the Swansea Metropolitan Area. They explained how responses from these communities in Wales took place in the form of dedicated programmes from existing organisations that had received funding from the framework offered by the Welsh government and local councils. For instance, the pre-existing and Wales-oriented organisation ‘Diverse Cymru’ created a BAME Mental Health Online/Telephone support project in December 2020 to support Black, Asian, and minority ethnic people across Wales who struggled with their mental health during the pandemic. Furthermore, at Council level, representatives of the BAME communities in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot launched a campaign to dispel fear and mistrust about the vaccination programme to encourage people to get vaccinated. This ‘Tell Me More Campaign’ signposts to correct information from local BAME medical practitioners, faith and community leaders.

CSOs that did not already work with national and local authorities before the pandemic responded by pointing out deficiencies in the pandemic policies. A women’s labour organisation wrote reports after collecting data on gender disparities in the effects of the pandemic measures and support structures. A research manager interviewee explained:

“From an ordinary women’s perspective, yes, unpaid labour has never been recognized. And in the pandemic, the inequalities exacerbated because of this problem. I just wanted to highlight it because as it comes, this was not reflected in the regulations of pandemic, so the policies are not prepared from a gender mainstreaming perspective, and this became a very big issue, because they prepared the policies from a very kind of a linear, very orthodox employment perspective. (...) But they never talked about these unpaid labour issues in those contexts (...) The policy was created gender blind, and it affected women’s life very, very badly in the beginning of the pandemic.” (CSO_1, Wales)

They argued that the Welsh government had a structure to govern labour that was already largely insensitive to a gendered labour market, which they identified to prohibit exacerbating gender inequalities during the pandemic. In addition to the differences on the labour market, the interviewee

from the women's labour organisation noted how women were also more vulnerable than men in the organisation of their everyday life:

“The support network carries part of our society, whether it is recognized or not. So the problem is that the pandemic made us recognize it, but it's already there. (...) So we need to care, this is our very existence, but in that existence, we lost the support network. So we are isolated and lost the caring community (...) We lost a very essential thing that makes us a society, you know, the support network. And I think this affects women quite a lot.” (CSO_1, Wales)

They continue with pointing out how their research demonstrates that the majority of domestic work and home-schooling fell disproportionately on women's shoulders during the spring 2020 lockdown and autumn/winter lockdown of 2021. As such, they organised several campaigns to get women's pandemic plights to the attention of businesses to improve flexible working. They already had guidelines about efficient flexible working and remote working, and they gave webinars on this and effective support provision for women employees, as well as directly to women.

CSOs also found each other when realising a shared problem for the vulnerable groups they work with and represent. During the early stages of the pandemic, a new partnership was set up between EYST, ProMo Cymru, Citizen's Advice Cymru, Women Connect First, and other stakeholders that is represented on its website as follows: The Multi-lingual Helpline Wales, which is a national helpline providing information, referral and signposting individuals to specialist advice, mainstream and community organisations. This participative action was mostly organised by and aimed at BAME groups who are vulnerable psychologically, linguistically, and/or do not have the capacity to find credible useful information about the pandemic themselves. It was funded by the *Welsh Government's Voluntary Sector Emergency Fund*.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

According to Community Engagement Officer 1, in **Wales**, the effects of the Councils' retrieval and claw-back of targeted subsidies to vulnerable communities (i.e. homeless people, refugees, and asylum seekers) in the Swansea Metropolitan Area undoes vital work to battle inequality. These groups were found to land back on the street after accommodation resources had been cut, and COVID-19-safe activities for refugees and asylum seekers were stopped. For GRTs this time period was characterised by the realisation on the sites that more people were dying from infection with the virus and, as a result, more people came forward to be vaccinated. As such, the Engagement Officer organised vaccine vans to be parked outside the campsites, so that if people decided to have the vaccine it was immediately available. The representative from the Women's organisation argued that women who were more likely to have been keyworkers (e.g. cleaners in hospitals) had had a very difficult time in the sense that they had more demands placed on them, for instance, in terms of the intensity of jobs and childcare. Aside from facing worse mental illness, and disproportionately having taken care of home-schooling without their care network, it emerged that self-employed women could not benefit from the self-employment schemes in the same ways men could. With the appearance of the 'Cost of Living' crisis in the wider UK, in this period it became clearer that women were affected much worse than men, as they are much more likely to live in poverty, particularly if they're single parents.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research site that actively involved “ordinary people”

In the Swansea Metropolitan Area in **Wales**, ‘ordinary people’ got involved in pandemic practices in several ways. According to Community Engagement Officer 2, many helped out locally by making and distributing food parcels, and recreating a care structure that attended to needs around food and medicine provision and in terms of improving mental health. Community Engagement Officer 1 added the following:

“The most vulnerable families have been provided help by someone within the neighbourhood by that family, they were not relatives, but because they thought that’s their responsibility to go out and help and support. And there are so many other examples, say, SCVS [Swansea Council for Voluntary Service] had, I think, more than 1000 volunteers, you know. People come in, and just volunteer.” (CSO_2, Wales)

In addition, ordinary people found each other in neighbourhood support groups that consisted of people who ‘represented’ their street and were the go-to person for practical issues such as picking up groceries for people who were shielding, picking up medication, dog walking, checking in with lonely people, and organising other things. These ‘Street Champions’ were not clinically vulnerable, but the group was likely to have included socio-economically vulnerable people. These groups very active on Facebook during the first lockdown rapidly disappeared over the summer 2020 when the first lockdown was over. Many were not re-started in the winter 2021 lockdown.

Local impacts and gaps of governmental responses in the research site, CSOs and participatory practices

Where certain social groups underperformed in the vaccine uptake rates in the area, in **Wales**, CSOs and community organisations collaborated with local authorities through community engagement officers. Participatory practices were organised to culminate in the deployment of a ‘vaccine van’ in 2021 and 2022 in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot municipalities. Stocked with AstraZeneca and Moderna vaccines, the van was driven to sites where particular groups come together and/or operate. One such site is a church that serves people with Caribbean origin, another a mosque, and the route also included certain streets to invite sex workers to have a vaccine.

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management (T0, T1, T2)

CSO engagement with vulnerable groups, changing or emerging vulnerabilities, and CSO responses to address these vulnerabilities

In **Wales**, the vulnerable groups that were worked with by the interviewees include women, minority ethnic groups, refugees and asylum seekers, Muslim faith groups, Gypsy Roma Travellers, and people with low socio-economic status in Swansea, Neath Port Talbot, as well as broader South Wales. These groups did not change as the CSOs had their communities they work with and advocated for. Gypsy Roma Traveller communities in Wales were already seen as vulnerable before the pandemic; mostly because they wanted to limit government interference in their life, which made the relationship with authorities challenging. Before the pandemic some sort of balance had been established, however, during the pandemic the authorities interfered further which caused disruptions in the lives of these communities. In particular, their mobile lifestyles were disrupted, and their income stopped as many

Gypsy Travellers rely on working on the land, scrap, collection, and selling objects, and doing horse sales. The TGP Cymru interviewee explained:

“The women will go on benefits because they've got children, and they've got to make sure that they've got money coming in for the children. (...) The men would not claim benefits, they wouldn't go on to Universal Credit or anything or wouldn't claim benefits because they were getting their own money's coming in. And even though a lot of them would have to claim through businesses, certain people obviously still – they didn't take off the government what they didn't give to the government in a way. Yeah, a lot of the families did have to go on to Universal Credit that was never dreamed of having to do that in the past, because they had money coming in.” (CSO_3, Wales)

Not claiming benefits in the complete absence of people's own income thus was a new reason for this group to become financially vulnerable. Via Facebook Messenger the TGP Cymru interviewee and their colleagues were asked to apply for Universal Credit on behalf of community members. Their status as vulnerable group prior to the pandemic was deepened further in another way. Gypsy and traveller communities have an average life expectancy of 20 years less than that of the settled communities. The interviewee from CSO 'TGP Cymru' stated that this is because medical attention is not often sought. In the first pandemic year, therefore, the charity *Friends, Family and Travellers* helped individual GRTs navigate the registration system of General Practitioners and receive medical support.

4 Discussion

In this report, good practices and lessons learned can be identified, while examining three distinct time periods which entail local multi-stakeholder responses. Throughout the report, a particular focus is placed upon the conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management.

The **main lessons learned** that are identified when the first phase is examined (*Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic*) are that in all countries, the target municipalities/sub-municipal areas can be characterised as high-density, culturally heterogenous, and in some cases highly segregated⁶³ areas, in which a plethora of vulnerable groups reside. Prior to the COVID-19 outbreak, indicators of vulnerability were already present, which were rapidly amplified due to the negative consequences of the pandemic. The vulnerable groups present in most COVINFORM countries include: persons with precarious working and/or living situations; ethnic and religious minorities (i.e. Pomaki, Armenian, Romani, Jewish, etc.); refugees and other migrants; houseless/homeless persons; unaccompanied minors; substance abusers; persons with disabilities; vulnerable women, such as victims of domestic abuse; etc. In most if not all target states, the pre-existing indicators of vulnerability identified are: poverty, poor health conditions, low skill and employment rates, high rates of unemployment and job insecurity, and low income, whereas in some cases, social exclusion, lack of social protection, and multi-level discrimination were also reported⁶⁴.

Good practices that are identified during the first phase include the utilisation of pre-existing CSO networks who actively worked with vulnerable target groups and provided services such as reintegration and rehabilitation, medical services, protection from human rights violations, legal procedures and counselling for asylum seekers and refugees in reception centres, etc.; the established existence of such services allowed CSOs to better mitigate the consequences of COVID-19. To increase their effectiveness, in most countries⁶⁵, CSOs actively engaged with local communities at all operational levels, expanding their networks and establishing cooperation with public authorities, international organizations, volunteers, and residents. These cooperative relationships led to targeted implementations of responses, and provided much needed support to the community. The implementation of “health/cultural guides” and “health centers” can also be considered as a good practice, which was implemented in Sweden. Local residents, who share the same linguistic and cultural background with vulnerable groups take up this voluntary role to provide support and information in all challenges these communities may face. This may include information regarding children's rights, maternal and child health care, vaccinations, parental allowance, civil registration, equal parenting and what to do when a child becomes ill, information on cultural differences and various health issues. Health/cultural guides receive their training was provided by the city of Gothenburg and during the first phase they cooperated with CSOs, however these initiatives were spontaneous, thus, cooperation between CSOs and governmental authorities did not achieve the desired coordination rate.

Factors contributing to changes in CSO responses between T1 and T2

⁶³ Such as in Sweden and Portugal.

⁶⁴ Such as in Portugal, Wales, and Spain.

⁶⁵ Such as in Italy and Portugal, among other COVINFORM countries.

During the second and third phase, the implementation of policies and measures as well as the emergence of new variants and the availability of the vaccine brought fourth changes and developments within CSOs and local communities.

The **main lessons learned** during the following two phases (T1 and T2) is that in all COVINFORM countries, vulnerabilities were exacerbated within the target communities, including as a direct result of governmental responses. In all cases, non-pharmaceutical interventions were implemented to contain the spread of the virus, generally including measures that restricted face-to-face interaction to various degrees; these measures often led to reduced access to services and support, and limited the range of activities which CSOs could perform. In all COVINFORM countries, CSOs experienced disruptions in their operations; in some cases, CSOs even consciously disregarded certain regulations in order to keep their services available. In most cases, the frequent changing of relatively vague top-down rules required constant readjustment, which led to tension and confusion. The rapid shift to remote work also not only posed challenges for CSOs, but proved very challenging for target groups with a lack of internet connectivity and/or technological skills or means. Another challenge faced by CSOs was to ensure the acquisition of personal protective equipment and hygiene equipment (e.g., masks) and achieve a balance between service provision and the minimisation of COVID-19 transmission. When certain CSOs became unable to continue their operations, other CSOs in the same community could become overwhelmed due to increased demand and a lack of resources (e.g., cascading failures could occur). A positive finding across most target countries was that relatively good cooperation between CSOs and public authorities continued throughout all phases of the pandemic, actively mitigating its negative consequences.

A **good practice** which was observed in all target countries, was the comparatively rapid adaptation of operations within CSOs, particularly the shift to a remote or hybrid provision of services. In many – though not all – cases, CSOs were able to adapt and continue to provide their services remotely via online portals, social media platforms, telephone, and even by using the radio. Another good practice was the implementation of Mutual Aid Groups (MAGs) and the active contribution of the VCFSE⁶⁶ sector, i.e., established networks of organisations and volunteers that engaged in the coordination of initiatives and reacted to the needs of vulnerable groups immediately, providing COVID-19 information, counselling, welfare services, etc. The initiative “help at home” within the context of the Partnership for Healthy Cities, implemented in Greece, can be considered as an example, as it provided healthcare assistance, counselling, delivery of essential need products and personal hygiene items to vulnerable groups such as the elderly. In all countries, CSOs, public authorities, and grassroots initiatives utilised both classical and online information channels to increase awareness in their target populations (social media platforms, fliers, advertisements, etc). An example is the establishment of online/telephone mental health support in several countries, for instance, in Wales, where services were particularly targeted to support Black, Asian, and minority ethnic (BAME) groups who struggled with their mental health during the pandemic. Moreover, in several sites, awareness raising campaigns (such as the ‘Tell Me More Campaign’ in Wales) were implemented in order to dispel mistrust and fear in relation to vaccination campaigns, particularly targeting vulnerable populations whilst engaging “multipliers” with connections to vulnerable groups, such as BAME medical practitioners, faith-based organisations, and community leaders. This practice was also noted in Sweden, which utilised bicultural “vaccination guides” who would raise awareness and dispelled misinformation revolving

⁶⁶ Voluntary, Community, Faith, and Social Enterprise (VCFSE), a term which originates from England.

around vaccines. In conclusion, another highly successful practice was the implementation of shift-basis mobile units and vaccination vans, for instance in Greece and Wales, which distributed personal protective equipment (i.e., masks), raised information awareness, and conducted tests and vaccinations.

Participatory practices that emerged in the research sites that actively involved “ordinary people”

Lessons learned in relation to participatory practices include the active engagement of citizens in a variety of solidarity activities aimed to mitigate the negative socio-economic consequences of COVID-19. This phenomenon was observed in all COVINFORM target countries and can simultaneously be considered to be **good practices**, especially as no negative impacts that derived from such activities can be observed. In all countries, services to vulnerable groups can be identified within the following thematic areas:

- a) Provision of items – essential goods (such as food) and personal protective equipment.
- b) Provision of services – counselling, support, assistance with everyday activities (such as shopping), and information/awareness-raising activities.

These CSO and citizen initiatives helped fill the gaps in governmental responses in all COVINFORM research sites, particularly via active engagement with target groups in information and awareness-raising, provision of goods and hygiene items, and provision of services.

Representative examples of such citizen initiatives are:

- *Austria*: Pro-Hund, Team Österreich Nachbarschaftshilfe, Long COVID-19 Austria, HaltDerGewalt, Plaudertischerl initiative, Nachbarschafts-Telefon.
- *Belgium*: Sensi Ambassadors, “Antwerp Helps” platform, Coronababbels, “t Werkhuys” food distribution initiative.
- *England*: Community Action Response, Local Governments Association (LGA), The National Lottery Community Fund, Nextdoor, Neighbourhood Watch, Campaign to End Loneliness, Eco Attractions Group, COVID-19 Mutual Aid Harborne, Acocks Green Together, Coronavirus Tech Handbook, Trees for Cities.
- *Germany*: Bürgeraktiv – das Engagementportal, #Nachbarschaftschallenge, Gabenzaun, Quaranteen, Krisenchat, "Impf-O-Mat", "Post-Coron-A-Mat", #hackthevirus.
- *Greece*: Coordination Center for Refugees and Migrants, [The Other Human](#), El Chef, Migrant Shelter, We Stay Active, Coordination COVID-19: Solidarity of Thessaloniki, Social Space Oikopolis, Perivolarides, Team of Social Solidarity of Xanthi, Sunday Kitchen of Solidarity, Social Shelter of migrants in Xanthi, Nobody Alone, Social Medical Facility and Pharmacy of Chania, Moria Corona Awareness Team.
- *Italy*: Binario95, La Spesa Sospesa, Sparwasser - Nonna Roma, EX OPG squat - The Red Phone, Laboratorio Salute Popolare of Bologna.
- *Portugal*: Vizinho Amigo, Comvidas, Caixa Solidária.
- *Spain*: volunteers sent letters of solidarity to people suffering from isolation and loneliness⁶⁷, several platforms were created to connect people offering support with those requesting it⁶⁸,

⁶⁷ <https://www.madridiario.es/cartas-para-paliarsolidad-enfermos-coronavirus>.

⁶⁸ <https://www.hacesfalta.org/oportunidades/iniciativas/buscador/>.

telephone support lines were introduced⁶⁹, or virtual meeting spaces were created for the exchange of actors from different sectors⁷⁰. The Rey Juan Carlos University created an initiative to help elderly people take out the rubbish during the state of alarm in Madrid⁷¹.

- Sweden: activities initiated by individual citizens during the pandemic aimed at the local community or even at a single neighbourhood (help with shopping, exchange of domestic services, informal FAQs on COVID-19, exchange of experiences from infection).
- Wales: Ordinary people got involved in pandemic practices in several ways. many helped out locally by making and distributing food parcels such as Street Champions.

A more comprehensive collection of participatory practices identified in the target countries will be presented in connection with the forthcoming deliverable D8.5, “Guidance and recommendations to enhance the citizen response summary report”.

⁶⁹ <https://www.idea-alzira.com/becamos>.

⁷⁰ <https://diarioresponsable.com/noticias/29234-fundacion-hazloposible-continua-apoyando-la-labor-solidaria-gracias-a-forgood-es>.

⁷¹ <https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/El-Ayuntamiento/Todas-las-noticias/Madrid-se-suma-a-YoTeAyudoConLaBasura-jovenes-dispuestos-a-bajar-la-basura-a-quien-lo-necesite/?vgnnextfmt=default&vgnextoid=8c0eea44a7b21710VgnVCM2000001f4a900aRCRD&vgnnextchannel=e40362215c483510VgnVCM2000001f4a900aRCRD>.

Conclusion

In all pandemic phases, COVID-19 is observed to have exacerbated existing vulnerabilities in all COVINFORM countries. These vulnerabilities relate to gender stereotypes, financial vulnerabilities, structural challenges tied to migration backgrounds, language barriers, social exclusion, discrimination, chronic health issues, and mental health disorders, among others. In order to mitigate the exacerbation of vulnerabilities, CSOs in COVINFORM target countries engaged in a wide range of activities (mentioned in the preceding chapters), often in cooperation with citizen initiatives and governmental organisations. Although outcomes varied highly site by site, a general pattern is that the higher the degree of cooperation between actors, the more successful the measures taken. Another general pattern is that initiatives that proactively involved local-level stakeholders with ties to specific vulnerable populations were able to increase their influence within those populations. These and other key findings will be analysed with reference to the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model (WP2) and the social-ecological systems framework (SESF; WP3) in the forthcoming deliverable D6.8 “Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts – Update M36”.

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Annex 1

D6.7 standardised reporting template

Each country report for WP6, D6.7 should **not exceed 3-4 pages**.

Baseline conditions in the sub-national research site prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

[Here, feel free to summarise the following sections of your D6.3 contribution: General description of the research site; Vulnerability in the research site; CSOs in the research site. You can supplement these if desired]

Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 and T2)

T1 = from the beginning of the pandemic until vaccination began to have an effect on policy

T2 = starting when vaccination began to have an effect on policy, until now

- 1. How did CSOs contribute to crisis management in the research site during the period T1 (What happened when the pandemic hit? How did CSOs react? Did they cooperate with, or work independently from, governmental institutions/services? How were decisions made?)**

[Here, you can summarise the D6.3 contribution section “COVID-19 impact timeline: Time period 1”. You can supplement it if desired]

- 2. How did CSO responses change between T1 and T2, and what factors may have driven those changes?**

[Here, you can summarise the D6.3 contribution section “COVID-19 impact timeline: Time period 2 & time period 3”]

- 3. What are some examples of participatory practices that emerged in the research site, i.e., practices that involved “everyday people” in an active way?**

[Here, you can summarise your contribution to D6.5]

- 4. What were the local impacts of governmental responses in the research site? Did unintended impacts occur? Were there gaps in governmental responses, and did CSOs and/or participatory practices fill these gaps?**

[Here, please scan through your contributions to D6.3 and D6.5 to find any info that could contribute to this topic]

Conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted measures in crisis management

- 5. What vulnerable groups do the interviewees' CSOs work with? What about other CSOs in the research site? Did CSO target groups change between T1 and T2?**

[You should be able to find this in your contribution to D6.3]

- 6. In the view of interviewees, did the pandemic a) change existing vulnerabilities, and/or b) cause new vulnerabilities among CSOs' target groups? Did CSOs take action to address these changes? *[e.g., lockdown affected domestic violence victims, people living in overcrowded conditions, chronically ill people, ageing people living alone, etc.]***

[You may find something on this in your contribution to D6.3; we recognise not everyone will be able to answer these questions]

Annex 2

The Ostrom social-ecological systems framework (SESF) model consists of five sub systems, which we have operationalised as follows:

Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to in a country and to manage a (health) crisis

Governance Systems (GS) – describes the basic structure of how a country is governed in relation to a (health) crisis

Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis management in a country

Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the governmental crisis response

Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. In this concrete case it mostly describes measures taken to manage the health crisis (e.g., lockdowns, etc.).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

D6.7

Goal of Deliverable:

Answer RQs by providing country profiles based on desk-based research of Tx.1 and Tx.5, as well the expert interviews using the SES Framework for T0, T1, and T2.

AUSTRIA

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
Information awareness raising, provision of social inclusion services for marginalised communities.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)
Essential item distribution, awareness raising services.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
CSOs are observed to cooperate with Municipal governmental organisations in terms of awareness raising and engage with other CSOs, however in comparison to other phases, this interaction was limited. CSOs were mostly invested in assisting their target groups while there is a lack of data in relation to the interaction percentage with the general public.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)
Bottom-up grassroots initiatives at this phase were observed to organise food banks among relevant initiatives of solidarity.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
- Vienna is not just the capital of Austria, but a city which is a state on its own.
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
- The city's achievements are built and influenced on the idea of a welfare state, which also influenced the handling of the current crisis, with the main decision makers being the Viennese mayor and Gesundheitstadtrat (Health Councillor who is the highest bureaucrat in the resort of health for the City of Vienna).
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
- Pluralistic socio-cultural non-governmental organisations
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
- "Active in women's support organisation, and operating city-wide, that particularly focuses on migrant women of Muslim background, providing support on a range of issues, including human rights (e.g., anti-people-smuggling/abduction) and domestic issues (e.g., marriage and divorce counselling and anti-forced-marriage work), also providing German classes to migrant women of Muslim background."
- "A transnational aid organisation that is active in many areas of social support in Austria and many other countries, working in as an advisor for people who experience long-term or short-time financial hardship and stress, as well as other issues."
- "The CSO is active in many areas of social support, and strongly involved in the national COVID-19 response, working in a management position overseeing the organisation's services for houseless/homeless people and refugees."

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
General vulnerable groups in diverse and multiple ways, mostly women exposed to stereotypes based on gendered identity as Muslim migrant women.
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Muslim migrant women and people with of financial vulnerabilities.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Whereas other states already passed age prioritizations in their vaccination strategy, the city-state of Vienna continued to implement them also due to its much bigger population size compared to other states. Because of this, everyone over 41 years and between 12-30 years became eligible for a vaccination. Vienna intensified its testing strategy at the beginning of the winter season 2020, by offering multiple testing options that also changed over the course of time, depending on the needs of its citizens. In principle, there were three testing categories: one for people without symptoms, one for people with symptoms, and one for close contacts, as well as returning travelers.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

In the city of Vienna, the first responders during the pandemic were in a vulnerable position, since in the beginning of the pandemic, they often did not have enough masks and home office was impossible for their employees, affecting their services.

- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

During the early phase of the pandemic, Vienna's citizens were actively helping vulnerable people or older residents in their neighborhood, for example with errands or shopping, thus, despite the challenges of the situation, the voluntary initiatives ensured the support of people in need throughout the pandemic.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

There was difficulty working with migrant women that did not know German and could not use modern technology, that were necessary tools during the lockdowns. Also, the biggest issue were the closure of many services as well as the increased barriers to reach government agencies. The uncertainty of the pandemic was combined with bureaucratic uncertainties, particularly for people who needed government support for the first time in their lives.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

The ability of CSOs to organise their own rules efficiently in a way that they were always able to stay open during the phases where face-to-face lessons were possible; even if individuals caught corona, they never had clusters. However, the biggest challenge was to organise lessons via WhatsApp; because there was no preparation during the first lockdown, since the ministry of education requested virtual lessons and this switch was very challenging (also regarding the timekeeping and how to organise language courses virtually).

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

The city of Vienna which is a state on its own, has implemented COVID-19 measures and tactics which deviated from the national recommendations and strategies to combat the virus. On multiple occasions, Vienna as a state extended its lockdown or implemented lockdowns where other states decided against one.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

The CSO ecosystem did not radically change. CSO regardless of size, reported that their workloads increased significantly. This is partially because the volume of service requests increased. However, the interconnection between CSOs, in the research sites across Vienna, did not go into detail

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

Muslim migrant women experienced financial vulnerabilities and other structural issues attached to their migrant status, because of their lack of German, that often led to social exclusion and difficulties managing everyday life with the Austrian bureaucracy.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Many of the migrant women had troubles progressing in their learnings, while many, particularly the ones that arrived as refugees, suffered from being homesick."

COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The general population was impacted severely, particularly from a financial and psychological perspective.

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Currently Vienna focuses on financial support initiatives established by the Wirtschaftsagentur Wien (Vienna Business Agency) which is a fund of the city, that launched multiple initiatives to mitigate the negative economic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. These initiatives mainly focus on the recovery phase of the pandemic and aim to support, small and medium businesses, creative industries, innovation and technology and many more.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

According to an interviewee, the pandemic will have a lasting impact, specifically, in resulting in a permanent "state of emergency" that will negatively impact the everyday lives of citizens, thus making living together with others a bit more difficult.

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

It is notable that despite the challenges of the situation, both CSOs and voluntary initiatives ensured to support people in need throughout the pandemic.

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

Research findings indicate that the CSOs had to still minimise the number of clients they could cater too due to social distancing rules.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
- No radical changes in municipality were identified.
- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Gradual disengagement from strict measures.

- Vaccination priority rules
- Vulnerable groups were prioritised.
- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
 - Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Ibid.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

It was reported that due to the switch to WhatsApp, the migrant women tried out functions such as sending voice messages, for example, one woman recorded herself reading and sent it to the interviewee, which means that these little learning successes made her appreciate her job. However, there were real gaps in the delivery of care for some old people, since their carers were not allowed to enter the country anymore and these people were often left alone with the care they needed.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
- Most visible, were the economic vulnerabilities in all of Vienna.
- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Presently there are big housing developments that got realised using the space of an old train station, with these developments particularly catering young middle to upper-middle class families.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
- Gradual disengagement from measures by the municipal authorities had an impact to the general public who could slowly return to their daily lives.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

BELGIUM

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
Sensi Ambassadors were recruited by the City of Antwerp to better engage with marginalised societies. At later phases they would receive training about COVID-19, distribute multilingual communication materials, and act as a trusted source of information for their network, as they have done prior to COVID-19.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)
Pre-existing resource systems and Units include socio-cultural organizations, religious institutions (i.e. Mosques) who would offer spiritual guidance and conduct cultural initiatives such as information awareness activities.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
CSOs supported Municipal governmental organizations in awareness raising initiatives.. The beneficiaries were other CSOs, target groups (particularly Sub-Saharan African communities) and the general population, who received easy to read content and audio messages in a variety of languages. CSOs actively combated misinformation.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)
Socio-cultural organizations, religious institutions and key community figures launched initiatives to promote awareness raising on social inclusion of marginalised societies and food distribution. At later phases they would engage in COVID-19 measure dissemination initiatives and combating misinformation.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
- Municipalities in Antwerp (Antwerp, Berchem, Berendrecht-Zandvliet-Lillo, Borgerhout, Deurne, Ekeren, Hoboken, Merksem).
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
- The municipality implemented policies and practices (non-pharmaceutical interventions) that contained the spread of the virus and measures to mitigate the negative health and socio-economic impact.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
- Pluralistic socio-cultural non-governmental organisations
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
- "The organization works on various different projects, with the common scope of promoting participatory processes and active dialogue, e.g. between local government and the city, or between different groups in society."
- "The sociocultural meeting house that provides a space for people to meet, create, rehearse, teach and reflect" in the local area
- "The NGO runs a wide variety of activities within this scope, ranging from preventative outreach work to day care for houseless/homeless people as well as citizens with dependence problems on illegal substances"

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
Ethnic minorities such as sub-Saharan communities, sex workers, migrants, citizens living in poverty, healthcare workers, elderly, homeless and substance addicted citizens .
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Ibid.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Provision of technological equipment to school children in order to make remote learning feasible. Distribution of multilingual material, particularly to marginalized groups. The city of Antwerp would employ Sensi Ambassadors.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

Implemented policies and practices, changed the modus operandi of CSOs. Many switched to a digital way of working. Besides their daily workload, CSOs would also raise awareness in relation to COVID-19 policies and guidelines. This modus operandi persisted until the last phase with the gradual lifting of restrictions. Services offered by CSOs were health and social service provision as well as risk communication and promotion of the vaccination campaign. , the volunteer initiative 'Antwerp helps' (provision of assistance in groceries and medication for people in need), Zipster's COVID coaches (Ibid and information provision/guidance), 'Coronababbels' (Psychological support), and specific initiatives in Borgerhout.

- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

Food distribution, information dissemination and psychological support (i.e. telephone helplines), combating misinformation.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

CSOs continue to support Municipal governmental organizations by disseminating official information in relation to COVID-19. Moreover, CSOs engaged in several initiatives such as food distribution, information, counselling and psychological support towards both marginalized groups and the general population, provided clear information in multiple languages to combat misinformation.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

Interviewees indicate that the abrupt switch of their modus operandi to a virtual environment introduced practical and technical challenges. Moreover, due to COVID-19 restrictions, CSOs were unable to provide adequate support to homeless citizens and help was scaled down or halted in comparison with the pre-pandemic phase. Due to the rapidly changing governmental policies and practices, CSOs were also encouraged to constantly adjust their approaches and responses.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

COVID-19 rules and guidelines experienced a constant change, which made the work of CSOs more challenging.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

The CSO ecosystem did not radically change. CSOs broadened their working definitions (i.e. verhoogde tegemoetkoming) to define vulnerability, based on the new vulnerabilities that emerged from COVID-19, which made them more encompassing.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

Homeless/Houseless citizens' vulnerability was magnified and more cases emerged.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

According to one interviewee "vulnerability is a sum of vulnerable factors: housing, finances, health, age, network, and of course the neighbourhood where you live. The more vulnerable factors, the more likely you are to be hit harder." Homeless citizens is a prime example, as CSOs could not help as much as they could before COVID-19 due to physical distance restrictions.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The general population was impacted severely, particularly from a psychological perspective.

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)
Walk in vaccination busses were rolled out by the municipal governmental organizations with the cooperation of CSOs and volunteers, in order to increase vaccination rates. Get up Wallonia! Was also rolled out, an online crowdsourcing initiative which requested citizens to provide their recommendations in order to formulate a COVID-19 recovery strategy. The Molenbeek Solidarity Platform was an initiative by the City and mayor of Molenbeek meant to connect volunteers and organize them in assisting vulnerable and citizens in need with service and product provision.
- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)
The sociocultural meeting house 't Werkhuys launched a neighborhood restaurant where people could enjoy a full take-away meal for three euros to actively combat food insecurity.
- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)
Volunteers actively assisted with the walk-in vaccination busses initiative. A residents' initiative is Antwerpen helpt in Belgium, which was initiated by a network of self-organised groups, but also supported by the City of Antwerp

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
CSOs interacted through established partnerships with Municipal governmental organizations, as evidently seen in the Vaccibuses initiative. CSOs also solidified their network with other local CSOs and continued to provide their services and assistance to both their target groups and the general population in need. Several grassroots initiatives can be observed. Antwerpen helpt is a prime example.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)
The 't Werkhuys team noticed that the COVID-19 pandemic worsened the food insecurity faced by many households in the district, and prioritised the scale-up of providing affordable community meals. They received additional funding for this during the pandemic, and the initiative was such a success that they have now been awarded longer-time financing to continue it.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
No radical changes can be identified.
- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)
Gradual disengagement from strict measures.
- Vaccination priority rules
Vulnerable groups were prioritised.
- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
No radical changes can be identified.
- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)
Ibid.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
The spectrum of vulnerability was broadened at the first and second phase of COVID-19. This included citizens with pre-existing and contemporary vulnerabilities that related to COVID-19, combining factors such as: housing conditions, socio-economic, health and cultural factors.
- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
No radical changes can be identified with the exception of the gradual disengagement from measures which allowed CSOs to slowly regain their pre-COVID-19 working modus operandi.
- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
Gradual disengagement from measures had a similar impact to the general public who could slowly return to their daily lives.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

ENGLAND

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
- Digital engagement of social media.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)

According to interviewees that were involved: in projects for a local health authorities, as officers with BAME communities, as officers in children's rights from different ethnic groups agencies, as community engagement officer working with many minority communities. The above worked in advisory roles, as community leaders and advocates, and decision-maker roles

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

The city's Council support for deprived communities had initially been organised around the themes of employability, health, and education, but in 2018, this changed to mostly employability, therefore leaving a gap regarding the health theme two years before the outbreak of the pandemic. CSOs were sharing knowledge and practices, at least on an occasional basis.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)

In the city of Birmingham the main response at the beginning of the pandemic was the collaboration and the formation of response groups, with their objective being the exchange of information and community support.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
- Birmingham, is a geographic community within the West Midlands, a county in England. In 2018, it was estimated that 1,141,400 people live in Birmingham.
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
- To meet the requirements of national guidelines, "The Local Covid Outbreak Engagement Board" was established as sub-committee of the "Birmingham Health and Wellbeing Board", with the purpose "to provide political ownership and public-facing engagement and communication for outbreak response to Covid19 in Birmingham". Following its first meeting on 24 June 2020, the Board has met on a monthly basis.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
- Pluralistic socio-cultural non-governmental organisations
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
- "Active with BAME communities with the local municipal council, also contributing in a decision-maker role to an engagement project for a local health authority
- "A worker in an engagement officer for a children's rights agency, focusing on building relationships with various ethnic groups.
- A worker in a community engagement office, working directly with many minority communities and a BAME community leader and advocate, and contributed to a Community Cohesion Plan that was aimed at diminishing social tensions and improving cooperation mostly in deprived areas.
- A policy researcher at a women's labour organisation, that has contributed to several reports about the pandemic and gender issues.

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
Mostly minorities and ethnic vulnerable groups in diverse and multiple ways.
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
BAME communities, children.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The 2021 draft of the “Birmingham City Council COVID-19 Local Outbreak Management Plan” highlighted seven key populations that have been identified as high risk: “Healthcare Settings, Workplaces and Public Places, Education settings Social Care settings, Justice settings, Vulnerable and marginalized individuals, and communities Non healthcare public sector workers, working with citizens at high risk of harboring COVID.

Under instructions from the UK Government’s Department of Health and Social Care, Birmingham’s local ethnic groups were at the heart of breaking the chains of transmission. A number of different methods to engage with communities, included: Launching a “COVID-19 Community Champions” initiative. Radio advertising in different languages to promote the NHS app and recruit COVID Champions. Targeting communications to “Community Centres, GP surgeries, high risk wards, faith settings, schools, councilors, and BCC staff”. Community and Faith meetings – between 1 September 2020 and 22 January 2021.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees’ CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

According to interviewees their scope was expanded to businesses to improve flexible working.

- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

During the early phase of the pandemic, in Birmingham there were groups providing help via the COVID-19 Mutual Aid UK network, examples include the Birmingham Mutual Aid and COVID-19 Community Response Group, with the main priority of this group being the support of the elderly, isolated, and immunocompromised when self-isolating. Another example is the COVID-19 Mutual Aid Harborne B17 group, which brings separate streets and small areas together to look out for and support one another. A further example is that of the Acocks Green Together: COVID-19 Community Support Volunteers group, which explicitly supports those that live and/or work in the Acocks Green Ward, an electoral ward in south-east Birmingham.

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

Two interviewees working in CSO’s indicated that the knock-on effects of the pandemic first noticed in the initial phase of the disease worsened, with the former indicating that in summer 2020, the news broke that BAME people suffered more disproportionately, and were thus seen as more vulnerable than white populations.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees’ assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

All interviewees indicated that COVID-19 had aggravated certain existing (intersectional) inequalities and power disparities, for example, interviewee 1 returned attention to the issue of discrimination, mentioning how incidents of racist abuse were seen to increase, while interviewee 4 argued that the pandemic increased the inequities between men and women regarding their work progression and career prospects. On the other hand all interviewees indicated that COVID-19 had increased consciousness of the critical importance of caring human relationships in modern society, as well as of the diversity and complexity of such relationships. BVSC, the centre for voluntary action, worked with the Birmingham City Council to establish the “C19 Support Brum partnership”, which involved drawing on “existing local neighborhood structures, voluntary groups, and local elected members” to ensure that there was access to support, help and advice across the city. Also local mutual aid groups in Birmingham that were listed on the BVSC website included the “Selly Oak Community Response to Covid-19”²⁴¹ and “Birmingham Community Solidarity: Coronavirus Response”.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Birmingham in line with the requirements set at the national Government level, published the “Birmingham Covid-19 Local Outbreak Control Plan, Version 2.0” on 30th of June 2020. The objectives of the Plan included, but were not limited to, reducing the spread of infection and saving lives in Birmingham, and giving “the public confidence that the city is able to respond appropriately to outbreaks of COVID-19 in order to minimise anxiety.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

The CSO ecosystem did not radically change. However CSO regardless of size, reported that they had to adapt to new circumstances.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees’ CSOs (if relevant)

No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

BAME people suffered more disproportionately.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee’s CSO works with (from D6.3)

As restrictions became more severe, economic and social impacts in the GRT community did as well.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The general population was impacted severely, particularly from a financial perspective, as well as the education of young people.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The local COVID Outbreak Engagement Board of Birmingham, was created to support public engagement, with the Members of the public being able to submit questions to the board via the Birmingham City Council website.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

An interviewee during the phasing out restrictions, focused on vaccinations in the GRT community, indicating that as people continued to get sick and die, more people in these communities have felt the need to be vaccinated, with mobile vaccination units being organised to help fill this need directly at camp sites.

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

Interviewees cautioned that as the risk of disease itself recedes, the threat to the communities is now the narrowness and "temporary" status of the provisions made during the earlier stages of the pandemic.

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

An interviewee explicitly addressed the role of CSOs in supplementing governmental risk communication and vaccine campaigns, stating that it became apparent that adequate information wasn't available in all necessary languages.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
- No radical changes in municipality were identified.
- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Gradual disengagement from strict measures.

- Vaccination priority rules
- Vulnerable groups were prioritised.
- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
 - Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Ibid.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

An interviewee gave a detailed analysis of the potential impacts of online work, arguing that new arrangements can meaningfully benefit some vulnerable groups, but that thought must be given to unintended consequences and trade-offs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
- Most visible, were the social vulnerabilities in all of Birmingham.
- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

There was severe impact that the COVID-19 and the lockdown measures have had on the health and wellbeing of the diverse communities of Birmingham.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
- The general population was impacted severely, particularly from a financial perspective, as well as the education of young people.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

GERMANY

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
Municipal organisations would offer awareness raising services and in certain cases distribution of essential need items to beneficiaries.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)
In the city of Mannheim within a short timeframe, living conditions for their target groups would become significantly more difficult and unstable. Municipal services prior to COVID-19 were already subject to barriers became near-impossible to access: e.g., employment services for the precarious; immigration services for refugees; etc, as a result, pressure increased on CSOs (and "all-purpose" municipal services) to fill these gaps. With regard to those conditions, in the research sites more generally: most interviewees testified primarily to effects upon their own target groups.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
In the city of Mannheim, the depth and breadth of cooperation and networking among local civil society groups and the local public sector, had a very positive dimension.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)
It is notable that many participatory initiatives - whether induced by governmental actors or grassroots campaigning - would take place on a face-to-face basis, while in the later phases they would be conducted partly or entirely online throughout the COVID-19 crisis.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
- Berlin is not just the capital of Germany, but also a federal state.
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
- There is a main municipal administration composed of ten senate administrations, which form the supreme state authorities. Each senate administration is headed by a senator, who also serves as minister. The tasks of the senate administrations are to decide on fundamental matters, to plan and control the development of the city, and to supervise state-owned institutions under public law.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
- Pluralistic socio-cultural non-governmental organisations
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
- "Active in many areas of social and health service provision; since 2015, the organization has been working primarily with refugees, now including many Ukrainians, otherwise many from Syria, the Balkans, Iraq, Afghanistan, Africa, and in essence all countries of the world."
- "A neighbourhood management association (Quartiersmanagement) in one of the target neighbourhoods of Mannheim, is charged with comprehensive tasks, including networking in the district, individual case assistance and counselling, and image enhancement for the district."
- "The CSO is providing counselling and assistance to women who have experienced or are still experiencing domestic and sexual violence, also managing multiple shelters for women and children, serving about 400-500 clients a year, including about 200 post-police contacts; these have doubled in the Corona period"

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
Ethnic minorities such as migrant communities, sex workers, irregular migrants, citizens living in poverty, healthcare workers, elderly, homeless and substance addicted citizens .
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Ibid.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)
A vaccination pilot by the Berlin municipal services was offered, via notices on the front doors and through social and educational institutions, informing residents about the offer at short notice. Also, residents' registration addresses alone were accepted as valid vaccination authorizations, with the Moderna and Johnson & Johnson vaccines being utilized. Later the vaccination campaign started in socially disadvantaged districts.
- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)
In the city of Mannheim, some organisations were able to resume nearly all of their conventional services (albeit sometimes digitally), while some were not. The size and portfolio of each organisation appears to have partially determined the impact of lockdowns on their ability to offer services. Eventually, CSOs of all sizes moved forward with digitalisation of those services that could be digitalised.
- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)
In some Berlin communities, citizens were setting up online groups to offer support for vulnerable persons, but also to provide advice, information, or guidance on how to get through the pandemic.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
It was agreed that the sudden total or partial closure of governmental offices and reduction in social services was "catastrophic" for both the CSOs and their target groups. During the lockdown periods, several key social services (such as the Youth Welfare Office) offered no opportunities for face-to-face contact and very limited opportunities for contact by telephone, meaning that only the digitally literate could maintain the needed access.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)
Most interviewees identified increased the organisational efficiency via digitalisation; spontaneous displays of solidarity and mutual aid among local residents; the development of new services and initiatives; and a new awareness of social issues, specifically, the vulnerabilities facing their CSOs' target groups, as positive outcomes of the pandemic. However, all interviewees criticised governmental services, to a greater or lesser extent, for a lack of responsiveness and accessibility; while some interviewees assessed their performance as "catastrophic".

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
No radical changes in municipality were identified.
- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)
Public health measures taken by Berlin municipal authorities have followed the evolution of the different waves of the pandemic. During the first quarter of 2020, the attention was put on restrictive lockdown measures to prevent the spread of the virus.
- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
The CSO ecosystem did not radically change. CSO regardless of size, reported that their workloads increased significantly. This is partially because the volume of service requests increased.
- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)
No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
It was indicated the potentially lasting psychosocial changes among their target groups, colleagues, and/or society at large, which include: lingering fear; exhaustion/burnout; the loss of a common, shared truth and a retreat into 'filter bubbles'; changing communication strategies and a reduction in meaningful discourse; and an overall drop in social cohesion and sociality.
- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
According to one interviewee "Now the war and the Ukraine crisis are coming and ruining what might have been possible."
COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
The general population was impacted severely, particularly from a psychological perspective.

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The Berlin authorities by the second part of the second quarter of 2021 introduces multiple removals of the restrictions due to the decreasing of the number of infections and the advancing of the vaccination campaign. Since the 21st of May it was possible to dine outdoor, and to organise cultural, recreational and entertainment events outdoor, new quarantine rules were introduced and applied all over Germany since May the 14th, while since mid-June mask obligation was not only mandatory on specified streets and squares as long as the minimum distance of 1.5 m. could be maintained, reopening of amusement venues and facilities with the obligation to wear FFP2-masks, and reopening of dance parties with up to 250 people.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

CSOs took advantage of the loosening restrictions, in order to re-offer services as soon as possible. Several interviewees' early designation as "system-relevant workers" meant that they had access to resources, such as testing, PPE, and priority vaccines, that helped speed this process.

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

It is notable that many participatory initiatives grassroots campaigning - have taken place partly or entirely online throughout the COVID-19 crisis, even when they originated in the municipality of Mannheim.

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

Research findings indicate that the majority of local participatory practices aimed at supporting specific societal groups, like the most vulnerable as they may rely on residents and local institutions on and offline for daily needs. Despite their short-term to mid-term approach, in particular online platforms are proven sustainable in terms of easy re-launch.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
- No radical changes in municipality were identified.
- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Gradual disengagement from strict measures.

- Vaccination priority rules
- Vulnerable groups were prioritised.
- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
- No radical changes can be identified.
- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Ibid.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

All interviewees reported that the pandemic has forced some positive changes, such as: increased digital competence; new training opportunities; and increased efficiency with regard to the delivery of some services. However, again all interviewees reported that challenges, such as high workloads, disconnect within the staff and between staff and clients, were persistent. Specifically, smaller organisations reported that not all services could be re-introduced, and that certain health-protective measures have remained in place, including some with adverse effects on operations.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
- The spectrum of vulnerability was broadened at the first and second phase of COVID-19. However, the general population was impacted severely, from a psychological perspective.

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3) indicated potentially lasting psychosocial changes among their target groups.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
- Gradual disengagement from measures by the municipal authorities had an impact to the general public who could slowly return to their daily lives.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

GREECE

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
Awareness raising initiatives and food distribution to socio-economically vulnerable.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)
Provision of healthcare services and counselling, as well as risk communication.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
CSOs actively cooperated with the municipality of Athens. For instance, the Hellenic Liver Patients Association "Prometheus", the Greek Association of People Living with HIV "Positive Voice" with funding from the Partnership for Healthy Cities managed to provide food, water, gloves, masks, antiseptic liquid, and information about transmittable diseases to those affected by homelessness, people who inject drugs, sex workers and migrants, creating in parallel temporary housing for homeless and specialised support drug center.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)
Grassroots initiatives that were carried out in Athens ensured the provision of health services, food, clothing, counselling etc. These acts of solidarity would not be a newfound phenomenon, as several similar initiatives were conducted the past decade due to the financial crisis.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
Athens is the capital and the biggest city of Greece. The Municipality of Athens is the country's economic, educational, and cultural centre and is home to approximately 664,046 people⁸². The Municipality is divided in seven districts, mainly for administrative purposes, one of which, the district of Kipseli, "is the world's second most densely populated urban area"⁸³. In terms of population, Athens is a rather homogenous community. The majority of the residents in Athens are Greek-Orthodox Christians with the exemption of some recognized ethno-religious minorities in the city, such as the Jewish, Muslim, Armenian, Romani and Pomaki.
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
The municipality implemented policies and practices (non-pharmaceutical interventions) that contained the spread of the virus and measures to mitigate the negative health and socio-economic impact as well as awareness raising.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
Segregated communities of individuals that present cultural, social-economic, and health vulnerabilities.
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
Metropolitan religious organisation, accommodation/shelter facilities, CSOs dedicated to abused children, Roma, homeless, drug addicts etc.

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
Ethnic minorities, migrants, citizens living in poverty, healthcare workers, elderly, homeless and substance addicted citizens .
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Ibid.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Athens Municipality installed a static spot for COVID-19 rapid tests. EODY (National Public Health Organization) offered free rapid COVID-19 tests to citizens, on Syntagma square right outside of the subway station. Thus, people could easily get tested for free every-day from 9:00h to 20:00h. The city of Athens conducted regular updates on COVID-19 on the municipality's website, with regular media communication towards the public as well as with specific financial aid to businesses that have been impacted by the pandemic. The Municipality of Athens has also adopted the "Help at Home Plus" program. This initiative is mainly intended for individuals with health related issues as well as the older population, where social workers, medical staff and the program's assistants, provide counseling around the COVID-19 pandemic and the imposed measures, medical care, as well as the delivery of basic goods such as medicines and groceries.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

The interviewees' CSOs and those in their networks contributed to the overall response by providing healthcare and counselling services for vulnerable citizens (disabled, elderly, children, no or low income citizens), as well as distributing health care products (masks, disinfectant sprays) with the assistance of doctors and nurses. Interviewees believed that CSOs helped fill gaps in the Greek governmental response, particularly for socially excluded citizens.

- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

Food distribution, daily live activities assistance provision, information dissemination and psychological support, combating misinformation.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

In cooperation with the European Anti-Violence Network and the General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality, CSOs created facilities to accommodate victims of domestic abuse. In cooperation with psychological health professionals, CSOs operated a phone helpline for citizens and orchestrated awareness campaigns for vulnerable groups. Several CSOs developed communications and outreach materials targeting the psychological impact of COVID-19, coping mechanisms, and discussions about welfare, educational and health services. The main recipients of these campaigns were citizens living in isolated geographical parts of the community and other vulnerable citizens such as Roma, houseless/homeless citizens, refugees and other migrants. Some CSOs, in cooperation with governmental ministries, took the utilization of digital communication a step further and developed communication tools for their beneficiaries. Specifically, a 24/7 chatting tool was developed for victims of domestic abuse – a phenomenon which increased during periods of social isolation under COVID-19.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)
- hospital visitation protocols were not appropriately amended during COVID-19; as a result, many hospitalized citizens could not be visited by relatives, resulting in a negative psychological impact. Wearing a mask has prevented unnecessary deaths, not only from COVID-19, but also from typical annual flus

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)
COVID-19 rules and guidelines experienced a constant change, which made the work of CSOs more challenging.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

The CSO ecosystem did not radically change, however, the modus operandi constantly shifted and proved to be a challenge to how CSOs operated with all restrictions, which overall reduced their effectiveness as CSOs suggested that on-site contact with their target groups is essential.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
Pre-existing vulnerabilities, particularly socio-economically challenged areas, were increased.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Due to the implemented measures, particularly during this phase, CSOs were not able to work on-site with their target groups in some cases, thus, responses may have not been as effective as intended.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The general population was impacted severely, which is evident by the socio-economic and psychological impact.

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Municipal governmental organisations continued to provide information in relation to personal hygiene and protection measures, guidelines, recommendations, vaccines and provided services that ensured the distribution of essential needs items such as food and clothes.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

Multiple CSOs launched initiatives regarding awareness and information raising, food and healthcare services provision etc. Online mutual aid platforms were among the most visible of participatory practices in Greece. Often, platforms were set up by established civil society organisations. Diotima, for instance, a well-known community organization promoting gender equality and offering psychosocial counselling to victims of gender abuse, was highly active during the pandemic, establishing a Facebook Help Desk to connect and support victims, through which information could be found and assistance could be requested in a variety of languages. Agkalia, another community organization dedicated to protecting deprived mothers and their children, has established online mutual assistance services for vulnerable residents, including psychosocial support for both mothers and children. Both Diotima and Agkalia provided tailored health and general information to their target groups. Furthermore, in addition to providing direct support, both organisations encouraged peer-to-peer connections between their clients to facilitate mutual aid Agkalia. Other organisations that provided assistance through online platforms during the pandemic include AMKE Fainareti, which provides remote psychosocial counselling to groups as diverse as young parents and healthcare professionals and SynAthina, which focuses on connecting users to CSOs based on their needs.

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

The online platforms active in Greece are not initiated solely by existing CSOs, but also by self-organised groups of residents. An example is Initiative “Ψ”, the Initiative for a Diverse Movement for Mental Health, a citizen-led Facebook-based mutual aid group. An Athens-based initiative that utilised both face-to-face and online activities was Kropotkin-19, organized by member of the left-wing/anti-authoritarian movement in the Exarcheia neighbourhood of Athens, who operate collective kitchens (i.e. OneLoveKitchen), self-organized schools, refugee solidarity collectives, “social clinics”, and other social solidarity measures

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

CSOs interacted in the municipal government, other CSOs, their target groups and the general population intensively during this phase as well, in initiatives such as food distribution, health services and counselling, risk communication and vaccination campaign.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

Lockdowns forced many businesses to close. This has resulted in serious social and economic consequences. Another important effect is the psychological impact of loneliness and isolation. CSO representatives indicated that in response to this effect, they have encouraged citizens to communicate more and demonstrate solidarity with their fellow community members. CSO representatives observed that many members of the general public avoided overcrowding, adhered to social distancing, and continued wearing masks even when lockdowns ended. Some suggested that the public may not consider the relaxation of restrictions as a constructive step. However, interviewees also noted that the pandemic offered an opportunity to implement new, improved social and institutional policies and practices in a variety of sectors, such as public administration, education, employment and the economy, particularly highlighting the importance of new technology in facilitating distance working and studying.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No radical changes can be identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Gradual disengagement from COVID-19 measures.

- Vaccination priority rules

Vulnerable groups were prioritised.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

No radical changes can be identified, however CSOs became more encompassing.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Ibid.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

The spectrum of vulnerability was broadened, similarly to other countries, and included among other vulnerable groups, children, the elderly, members of marginalised and deprived groups, victims of domestic abuse etc.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

CSOs returned to the pre-covid-19 modus operandi which allows CSOs to reach their target groups easier.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

Gradual disengagement allowed the general public to slowly return to their daily lives.

ITALY

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)

Health and social governmental services are managed under the administration of the Latium region but in a rather centralized way as interviewees emphasized. The Latium region also stands out for a marked level of specialization in the information and communication technology services sector, as well as a rate of digital technology adoption by businesses

What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)

The CSOs represented by the interviewees, and CSOs in their professional networks, provide multiple services, such as reintegration and rehabilitation, medical services, protection from human rights violations, legal procedures for asylum seekers and refugees in reception centres, and counselling in reception centres.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

Interviewees observed that cooperation increased between governmental authorities and CSOs was rather high. For instance, it was observed that synergies between public and civil society were substantially important in efforts to serve and manage houseless/homeless people, a quite challenging activity. Public-private synergies were identified as key dimensions in responses targeted toward vulnerable populations, and it was acknowledged that they should be continued.

Outcomes (O)

Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)

The CSO Italian Alliance for Sustainable Development (ASviS) was established on 2016 with primary goal to enhance awareness about the 2030 UN Agenda for Sustainable Development, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To date, the CSO has united approximately 270 member organisations among the most crucial civil society institutions and networks. In response to the pandemic, especially during the peak of the crisis, the CSO established the AlleanzaAgisce, a solidarity initiative gathering, disseminating, and providing instant access to projects conducted by affiliates of ASviS's network throughout Italy

Governance Systems (GS)

What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)

Local municipalities are governed by popularly elected municipal councils, municipal committees and the mayor. The regional government is comprised by the Regional council which has constitutionally limited legislative powers, the regional committee with executive power and the president of the regional committee. Regions have some control over the activity of the municipalities

What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)

Measures in response to the COVID-19 have mainly been targeted at containing the virus outbreaks by limiting social contacts and mass gatherings. A large part of the response was directed to the recovery of the touristic sector but also to provide economic support to low-income and marginalized communities. Implemented measures for safeguarding the fragile socio-economic households' situation included economic support to pay the rent, food aids, improved access to credit and family and child protective services, and temporary shelters for needy persons and street sleepers. Several measures to remove the obstacles to digital access were also applied.

Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).

It can be described as an integrated territorial assistance (public-private social), cross-cultural (involving both native and immigrant populations in conditions of marginality), multidisciplinary, and based on community involvement system

Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)

Works for a social-health organisation that provides care to houseless/homeless and migrant populations. Works for a social-health association that operates with a mobile unit within the city of Rome to provide health care to the houseless/homeless population or living in precarious housing conditions. Works for a social enterprise whose purpose is to contribute to the wellbeing and development of an inclusive community through the activation of interventions and services in the social, educational and psychological fields. Is responsible for a shelter for mothers (victims of violence and victims of sex trafficking) with minor children.

Actor Systems (A)

Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)

Vulnerable groups included houseless/homeless citizens, the elderly, people with disabilities or psychological health problems, drug addicts, female victims of domestic violence, migrants, and asylum seekers and refugees (including unaccompanied minors and victims of torture).

Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

The CSOs represented by the interviewees, and CSOs in their professional networks, assist vulnerable groups such as houseless/homeless citizens, asylum seekers, refugees and other migrants, unaccompanied migrant minors, youth with disabilities, and vulnerable women

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

At a regional level several measures were activated to support people and reduce the spread of the virus like the APP LAZIO DOCTOR for Covid (LAZIODrCOVID) that was launched in order to receive remote emergency medical assistance and facilitate access to dedicated home tele-assistance services to chronic or frail patients, and the dematerialized prescription where patients could pick up their medication directly at the pharmacies using an "Electronic Prescription Number" (NRE), that doctors provided

Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

Some CSOs had to implement changes so to adapt continuously to new ministerial decrees during the pandemic. Spaces that had been created to assist the need of certain vulnerable groups had to be adapted to needs of other, newly-vulnerable community members. Some organizations also had to reorient their mandates, implementing services beyond their main services.

Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

Italy has experienced a strong wave of participatory practices since the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic. Online psychological support, healthcare and

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

The municipality has repeatedly asked for support from associations, both international and grassroots in different areas. Specific administrative subdivisions sometimes promoted initiatives informed by localised conditions and concerns. CSOs and cultural spaces that have deep roots in particular districts sometimes dedicated resources to the pandemic response

Outcomes (O)

Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

Residents took the initiative and collaborated with local CSOs to provide help to people in need of assistance. Particularly in the second phase of the pandemic, residents showed solidarity and offered help in any way they could. They started reflecting on possibilities to help the most vulnerable in their communities, and established semi-autonomous systems of support. The pandemic made citizens more aware about vulnerable groups in their neighborhoods, and drove them to rethink the meaning of "community". It was further noted that local CSOs experienced increased interest on the part of volunteers who wanted to be part of the response.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No substantial changes were observed

COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Due to the decentralization of power granted by the Italian Constitution, the Regional Ministry of Health made some adjustments to the Governmental strategy in relation mainly to the vaccination campaign

Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

In support of vulnerable populations, INTERSOS a private sector initiative has rapidly adapted the activities of the INTERSOS24 Center (active since 2016 in partnership with UNICEF Italy with an ambulatory health clinic, a safe space, and a mobile team) to the mobility's restrictions implemented by the government. Preventive measures were implemented addressing the homeless population and the population in conditions of social exclusion, in order to guarantee the protection of their health and support the Regional Health System of Latium. International organisations (Médécins Sans Frontières for example) also contributed to participatory practices

Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Operational challenges were raised for CSOs since they had to implement changes continuously to adapt to new ministerial decrees during the pandemic. Spaces that had been created to assist the need of certain vulnerable groups had to be adapted to needs of other, newly-vulnerable community members. Some organizations also had to reorient their mandates, implementing services beyond their main services.

Actor Systems (A)

New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

The economic impact of the pandemic was profound. Many people were left unemployed or experienced a substantial drop of their income, some were even forced to live in the streets,

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

The pandemic has further exacerbated the already existing social inequalities and the longstanding rent crises, putting at high risk of social exclusion a big portion of the urban population

COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

In some cities, especially in Northern Italy, the COVID-19 pandemic had a heavy psychological impact: people suffered not only for the deaths of their loved ones, but also for the regret for not having been

present, the lack of a shared ritual with others to witness life and

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The Metropolitan City of Rome implemented several measures to remove the obstacles to digital access like The Metropolitan Wi-Fi Network Project that was extended and the delivery of digital devices to high school students in need, to provide them the tools to access remote learning activities. Also RomaAiutaRoma was a site created by Rome municipality as a single access point to all information relevant to the emergency management of the pandemic ranging from real-time updates on the services of the local government up to solidarity initiatives such as help with shopping psychological support and 24h reception for homeless people.

Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

There was a great mobilisation to respond to the housing emergency. One organisation that stepped up to help was Binario95, which launched the online campaign #VorreiRestareACasa [I would like to stay at home] to support persons in need of housing, mainly homeless, via an online fundraising and increasing shelter services.

Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

The most prominent such initiative is COVID19Italia.help, which was led by volunteers from different organisations such as ActionAid and EmergenzeHackaiming to connect requests for help and offers of goods and services in the various Italian cities. Additionally ANPAS, a non-profit voluntary organisation has launched a similar project, anpas.ushahidi.io, to disseminate information about services of its associations and volunteer networks to people stuck in their homes because of health problems/quarantine.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5):

a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

The pandemic "awakened" local communities, resulting in the creation of a network between CSOs, public and governmental authorities, international organizations, volunteers, and residents, thus increasing cooperation on minimizing the pandemic's effects. CSOs sometimes initiated and led cooperation with authorities and other organisations at all operational levels. In addition the municipality has repeatedly asked for support from associations, both international and grassroots in different areas.

Outcomes (O)

Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

Governmental responses were formulated far away from local communities and did not always appropriately address those communities' needs. Due to significant regional decentralisation, the measures adopted and initiatives promoted have differed in number and in terms of resources allocated per region. Even within large cities, there have been some districts more supportive than others, mainly because of higher concentration of vulnerable people, but also depending on whether relevant civil society organisations or supportive networks were already present in a given district. Nonetheless improved contact and coordination between communities and CSOs was observed. Civil society associations were crucial in the management of the pandemic in Rome, and it was mentioned that they were a key player with whom government authorities worked efficiently to provide assistance, treatments, and vaccines.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No substantial changes were observed

COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

The large number of ministerial decrees, made it difficult to establish long term projections:

Vaccination priority rules

Due to the decentralization of power the Regional Ministry of Health made some adjustments to the Governmental strategy in relation mainly to the applied timeline of the vaccination campaign which was acknowledged to be quite successful, but its mandatory nature created scepticism and mistrust. With regard to vulnerable refugee and migrant populations cultural aspects and language were acknowledged to be the most critical limitations to both COVID-19 communication campaigns and vaccination campaigns.

Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

Specific administrative subdivisions sometimes promoted initiatives formed by localised conditions and concerns. For instance, Municipality XIII Roma Aurelio promoted the solidarity service campaign La Spesa Sospesa [Suspended Spending] to create a virtuous network to support people in difficulty.

Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

As already stated previously

Actor Systems (A)

New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

Major impacts were observed particularly in health care facilities and elderly care facilities, as well as among health care practitioners. Not only those from vulnerable communities, but also key workers, women, enterprises, students, and culture professionals that majorly affected by the pandemic needed help and support.

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Even though the pandemic exacerbated social differences within the community it brought greater cohesion and interest among those who lived in the same spaces.

COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The social issues that the pandemic has highlighted may be regarded as landmarks representative of permanent impacts on peoples' physical and psychological states and daily lives. Especially long

PORTUGAL

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
Awareness raising and food distribution to vulnerable citizens and beneficiaries.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)
In Lisbon before the beginning of the COVID 19 pandemic, CSOs were providing assistance, support, and relief to people dealing with severe socioeconomic difficulties such as extreme poverty, job insecurity, or unemployment; ethnic, racial or gender discrimination; domestic violence; social exclusion; and/or houseless/homelessness.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

According to interviewees, before and particularly during the first phase of the pandemic, there was a sharp aggravation of needs resulting from the fact that the general population's income dramatically dropped, in addition to a significant decrease in the capacity of institutions to provide some kinds of support.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)

Due to high infection rates among older people, especially within nursing homes, long-term facilities themselves took the initiative and established telephone or web-based visits, to ensure that residents could keep in touch with their families. Furthermore facilities used social media as platforms to update families and carers on the residents' health status. A practice that continued to exist during COVID-19 too.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
- Alentejo is the bigger region in Portugal with a total area of 31,603 km².
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
- In March 2020 in Portugal there were already municipalities testing the elderly in long term care facilities, due to a governmental program of COVID-19 testing across nursing homes staff, which started in April 2020 thanks to a partnership established by the government with scientific institutions and municipalities.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
- Pluralistic socio-cultural non-governmental organisations
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
- "Active in a member of the board of a social solidarity organization in Lisbon that provides different kinds of support to visually impaired people, whose duties are based on providing advice to the board in all aspects."
- "A founding member of a social solidarity organization in Lisbon that provides different kinds of support to a community with multiple vulnerabilities, whose duties are essentially based on providing technical guidance to community intervention teams and project management."
- "Active as an executive director of a social solidarity institution that provides support at various levels to a community of migrants with multiple vulnerabilities, whose duties are essentially related to ensuring the sustainability of the institution."

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
Mostly elderly living in long term care facilities or nursing homes.
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Elderly, handicapped, migrants.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Vaccination in elderly care facilities in Portugal started on the 4th of January 2021, while on the 17th of February registers showed that over 170,000 elderly and staff had already been vaccinated.

The Portuguese Governmental program of COVID-19 testing across nursing homes staff started in April 2020 due to a partnership established by the government with scientific institutions and municipalities of the Alentejo region.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

Most of the CSOs were active mainly, but not exclusively, at a local level, engaging in the field/on the street with highly vulnerable communities and social groups that prior to the pandemic already faced great challenges in terms of living conditions and deprivation of basic goods (e.g., food and housing), but also access to social and health support.

- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

As the Portuguese region with the highest ageing index, Alentejo was confronted with significant challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic, forcing multiple support networks within the population to be formed, in which ordinary residents came together and supported each other, particularly in smaller places, where people are closer, mutual aid networks took shape much faster than in large urban settings.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

Interviewees characterised the second period of the pandemic as marked mainly by the coordinated and intensive efforts of their and other CSOs, in order to cover basic needs such as food distribution (by setting up food banks), essential products provision, and healthcare assistance for vulnerable groups.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

CSOs presented a variety of drawbacks, in relation to the pandemic management, which were mostly related to breaks in services and institutional activities, the lack of a clear strategic plan, inconsistent communication, and fake news. According to interviewees, specific drawbacks included incomplete communication of critical information, delays in services, and restrictions on their CSOs' activities, fake news and sensationalism. For most CSOs, the main positive impacts, were the environmental (carbon) impact due to a significant decrease in movement; digital skill acquisition; increased solidarity among the members of the community; and a new appreciation of the value of human relationships.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

On a local level in the Lisbon and Tagus Valley region infrastructures were created to support people in isolation or quarantine; support networks that contributed to restore some social and psychological normality in disruptive times; and individual preventive behaviours that could reduce the rate of virus transmission.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

Interviewees highlighted the new role of CSOs in carrying out awareness-raising actions: e.g., distributing informational material and releasing audiovisual media with practical guidelines, such as videos on how to wash your hands, how to use a mask, the safety of vaccines for young people, etc.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

CSOs had to provide guidance and psychological support to enable people to cope with the new and unknown circumstances imposed by the pandemic.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Interviewees acknowledged that the awareness campaign improved over time, eventually managing to change many people's behaviour. COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
The general population was impacted severely, particularly from a financial and psychological perspective.

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The post-vaccination period had promising practices such as: the continuous revision of the contingency plan to reflect any updates to the guidelines set forth by the Directorate-General of Health and other relevant competent authorities, the emergency protocol with the nearest primary health care centers for a quick response in case of an outbreak, the systematic maintenance of an inventory of PPE in close collaboration with governmental authorities, and the use of social media and other platforms to update families and carers on residents' well-being, and on the public health measures that the nursing home is developing.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

According to the interviewees it was acknowledged that all involved stakeholders have been making significant efforts to regain their normal modus operandi – although in many cases, all activities and services have still not yet resumed.

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

An interviewee argued that the pandemic created greater awareness among the population regarding the need to help each other, because the long pandemic phase offered the time and room to think about solidarity more deeply, which motivated some individuals to act and start their own initiatives.

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

In the metropolitan area of Lisbon, established, donation-supported CSOs sometimes proved unable to scale up their activity of supporting marginalised people and groups to the degree required by the new crisis situation. For example, in the domain of hunger prevention, longstanding CSOs such as ReFood could not always meet the needs of the newly food-insecure households.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
- No radical changes in municipality were identified.
- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Gradual disengagement from strict measures.

- Vaccination priority rules

Vulnerable groups were prioritised, such as the elderly.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

No radical changes can be identified.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Ibid.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

For most interviewees, the main positive impact, was the increased solidarity among the members of the community; and a new appreciation of the value of human relationships, while the negative impact was the restriction of community activities in the field/on the street, a lack of transparency and consistency in governmental communication and decision processes, and generalized demotivation throughout society.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

Most visible, were the economic vulnerabilities in all of the Alentejo region.

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

According to CSO representatives, changes occurred within psychological and social relationships, but these changes are unlikely to permanently alter the fabric of the community in the Alentejo region.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

Gradual disengagement from measures by the municipal authorities had an impact to the general public who could slowly return to their daily lives.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

SPAIN

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)

Programs offering professional support from Social Services to caregivers and support for single parent households, assistance to any kind of violence victim but more especially to women who suffer abuse, deployment of violence detection systems with special attention to women, programs that offer remote social and medical services like the Home Telecare (TAD), policies that target homeless people because of their extreme situation, suicide prevention strategies among risk groups, a Pathological Grief prevention Program and the Compassionate Communities program that generate support and accompaniment networks for people and families in mourning, Mutual Help Groups for people with mental health issues and the Vallecas Labora programme, aimed at the socio-occupational insertion of people at risk of social exclusion.

What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)

Services promoting the integration of migrants into Spanish society through reception programmes, information, legal and employment advice, school support, employment training, programmes to reduce the digital divide, health education programmes and refer people to the health and social services of the public system. programmes of legal advice, psychological care, and protection of children and women who suffer gender violence.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

The political representatives of the city of Madrid, agreed to work together to get through the different consequences of the pandemic in every area of the region. They created and approved a Coordination Table for Agreements designed to modernize the city and reduce inequalities, containing specific measures to tackle the sanitary and socioeconomic crisis in the areas of social services and housing, health and security services, urban space and sustainable mobility and vulnerable groups while other measures were devoted to boost the economic recovery and safeguard employment.

Outcomes (O)

Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)

The FrenaLaCurva (Stop the Curve) initiative, a citizen platform and community, which progressed into a grass-roots project aimed at bringing together the numerous civic initiatives which were spontaneously being set up to meet local needs. Volunteers, entrepreneurs, civil servants, and social organisations used the channel to organise social energy and civic resilience, involving more than 2,000 activists from more than 300 social organisations

Governance Systems (GS)

What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)

At the subnational level, Spain is organised into 17 Autonomous Communities and two Autonomous Cities. The Spanish regions are parliamentary sub-political systems, whose governments are elected by their own regional parliaments.

What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)

The pandemic has not impacted, the political structures of local governments, since they do not have direct competences in the main policy areas to fight the COVID-19 expansion. However, some of them such as policing, emergency health services, social services and communication strategies in support to regional and national governments, have been key to mitigate its consequences in cooperation with other levels of government

Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).

A multi-dimensional, socio-cultural, resident participatory network of grass-roots, local, regional, national and international initiatives

Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)

A decision-maker at a CSO that works with migrants, primarily from South America

A decision-maker and psychologist at a CSO that works with vulnerable populations at local level

A first-line practitioner at a CSO that works with vulnerable women

A first-line practitioner at the Madrid office of a worldwide health CSO that works with socially excluded populations

A decision-maker at the Madrid office of a well-established national CSO that aims to protect the rights of women and their children and to eradicate gender violence

Actor Systems (A)

Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)

People who are in a situation of social exclusion, especially young migrants, migrant women, single-mother households, women in prostitution or sexual exploitation, female victims of gender violence and transgender people, homeless people or people living on the streets

Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Ibid

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

Citizen political participation continued through an online platform that facilitated both communication of residents with the Madrid City Council and deliberations in citizen forums about local issues that rose during the confinement.

Also the Ministry of Health took the unprecedented initiative to call up to 50.000 medical resident Interns, final year medical students, and retired doctors to be ready and available in case their services were required to support hospitals.

Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

CSOs focused primary at health measures by distributing hygiene products in the streets and educating people regarding socio-health issues as well as providing psychological health assistance but also helped guarantee and provide basic needs such as food and basic necessities

Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

One of the initiatives promoted by self-organised ordinary people through social networks in Spain was the Cartas venceremos al COVID-19 (We will beat COVID-19 letters). These were letters of solidarity and encouragement addressed to COVID-19 patients. The case of the Coronavirus makers initiative, a collaborative project in which volunteer engineers, designers, researchers, doctors, and techies dedicated themselves to making facial masks and automatic respirators for hospitals with 3D printers during the quarantine is another example

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

Multiple voluntary and solidarity initiatives were launched to respond to different areas, where people required support due to the pandemic. Volunteers were sending solidarity letters to people suffering from isolation and loneliness, several platforms were established to connect people offering support with people requesting support, telephone support lines were introduced, or virtual meeting spaces for exchange of actors from various sectors were generated.

The Rey Juan Carlos University has created an initiative that helps older people to take out their trash during the state of alarm in Madrid.

A group of Metro de Madrid has mobilized thousands of people via social media channels to raise funds for vulnerable people. With their initiative, they were able to provide resources for health centers, senior citizens, essential products, or food for vulnerable people.

Outcomes (O)

Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

Although the contribution of CSOs was crucial in the management of the pandemic, they continued their operation without receiving substantial public resources. They utilized only the available sources, and, in some cases, they received donations, voluntary work, and a lot of personal effort. Nonetheless the role of volunteers was crucial, for many national NGOs to scale up their intervention action plans

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

Public social services were shut down and local administration was closed to the public

COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

Since public administrations were shut down during lockdowns, CSOs were operating continuously to socially accompany the most vulnerable people (especially women) throughout the pandemic, despite strict confinement and mobility restrictions

Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

Addressing the needs of vulnerable populations was achieved in the case of Madrid with public policy networks involving governmental actors and civil society associations

Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

CSOs increased their online and phone assistance because of the volume of requests, while acknowledging that face-to-face interaction is preferable

Actor Systems (A)

New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

COVID-19 increased the vulnerable population and affected mostly those who are living already in poor conditions. Furthermore, delays or obstacles in accessing the public health system led to insufficient medical care or psychological health issues, which were caused by the stress of experiencing economic difficulties

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Households and people who were already living in poor economic circumstances and employment, and did not have any economic support such as migrants and female migrant workers were majorly affected

COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The loss of economic capacity because of wage reduction was especially sharp among single parent households and couples with children increasing the demand for social assistance

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

the Madrid City Council channelled the provision of food through the Tarjeta Familias (Families Card programme), a financial assistance programme managed through the social services of the Madrid City Council, similar to a bank card that allows low-income families to buy food and hygiene products in supermarkets and shops in the Community of Madrid.

Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

Through their initiatives vaccination was made available and accessible to vulnerable groups while they additionally assisted families to adapt in the new era of digitalization by providing laptops and internet connections, or by educating people to carry out activities online

Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

An emblematic example of the role of volunteers was the Plan Cruz Roja RESPONDE (Red Cross RESPONDS Plan), an initiative aimed at mitigating the social and health emergency, which involved public-private collaboration and more than 12.000 volunteers mobilized throughout the country, through whom aid was channelled to assist 1.350.000 people through the delivery of more than 80.000 bags of food and medicines, 540.000 masks and protective equipment and 27.000 kits of basic personal hygiene products during the peak months of the pandemic

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

The collaboration between public institutions, NGOs, and ordinary residents was particularly effective in reaching the most vulnerable and hard-to-reach target population, such as people living or sleeping on the streets. The channelling of social and health care to this population was carried out mainly through the collaboration between SAMUR Social, Madrid Salud, the Social Services of Madrid City Council, and some NGOs with active work on the streets. An example is the campaign to vaccinate homeless people or women in situations of sexual exploitation

Outcomes (O)

Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

CSOs faced various obstacles to access the measures or aid granted by the different public administrations. The digital, linguistic, and bureaucratic gaps were highlighted as the main limitations for accessing this aid and as the main drawbacks to successfully carrying out their intervention. Also the procedures for accessing these financial aids were complex and required documents that were difficult to file quickly and easily. Nonetheless CSOs showcased great adaptability adapting their work methodology and programmes in order to respond immediately to the new needs and the social and health challenges posed by the pandemic

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

None substantial change was observed

COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

The tasks of the local governments have consisted in assisting other levels of government by helping them in controlling the observance of their disposals, adding resources to protect vulnerable population, offering analysis to generate quality information to deal with the pandemic; and, finally, throughout information campaigns to make citizens aware of the crisis and how to respond to assure self-protection.

Vaccination priority rules

The vaccination campaigns are considered to be successful. However, some gaps, were identified especially regarding communicating on when and how to get vaccinated as well as how to use the COVID-19 certificate. CSOs helped fill this gap by creating relevant material in multiple languages to address this issue and reach different migrant and migration-background populations. Also a dedicated vaccination campaign was carried out with the aim of maximising the effectiveness of the immunization of homeless people living in shelters in Madrid and on the streets, by simplifying the logistics needed to vaccinate this group

Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

CSOs were from the beginning in the frontline providing social services in order to minimize the pandemic impact on vulnerable populations and continued their work primary face-to face but with measures to avoid overcrowded situations

Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

Many CSOs activities shifted to digitization but also hybrid participatory initiatives also emerged, carried out simultaneously through both online platforms and face-to-face mutual aid networks

New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
People and families in mourning and people with mental problems especially among the young population were also a recognized as vulnerable

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

Street work and visits to distribute essential need products such as food, clothes continued. Even though the pandemic demanded telework, CSOs acknowledge the importance of working in the streets were most of the vulnerable populations may need assistance

COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

As already stated previously:

SWEDEN

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)
Healthcare and hospitalisation has been administered by the VGR, and care of elderly persons and persons with disabilities by the Gothenburg municipality. However, the handling of the pandemic involved more sectors than only healthcare and elderly care. In order to facilitate cooperation and mobilisation between public institutions, agencies, business and social partners, the forum West-Swedish Group (Västsvensk samling) was established. Its main purpose was to inform the business and labour market within the region about the pandemic and its consequences.
- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)
Provision of healthcare services and counselling as "vaccination guides"/health guides/cultural interpreters for local communities and marginalized groups.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
CSOs cooperated with SU, a system of hospitals associated with the University of Gothenburg, while disseminated information to citizens in multiple languages and cooperated with local community leaders (such as mosques and churches who had the role of information ambassador.)

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)
Health ambassadors utilized a variety of means and methods to communicate with the local community such as Facebook and Whatsapp groups, nevertheless, they were supported to a certain degree by the municipal governmental structure, therefore, the percentage of completely self-organized initiatives at the first phase is unclear.

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
Västra Götaland (VGR) region, municipalities in Gothenburg (Ale, Alingsås, Härryda, Kungälv, Lerum, Lilla Edet, Mölndal, Partille, Stenungsund, Tjörn, Öckerö, and Kungsbacka). Highly decentralised system, At the regional level, 12 regional councils and 9 regional bodies are responsible for financing and delivering health services to citizens. At the local level, 290 municipalities are responsible for care of the elderly and the disabled. In the municipality/city of Gothenburg, the VGR region provides healthcare to the citizens through 64 health centres (28 public, 36 private), one major public university hospital, Sahlgrenska University Hospital (SU) and one private hospital, Carlanderska Sjukhuset. SU is a system of hospitals associated with the University of Gothenburg
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
The municipality implemented policies and practices (non-pharmaceutical interventions) that contained the spread of the virus and measures to mitigate the negative health and socio-economic impact, which contrary to other countries were not as strict and had a voluntary character.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
"Very segregated" and "full of immigrants [from different countries] speaking different languages"
· Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
"Local hospital providing health-promoting advice and activities" and cultural interpreters working in Bergsjön with the nearby neighbourhoods of Gamlestan, Körtedala, and Kviberg.

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
Ethnic minorities, migrants, citizens living in poverty, healthcare workers, elderly, homeless and substance addicted citizens .
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Ibid.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

No apparent changes in the modus operandi of municipal governmental organizations. The municipality/city of Gothenburg provided care in nursing homes, housing for people with disabilities, daily activities and home health care.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

In Sweden, CSO employees, particularly cultural mediators were challenged by certain barriers, especially dealing with distrust and disinformation. Moreover, according to most interviewees, the uncertainty of their employment situations and the uncomfortable working conditions as potential threats to the sustainability of the working role, contributed to their uneasiness.

- Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

Food distribution, daily live activities assistance provision, information dissemination and psychological support, combating misinformation.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

The city of Gothenburg established cooperation with bicultural/bilingual women as "health guides/vaccine guides" specifically to fill systemic weaknesses. Health/vaccine guides, utilized their own social networks to promote health-protective behaviours and improve vaccine uptake, at a later phase, among migrants.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

Interviewees in Sweden take great pride in their work, which they assess as successful, nevertheless suggest that their working conditions can be harsh, indicate low payment, while also plagued by employment insecurity. *"we work, you know, mostly outdoors. Sometimes at night, it's so cold out, at eight, nine PM [...] We have to risk all the time to be outside among people, and we have a family at home. It's not a lot of pay. It's not like they [employers] think a lot about us."* *"Especially lately, we've become better known, with different agencies and radio and television has focused more on our work."*

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
- No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)
- COVID-19 rules and guidelines experienced a constant change, which made the work of CSOs more challenging.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
- The CSO ecosystem did not radically change. CSOs however agree that without involving mediators who understood the culture and spoke the language, it would have been very difficult to create bridges between cultural divides.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)
- No radical changes occurred within the structures of CSOs.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

Pre-existing vulnerabilities, particularly socio-economically challenged areas, were increased. This was the case of north-eastern Gothenburg which was described as an area with socioeconomic challenges. The interviewees argued that many of the residents in the target area are poorly integrated with Swedish society.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

All interviewees also argued that the target group often had little education and language skills, both in their native languages as in Swedish, as well as low health literacy.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

The general population was impacted severely, which is evident by the change in course of action and abandonment of the "herd immunity" as a governmental response.

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The municipality of Gothenburg actively engaged in activities and social media pages/groups. initiatives to disseminate accurate COVID-19 information within migration-background communities, such as an informational meeting in Ljungby Municipality proactively organised Arabic-speaking assistant nurse Hanin Mshenesh in cooperation with the regional government and a local Islamic association Kids Hack the Crisis, organised by UNICEF Sweden, invited children on a global level to participate in a hackathon to find sustainable solutions to challenges posed on them by COVID-19 pandemic. Other practices targeted a wide range of psychologically and socially vulnerable groups

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

A page on Facebook, Låt Live Leva founded by the arts agency Jubel, invites musicians to play in a digital festival, giving them the opportunity to perform and earn income. #vitecherupp (#quicksearch), gathers examples from the tech and IT businesses that contribute to fighting the pandemic. GP hjärta GBG managed by a newspaper offered regional and local enterprises free adds, Action Against Corona92, invited companies on a global level to engage in solutions for problems created by the pandemic situation. Gatans lag (Law of the streets), an organisation that works with drug addicts, ex-criminals, and people suffering from mental illness, arranged activities outdoors during the pandemic for their members to meet and talk. Kvinnojouren Online (Women's Shelter Online), a support hotline for victims of gender violence, which expanded their operations during the pandemic and proactively disseminated information on gender violence in cooperation with local authorities. Several practices were directed at youth and children, who have suffered socially and educationally due to lockdown. God Hjälp (Good Help), an initiative founded by established CSO Good Cause, which organised volunteers to deliver food to the elderly for free Corona

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

Hjälp till med inköp av livsmedel till riskgrupper! (Corona - Helping to buy food for at-risk groups) and Coronahjälp Fyrstad (Corona Help Fyrstad) Facebook groups founded by self-organised residents where people could ask for and offer help with everyday tasks like shopping for groceries. Enabling sharing of experiences: e.g., Vi som har/har haft corona (we who have/had Corona) and COVID-19, Vi som är drabbade (COVID-19, we who are affected).

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

CSOs interacted in the municipal government, other CSOs, their target groups and the general population more intensively this phase, particularly on the virtual domain, utilizing social media platforms such as Facebook and whatsapp.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

A vast number of initiatives conducted by municipal organisations, CSOs and citizen-led initiatives can be characterised successful such as Facebook-groups for people with long-term effects of the infection. Digital technology and social media were essential for public authorities and organisations, as well as for the public, to communicate, locate individual needs and offer support. Another conclusion is that spontaneous civic initiatives emerged where authorities and established organisations failed to reach, mostly at societal micro level.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
No radical changes can be identified.

· COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)
Gradual disengagement from COVID-19 measures.

- Vaccination priority rules
Vulnerable groups were prioritised.

· Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)
No radical changes can be identified, however CSOs became more encompassing.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)
Ibid.

Actor Systems (A)

· New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
The spectrum of vulnerability was broadened, similarly to other countries, and included among other vulnerable groups, children, the elderly, members of marginalised and deprived groups, victims of domestic abuse etc.

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
No radical changes can be identified with the CSOs, it is unclear if the roles of cultural mediators and health ambassadors continued to be plagued by employment uncertainty.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site
Gradual disengagement from measures had a similar impact to the general public who could slowly return to their daily lives.

WALES

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What services were offered by municipal governmental organisations? (from D6.1)

Welsh governmental organisations provided awareness raising and distribution of essential need items to beneficiaries and socio-economically vulnerable citizens.

- What services were offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)? (from D6.3)

Organisations such as FNA-UK (Filipino UK Nurses Association) and British Indian Nurses Association (BINA260), 'Diverse Cymru' created a BAME Mental Health Online/Telephone support project in December 2020 to support Black, Asian, and minority ethnic people across Wales who struggled with their mental health.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

- What were pre-pandemic patterns of interaction between CSOs and... (from D6.1 & D6.3): a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population
- CSOs attended weekly and monthly meetings with the Welsh Government to make changes to the way GRT communities were addressed and governed. CSOs sometimes took their own initiative to supplement governmental campaigns: for instance, the interviewee's group set up a (private/restricted) Facebook page that enabled the usage of voice-messaging for people who couldn't read or write very well.

Outcomes (O)

- Which are the bottom-up grassroots initiatives that can be identified during this phase, if such self-organized activities emerged? (contemporary initiatives)

N/A

Governance Systems (GS)

- What is the government structure of the municipality? (from D6.1)
Swansea is the second largest city in Wales and the regional commercial centre for South West Wales. Swansea Council consists of 32 Electoral Wards, represented by 75 local Councillors.
- What is the responsibility of the municipality (and/or region) in crisis management? (from D6.1)
The municipality implemented policies and practices (non-pharmaceutical interventions) that contained the spread of the virus and measures to mitigate the negative health and socio-economic impact, particularly emphasizing in risk communication.
- Brief description of CSO ecosystem in target site (from D6.3).
Target communities in the UK, including Wales include: people with learning disabilities and Black, Asian and minority ethnic populations (BAME) people.
- Pseudonymised description of interviewees' CSOs (from D6.3)
Engagement officers with BAME communities for a local municipal councils, CSOs in the Swansea area during the pandemic and policy researchers at women's labour organisation in South Wales.

Actor Systems (A)

- Description of vulnerable groups in the target site (from D6.3)
People with learning disabilities and Black, Asian and minority ethnic populations (BAME) people.
- Description of what vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)
Ibid.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

The Welsh government launched its £24 million “Welsh Government Third Sector COVID-19 Response Fund” on 27 March 2020 to help charities and third sector organisations financially through the crisis, improve possibilities for organising volunteering and streamlining volunteering, and supporting the volunteering infrastructure. More specified funding support schemes for grants or loans are also made available through the Third Sector Support Wales by trusts, foundations, and companies for existing civilian clubs related to social causes, sports, hobbies and interests, and neighbourhoods.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees’ CSOs; if known, CSOs in general) (from D6.3)

CSOs such as the Swansea Mosque worked to fill the gaps left by the governmental structure. First, they organised a broadcasting system for guided prayers before, after, and during Ramadan that enabled people to better exercise their faith while remaining in their homes during the lockdowns. Later, when it became apparent that BAME people and Muslims amongst them did not follow up recommendations because of misinformation the Mosque promoted the vaccine by providing correct information.

Did participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) emerge in the municipality in response to COVID-19? (D6.5)

Multiple grassroots initiatives launched regular information briefings on pandemic measures or vaccinations. Some initiatives were launched to express concerns about the vulnerability of certain groups, as for example people with learning disabilities.

TIMEFRAME

T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5):
a) Municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

CSOs such as the Mosque Foodbank made over 2000 food parcels available for people in need and provided information on COVID-19 relevant measures and guidelines. CSOs in Wales, such as charity Learning Disability Wales and self-advocacy group for people with learning disabilities *All Wales People First* collaborated to express concerns about the potential for harm done to people with learning disabilities if the government and National Health Service (NHS) Wales do not take into consideration the effects of a reduction or diminished quality of care and inadequate communication styles.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees’ assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)

COVID-19 had aggravated certain existing (intersectional) inequalities and power disparities. Discrimination, incidents of racist abuse were seen to increase. Inequities between men and women regarding their work progression and career prospects, In GRT communities, the impositions of restrictions did not reify existing social roles, This limitation drove many people to become newly reliant on benefits, which they did not like, as they felt as if since they don’t contribute to the State (via tax), they should not receive anything from the State. On the other hand, vulnerable people were helped in ways not possible before the pandemic as patterns of solidarity and the new interpretations of vulnerability emerged. Moreover, pressure from the pandemic promoted CSO operational changes..

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)

No radical changes in municipality were identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

No radical changes in COVID-19 rules and guidelines were noted.

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

The pandemic has likely changed the (geographically situated) reference communities in various ways. New patterns of mutual support and joint action within BAME and Muslim communities appear to be sustainable. The pandemic has promoted a (re)invigorated community feeling which the community has held on to by setting up projects around health, wellbeing, and leisure (e.g. yoga and swimming groups for Muslim women in Port Talbot).

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees’ CSOs (if relevant)

Operational changes occurred within interviewee CSOs which according to the interviewees was a positive outcome.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site

Pre-existing vulnerabilities, particularly socio-economically challenged areas, were increased. This was the case of BAME communities, which are described as areas with socioeconomic challenges.

- Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee’s CSO works with (from D6.3)

N/A

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

N/A

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in services / new services offered by municipal governmental organisations (from D6.1)

No change in the modus operandi of municipal governmental organisations was identified.

- Changes in services / new services offered by CSOs in the municipality (interviewees' CSOs; if known, CSOs in general)

CSOs who actively engaged with the BAME communities, suggested operational changes, but with the exception to their services. During this phase, CSOs actively provided essential need items such as food and information awareness services.

- Changes in participatory practices (e.g., in which ordinary residents played a significant role) (D6.5)

In the county and city of Swansea, the target municipality in Wales, voluntary participative action strongly increased at the beginning of the pandemic (late March 2020). From averaging at 80 new sign-ups for volunteering in the 2 years prior, the March-April 2020 sign-up list stopped just short of 1600 new volunteers (Urban Foundry 2020). New organisations, including spontaneous groups, have been supported with advice and help to constitute and review their governance to respond to the new emerging needs during the crisis, such as food banks. These initiatives include:

- 4x4 Response Wales - South Wales: £2000 - Delivery service;
- • Pontarddulais Partnership: £3000 – foodbank;
- • Welsh Hearts: £5000 - Defibrillators in the community;
- • GSP Partnership: £500 - Contribution to core costs during COVID-19 lockdown;
- • Morrision Tabernacle: £500 – Newsletter to local residents;
- • Iberian and Latin American Association: £200 - To support refugees and asylum seekers;
- • South Wales MSTC Ltd: £577 – Staff training in preparation for restarting service;
- • Race Council Cymru: £2000 – To support international students in Swansea.
- Two addition groups were funded using Comic Relief VSEF Fund in July 2020:
 - • Llamau: £3000 – IT for remote working for outreach staff;
 - • National Autistic Society - Swansea branch: £2825 – Costs of online training.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Post-vaccination

Interaction Area (I)

- How did CSOs interact with (from D6.3 & D6.5): a) municipal governmental organisations; b) other CSOs; c) their target groups; d) the general population

CSOs interacted in the municipal government, other CSOs, their target groups and the general population intensively during this phase as well, particularly in the vaccination and information awareness efforts. The efforts of Mosques and the 'Tell Me More' campaign in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot, in which community leaders were video-recorded getting the vaccine and explaining why it was good, are good indicators of this case.

Outcomes (O)

- Interviewees' assessments of what worked well and what went poorly (qualitative) (from D6.3 & D6.5)
- CSOs in particular suggest that the operationalisation of a 'vaccine van' in the Swansea and Neath Port Talbot municipalities that was based on the 'Tell Me More Campaign', was highly successful. Stocked with AstraZeneca vaccines, the van is driven to particular sites where particular groups congregate who, on average, have responded to vaccination invitations to lesser extent. This includes a particular church that serve people with Caribbean origin, a mosque to offer jobs to attending Muslims, and certain streets to invite sex workers to have a vaccine.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in the government structure of the municipality (if relevant)
- No radical changes can be identified.

- COVID-19 rules, restrictions, recommendations, etc. issued on a sub-national level (if relevant)

N/A

- Vaccination priority rules

N/A

- Changes in the CSO ecosystem in target site (if relevant)

No radical changes can be identified.

- Changes in the structure of the interviewees' CSOs (if relevant)

CSOs became more encompassing and report changes on operational functions which consider them to be beneficial.

Actor Systems (A)

- New vulnerabilities / vulnerable groups in the target site
- The spectrum of vulnerability was broadened, similarly to other countries, and included among other vulnerable groups, children, the elderly, members of marginalised and deprived groups, victims of domestic abuse etc.

Changes affecting the vulnerable groups each interviewee's CSO works with (from D6.3)

The digitalised services, while CSOs are subject to their own set of access barriers, can be convenient for many residents, as well as for CSOs themselves; care must simply be taken to ensure that alternative pathways are kept available.

- COVID-19 impact on the general population in the target site

N/A